

**Enterprise Risk Management (ERM):
Developing an Enterprise Risk Management Adoption Framework
for the Algerian Insurance Industry**

A Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Doctor in Business Administration

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March 2024

Dedication

I dedicate this work to my parents, my sisters, my husband, and my lovely son.

Acknowledgement:

Before starting, I would like to reflect upon the past few years working on this research and thank those who have helped me throughout this journey with their constant love and support. I want to thank Dr Mona Althonayan my supervisor. I express my wholehearted gratitude for her continuous support and advice. My sincere thanks to my family for their love and support throughout this journey. Thanks to my husband for always being my biggest supporter in this journey.

Declaration

I declare that this work has not been submitted for any other degree or qualification within any university.

Word Count: 56892 (Excluding the table of contents and references)

Signed:

Date:

Abstract

Organisations must manage risk more effectively to survive the uncertainty of the business landscape. This applies to firms operating in the insurance industry since their primary function is risk management. Consequently, the present research aims to propose an Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption framework tailored to Algeria's insurance firms. Despite the increased attention from academics and practitioners towards ERM following the financial crisis of 2008, evidence on how it is adopted and implemented effectively across organisations is limited in the context of insurance firms. Moreover, regardless of the emergence of various ERM standards and frameworks, organizations need help adopting and aligning ERM to the leading strategies and objectives.

Moreover, the drivers for ERM and the obstacles associated with this adoption across Algerian insurance firms still need to be discovered. This may be because most studies have been conducted in developed countries. Thus, most available frameworks need clear implementation guidance, which can assist organisations in adopting and implementing ERM successfully. Therefore, this exploratory research investigated the drives and challenges facing insurance firms and adopting ERM in the Algerian insurance industry. To attain this, the study adopts an interpretive approach to investigate ERM adoption in an Algerian insurance firm. Data collection and analysis were conducted following a qualitative paradigm, assuming a case study as a research strategy involving a sample of 25 respondents directly or indirectly involved in the ERM adoption process.

The empirical findings of this research revealed that ERM adoption among the Algerian insurance industry is immature and remains early, evidenced by the need for an industry-specific adoption framework that considers the nature and needs of this industry. The empirical findings also emphasize the significance of the suggested adoption framework's

components for achieving successful ERM. Besides proposing an ERM adoption framework that addresses the specific challenges and concerns of the insurance industry regarding ERM adoption, another essential contribution of this research is the practical recommendations that intend to assist the studied insurance firm in enhancing its internal environment to achieve an effective ERM adoption and implementation.

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List of Abbreviations

Acronyms	Definition
AS/NZS	Australia/New Zealand
CAO	Chief Audit Officer
CAS	Casualty Actuarial Society
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
COSO	Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Tradeway Commission
CRO	Chief Risk Officer
ERM	Enterprise Risk Management
FEFRMA	Risk Management Standard Evolved by Federation of European Risk Management Association
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
IIA	Institute of Internal Audit
IRM	Institute of Risk Management
ISO	International Standard Organisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KRIs	Key Risk Indicators
PwC	Price Waterhouse Coopers
RIMS	Risk Management Society
US	United State of America

1 Chapter One:

1.1 Introduction

The primary aim of this Doctorate of Business Administration (DBA) dissertation revolves around scrutinising the adoption of enterprise risk management (ERM) within the Algerian insurance domain. The overarching objective is to construct a customised framework to fulfil the needs of insurance establishments in Algeria. It is commonly believed that the uptake and execution of ERM in insurance companies in Western countries have stemmed mainly from regulatory oversight. Thus, this study seeks to investigate the factors influencing the initiation and acceptance of ERM.

To provide a comprehensive roadmap for the research endeavour, this initial chapter will outline the trajectory for the study and the proposed ERM adoption framework. It will briefly introduce the study's context, mainly focusing on the Algerian geographical landscape. Additionally, it will examine the existing problem scenario, laying the groundwork for formulating relevant research questions. The chapter shall begin by offering an outline of the research's backdrop, followed by an intricate delineation of the research issue to validate the necessity for conducting this examination. Moreover, it shall elucidate the study aims, objectives, and queries it seeks to tackle. Furthermore, it will explore risk management practices within the insurance sector and the consequential importance of ERM for organisational efficiency. The chapter will also concisely discuss the significance of the research and its contributions to academic literature and practical applications. Finally, it will conclude by outlining the research's structure in subsequent chapters.

1.2 Research Background

The concepts discussed below will be discussed in detail in the following chapters; however, this chapter will address them briefly since they are the main elements upon which this research is based.

Over the past few decades, business organisations have run businesses beyond familiar local borders. High uncertainty and complexity are the characteristics of the current business environment compared to the past. Challenges facing organisations are more significant; therefore, risk exposure is higher (Caporale *et al.*, 2017). As the global economic scenario becomes increasingly unpredictable and volatile, the scope of uncertainties and risks increases, promoting the duplication of efforts in effectively dealing with those emerging risks (Beasley *et al.*, 2016).

Moreover, many businesses accumulated significant losses during the 2008 financial crisis that struck the world. The consequences of the 2008 financial crash have led several prominent corporations, such as Lehman Brothers Bank, to collapse and go bankrupt, losing more than \$ 691Billions of assets (Peck, 2016). Consequently, corporate frauds, bankruptcy, and other dynamics were among the major drivers for abandoning the traditional risk management (TRM) discipline of dealing with risks, most hazardous and insurable risks, to adopting the ERM approach that views risks from a wide-enterprise perspective that is more comprehensive for managing the diverse type of events. Unlike the traditional way of managing risks (TRM), which categorises risks and organises them independently (Hoyt and Liebenberg., 2008), ERM analyses and manages the entire risk portfolio of an organisation from an enterprise-wide perspective, helping organisations to achieve their organisational strategy and goals (Selamat & Ibrahim, 2018). Principally, Enterprise Risk Management improves the organisation's awareness of risk, leading to more intelligent decision-making and more efficient operations (Aljami, 2019).

Accordingly, the changes in the business environment have changed the way organisations manage risk, and such a trend has moved organisations toward an integrative and more comprehensive risk management approach known as ERM.

According to Gordon *et al.* (2009), ERM enables business organisations to shift their focus from being mainly defensive to becoming more offensive towards risks through its integrative way of managing them (Kauspadiene *et al.*, 2017).

Moreover, organisations have traditionally employed the "silo" approach to risk management, which generally looks at the individual effectiveness and performance of a business instead of a more holistic approach, which in contrast, looks at the long-term effect of risk and capital needs of the entire enterprise (Beasley *et al.*, 2019). For instance, in the traditional risk management approach, the finance department can manage liquidity, interest, and credit risks, while the IT departments can handle the privacy and security risks. Such specialisation is essential to developing various risk management enterprises within the organisation. However, the silo approach allows risk specialists to collaborate with other business units (Oulasvirta & Anttiroiko, 2017). Issues can arise when those different business units develop different risk philosophies. Risk management has become more strategic and elevated in most organisations. Most executive teams grasp the significance of risk management in attaining corporate goals and objectives (Fraser & Simkins, 2016).

Many factors impact the successful adoption and implementation of ERM programs. Some drive its adoption, while others affect its practical adoption. Despite the various studies on ERM across organisations operating in different industries, more research has sought to investigate the factors obstructing and boosting ERM adoption among insurance firms (Achaarya, 2016). Hence, the present study investigates the drivers for adopting an ERM and explores the challenges associated with its adoption across the insurance industry. Identifying what drives ERM adoption will allow today's managers to gain essential support, which will

help them strengthen the positive impact of such drivers. In addition, identifying the challenges associated with ERM adoption will allow managers to understand better the obstacles that may hinder the adoption of their ERM program and take the required actions to decrease the undesirable impact that may overwhelm them.

ERM is a newly emerging discipline, only about two decades ago. It has been defined by the IRM (2014) as “*the systematic process of understanding, evaluating and addressing these risks to maximise the chances of objectives being achieved and ensuring organisations, individuals, and communities are sustainable*” (IRM, 2014).

ERM involves integrating and coordinating all types of enterprise risks. It is also defined as “*an overreaching framework, which aims at identifying and removing the financial impact and volatility of a portfolio of risks.*” The significance is that each risk can be seen as a chance to gain a competitive advantage (Seik *et al.*, 2011).

Regardless of the significant attention toward ERM adoption and implementation from academics and practitioners, the evidence of its effective adoption and implementation among insurance firms is still in its infancy; no previous research demonstrates how insurers implement ERM programs (Altuntas *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, more information is needed about the determinants for effective ERM adoption across firms within the insurance industry (Altuntas *et al.*, 2018). In addition, the nature of the insurance firm’s operations is challenged by diverse hazards and risks. Therefore, they are faced with the urgency of addressing and managing risks from an enterprise-wide perspective to create value and sustain good financial health.

The following section will address risk management practices in the insurance industry.

1.3 Risk Management in the Insurance Industry

Insurance firms generally make money by managing different types of risk for corporate entities, municipalities, and individuals. The risk management process involves several stages, such as risk identification, risk assessment, identification of proper means to counter the challenges, and review and evaluation of the risk management policy employed (Arena *et al.*, 2011).

Insurance companies are facing turbulent times, and risk management is at the top of insurers' agenda. Pressure has increased recently on insurers to implement and professionalise their risk management practices. Top management encourages risk management information to be widely spread all over departments within organisations to achieve fully integrated risk management practices into the daily management of the business (Acharyya & Johnson, 2006).

The Insurance industry is considered an essential industry within an economy as it contributes significantly to the economic development of a country and the world economy (Outreville, 2013). For an insurance industry to be considered healthy, it should contribute to the stability of the financial market, in particular in the light of increased uncertainty. Accordingly, it is regarded as a significant business employer (Mishkin & Eakins, 2006). Insurance firms also act as financial intermediaries for various reasons; *firstly*, they receive policyholders' funds. *Secondly*, those funds are placed in multiple money-earning investments such as large mortgage loans, stock exchange investments, buying bonds, and taking funds from one sector to another for investment (Mishkin & Eakins, 2006). Insurance firms have three primary tasks contributing to their value creation: finance, underwriting, and investment. Insurance firms are in the business of accepting their customer's risks in return for a fee that is called "a premium." They profit by imposing costs on their policyholders to cover the company claims plus a profit.

The primary reasons that guided the researcher to conduct his study within this context are the growing role and importance of the insurance industry in the context studied and its requirement for a more robust risk management system (Duverne & Hele, 2016).

1.3.1 Risks in insurance companies

Risk is considered the primary issue within financial institutions; therefore, regulations have been set to regulate risk to guide the risk management process. The purpose of rules that control insurance companies is to protect policyholders from losses if the company becomes insolvent (Jabbour, 2016).

As a result of several corporate scandals, business failures, and fraud witnessed in the business environment over the past years, insurance firms have faced regulation scrutiny that calls for more transparent risk management practices and corporate governance (Bohnert *et al.*, 2018). For instance, in the US context, regulations like the Sarbanes Oxley Act (SOX) were introduced in 2002 to improve financial disclosures and prevent potential business and accounting fraud.

On the other hand, in the European context, and support of the widespread Enterprise risk management, regulators have introduced Solvency II, which obliges financial institutions to adhere to regulations that call for more robust and more rigorous risk management (Gatzert *et al.*, 2018). Since its initiation in 2014, Solvency II has pushed financial institutions to adopt enterprise-wide risk management. Therefore, it is clear from the above that risk management in the financial sector is highly regulated. Jabbour (2016) argues that insurance companies aim to create value. Therefore, ERM could not only be adopted as a response to regulatory scrutiny but must also be considered for its economic benefit to businesses (Pagach & Warr, 2011).

Moreover, in the insurance industry context, many empirical investigations examine the main motives behind adopting an ERM, the main determinants, and the associated challenges. Specifically, in the geographical context of the present study and to the best of my knowledge, this study is the first to investigate those factors across the Algerian insurance industry. As such, this research will shed light on the factors driving ERM adoption and implementation in the Insurance sector in Algeria and explore the challenges as perceived by the most informed people directly or indirectly involved in ERM adoption. Thus, nowadays, insurance companies are expected by their supervisors to adopt management practices commensurate with the nature and complexity of their operations. Amongst the techniques and analyses that insurers could implement to tackle their risk spectrum are the stress testing technique, which has as a principle to determine an insurer's financial strength, and scenario testing, which is another stress testing technique for insurers that entails testing insurance companies' financial condition when experiencing shocks from a variety of risk factors at a time. General risks and hazards apply to all industries. However, there exist more concentrated risks that are specific to an industry. Among the numerous risks insurance companies face, the primary six are regulatory, underwriting, credit, market, operational, and liquidity (Bisrat, 2018). The risks are explained below:

- **Regulatory Risk:** Regulatory risk refers to the risk that occurs because of changes in regulations and laws and adversely impacts the security of business organisations (Bui & De Villiers, 2017). The CSFI's (Centre for the Study of Financial Innovation) Insurance Banana Skins survey, conducted in collaboration with PwC, revealed that the continuing heavy regulatory changes are driving the regulatory risk up in the insurance industry (Pwc.com, 2020) and targeting over 600 insurance companies and industry specialists in 54 countries to discover the industry's most significant risks over the next

2 to 3 years. Regulatory risks emerged as one significant major risk facing markets such as North America, Europe, and the East Pacific.

- **Underwriting risks:** Underwriting refers to the mechanism that insurance companies use to measure risk exposure to determine the eligibility of their customers to receive their products and decide on the appropriate premium for the insured. The premium charged by the insurance company should incorporate the risk premium that must cover not only the claims but also the solvency requirements (Alam, 2019). Therefore, underwriting risk emanates when an insurer's faulty underwriting can affect the insurer's solvency and profitability.
- **Credit risks:** According to Finkelstein *et al.* (2018), Credit risk occurs when an insurance firm is exposed to loss if the other party fails to fulfil the obligations set by the contract, which can include failing to execute them in the agreed time. Therefore, credit risk may affect insurance companies' ability to meet their claims. In addition, credit risk may also occur from causes that may affect the creditworthiness of all parties within a geographical location.
- **Market risks:** Market risks occur in response to the market movements that insurance firms could face, such as the fluctuation in the value of their assets or the amount of their liabilities (Koiijen & Yogo, 2018). Sources of market risk include but are not limited to fluctuation in the interest rate, equity, and real estate prices.

This risk refers to the movement in the volatility of market prices, such as fluctuations in interest rates, equity, and currency, which could negatively affect the investment assets of the insurance firm. It is concerned with the value of an investment that could decrease due to changes in market factors. The three market risk factors are as follows:

- Equity risk refers to the impact that stock market dynamics could have on insurers' and insurers' investments, which will depreciate if this happens (Tong, 2019).
- Interest rate risk: This risk occurs when the relative value of an interest-bearing asset, like a bond or loan, decreases because of the increase in the interest rate risk (Liu et al., 2019).
- Currency risk: This type of risk arises from the exchange rate fluctuation of one currency against another. Having assets or operating a business beyond the national borders increases the risk of facing currency risk (Duverne & Hele, 2016)
- Operational risks: Operational risk refers to risks that arise from the failure of systems, internal procedures, external dependencies, and controls, resulting in financial loss. In some situations, operational risks could result from external events, e.g., fraud. Some operational dangers could not be quantified (e.g., reputational impact), and some could be partly quantified (e.g., legal fines) (Chavez-Demoulin *et al.*, 2016).
- Liquidity risks: This risk arises from the insufficient availability of liquid assets to meet policyholders' obligations and the cash flow requirements of policyholders when due (Chen *et al.*, 2019).

1.4 Research Problem Statement

In the last two decades, risk management has become one of the significant concerns worldwide. Risk can emerge from natural hazards, e.g., Earthquakes and Tsunamis, financial risks, such as the 2008 financial crisis, and global pandemics, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. All those unpredictable situations led to significant losses in the world economy and human lives.

Accordingly, the lack of a solid approach to assessing and monitoring risks supports the need for a more transparent and integrative approach to managing risks that allows aligning risk with the organisation's different areas and maximises the organisation's value (Andronache et al., 2019).

Regardless of researchers' broad interest in the topic (Liebenberg & Hoyt, 2003), ERM is still in its infancy, and identifying ERM adoption within organisations remains a challenge in the literature on ERM. Moreover, the widely available literature on the ERM principally covers two main areas. The first main area covered by the literature addresses the impact of ERM implementation on the value of firms by authors like (Hoyt and Liebenberg (2008), Wu et al., 2014 Nair et al., 2014 Farrell and Gallagher (2015), Grace et al. (2015); Bohnert et al. (2017); Phan et al. (2020); and Malik (2020). The second area covered in the literature mainly focused on investigating firms' characteristics associated with implementing an ERM system, also known as "determinants of ERM implementation" in the literature, which was studied by authors like (Lechner & Gatzert, 2017).

Moreover, most empirical studies on ERM take the form of quantitative surveys. For instance, scholars like Liebenberg Hoyt's (2003) study, which investigated evidence of ERM adoption within organisations, employed the keyword method for analysing the presence of ERM in several financial databases such as Nexis Dow Jones, and Lexis, for "announcement of the appointment of Chief Risk Officers" "Risk Committee" "Strategic Risk management," "integrated risk management" "holistic risk management, "and "consolidated risk management." At the same time, other studies used ERM ratings proposed by standards and Poor's for identifying ERM adopters across the banking and insurance industries (Eackles et al.,2014; Bohnert et al., 2019). The remaining studies adopted the method that entails searching for "Keywords" in annual reports of organisations and publicly available business databases and press releases looking for evidence of existing ERM functions among organisations, for

instance (Pagach & Warr, 2010); (Tahir & Razali, 2011); (Silva et al. (2019) and (Lun Chen, 2019).

Most of the above methods and findings have been widely considered controversial and limited in scope. Those studies are helpful, but they must address a critical point in ERM adoption and implementation: how action and plans occur in practice. Those unaddressed aspects will be addressed in this research by adopting a qualitative method of inquiry using a case study methodology, which is deemed to explore those actions in detail by studying the phenomenon from individuals responsible for ERM introduction and adoption.

Regarding the insurance industry, Jabbour (2016), through the use of the qualitative method of inquiry, conducted a study investigating ERM adoption and implementation among ten medium/large UK insurers; findings highlighted that ERM evolution within the UK insurance industry is still at an early stage and the maturity level of adoption varies across firms and further opined that ERM understanding is not common amongst the practitioners. Jabbour's study findings suggested that further research is necessary within the context of insurance companies in different geographical settings to shed light on the internal and external factors shaping ERM adoption. Thus, the adoption and implementation of ERM programs are growing significantly among organisations operating in different geographical settings (Ai et al., 2018). However, it is worth noting that financial organisations are among the most involved in ERM programs compared to organisations in other sectors (Nguyen & Vo, 2020; Saeidi et al., 2019).

According to Nguyen and Vo (2020), organisations belonging to the financial sector were among the early adopters and implementers of ERM programs in the Western world. Moreover, studies have reported on the critical role of financial institutions in contributing to the economic development of countries (Chen et al., 2019; Khafaji, 2019). Consequently, risk management across the financial industry is more critical than for other firms in different sectors (Chen et al., 2019; Gelman et al., 2018). Since issues facing financial organisations can

significantly impact the whole economy, according to Talwar (2011), a single financial organisation's failure can negatively affect a country's entire financial system, resulting in system-wide failure.

It is also worth stressing that little is known about ERM adoption and implementation in developing countries (Silva et al., 2019). In their discussion about ERM adoption in developing countries, authors like Chen et al. (2019), Silva et al. (2019), and Khattab et al. (2015) argued that developing countries, as compared to developed countries, face more significant uncertainty, risks and challenges that impact their performance and that organisations in developing countries are required to consider risks on a much extensive scope than organisation operating in developed countries which tends to be well-established. Therefore, a more efficient risk management system is needed to ensure a more effective organisational function. This could be attributed to the need for an appropriate understanding and established knowledge about the ERM concepts and their positive effect on organisations operating in developing countries. Therefore, researchers like Manab et al. (2010), Tahir and Razali (2011), Li et al. (2014), and Silva et al. (2019) emphasised the need for further research to be conducted on the topic of ERM in developing countries, which could help to promote awareness about ERM adoption. Conducting this research in a developing country such as Algeria would significantly contribute to extending the knowledge of ERM in a more comprehensive universal geographical setting. According to the researcher, ERM among Algerian organisations must be appropriately considered in the academic literature and practice.

The present study examines the primary obstacles confronting implementing and accepting Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) within the Algerian insurance sector while proposing a framework tailored to address the industry's requirements. Focusing on Cash Assurance Algeria, a prominent player in the nation's insurance landscape, this inquiry will

explore the factors motivating ERM adoption within the sector, the significant hurdles impeding its uptake, and the components essential for an efficient ERM adoption framework. It is posited that a bespoke ERM framework attuned to the peculiarities of a given industry holds promise for enhancing risk mitigation strategies throughout the Algerian insurance landscape. The insights gleaned from this investigation are poised to furnish practical insights into the crafted ERM adoption framework, enriching the existing understanding of risk management practices within the Algerian insurance domain.

1.5 Problematising the risk management practices within the Algerian insurance industry

1.5.1 Risk management in the Algerian insurance industry

Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) is an area that has attracted attention from researchers (Liebenberg & Hoyt, 2003). However, the understanding of ERM adoption in organisations is still developing. The literature mainly concentrates on two aspects: the effect of ERM implementation on firm value and the factors affecting ERM adoption. The former is studied by authors such as Hoyt and Liebenberg (2008), Wu et al. (2014), Nair et al. (2014), Farrell and Gallagher (2015), Grace et al. (2015), Bohnert et al. (2017), Phan et al. (2020), and Malik (2020). The latter aspect, known as "determinants of ERM implementation," is explored by authors like Lechner and Gatzert (2017).

Many empirical studies on ERM utilise quantitative surveys. For example, Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003) employed the keyword method to search financial databases for evidence of ERM adoption in organisations. Other studies used ERM ratings from standards such as Standards and Poor's (Eackles et al., 2014; Bohnert et al., 2019) or searched for keywords in annual reports and publicly available databases (Pagach & Warr, 2010; Tahir & Razali, 2011; Silva et al., 2019; Lun Chen, 2019). While these methods offer valuable insights, they come

with limitations and controversies. They often neglect practical aspects of ERM adoption and implementation. To address this gap, this research takes a qualitative approach, employing a case study methodology to examine ERM actions and plans in practice, focusing on individuals responsible for ERM introduction and adoption.

Like in numerous other developing nations, Algeria's risk management landscape unfolds a narrative of recent inception. Post-World War II, the exploration of risk management commenced, predominantly tethered to utilising market insurance mechanisms aimed at shielding individuals and enterprises from an array of losses stemming from mishaps (Khan, 2013). Nevertheless, the assimilation of contemporary risk management methodologies within the Algerian insurance domain has been sluggish, with a continued reliance on conventional practices (Slimani & Lalmi, 2015).

Lalmi and Slimani (2015) opined that the Algerian insurance sector suffers from different difficulties. Some examples of such problems include non-payment of compensation payable to owners and length of compensation. Such challenges are mainly caused by adopting traditional methods to measure and detect the risks and select the proper means to deal with those risks. The Algerian insurance companies should focus on training the employees to quickly identify the risks and choose the appropriate way to encounter them.

Presently, the Algerian insurance arena accommodates a roster of 23 insurance entities, all under the governance umbrella of the Ministry of Finance. A plethora of challenges loom over the Algerian insurance landscape, meticulously scrutinised by Slimani and Lalmi (2015) in their exploration of the state of risk management within the Algerian insurance sphere. Their investigative findings underscore a prevailing dependence on traditional risk management modalities for risk assessment and policy formulation.

1.5.2 Challenges and opportunities of the Algerian insurance industry

The significance of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in the insurance sector, especially in developing nations like Algeria, where it is still emerging, must be considered. Challenges abound in its implementation. Foremost among these is the limited understanding and awareness of ERM's principles and advantages, a fact highlighted by Beasley, Clune, and Hermanson (2005). Many Algerian insurers persist with conventional risk management techniques, which need to be utilised in today's intricate and uncertain business landscape, as noted by Slimani and Lalmi (2015). Furthermore, organisational inertia and a siloed mindset pose formidable obstacles to change, as Mikes (2009) observed. ERM is frequently viewed merely as a regulatory checkbox rather than a strategic enabler that can enrich decision-making and yield tangible business benefits (Beasley et al., 2005). The need for more data and inadequate skills and resources further complicate ERM adoption and implementation (Gordon et al., 2009). Many insurers in Algeria need more infrastructure and capabilities to fully embrace and integrate ERM into their operations (Slimani & Lalmi, 2015). Despite these hurdles, embracing ERM promises several advantages for the Algerian insurance sector. By bolstering risk awareness, decision-making processes, governance structures, and risk management strategies, ERM can enhance insurers' performance and competitive positioning while refining their risk mitigation, transfer, and financing mechanisms.

Among the myriad challenges grappling with the insurance sector in developing nations lies subpar insurance penetration and awareness (World Bank, 2020). In Algeria, the insurance realm grapples with a tarnished reputation and dismal customer satisfaction metrics, primarily attributed to claims non-payment or delays, convoluted contract structures, and bureaucratic inefficiencies plaguing insurance entities. Sadi and Achouche (2016) delve deeper into the intricacies of the Algerian insurance problem, identifying an amalgam of factors thwarting

industry development, including financial market frailty, service quality deficiencies, workforce inadequacies, and religious considerations.

Furthermore, the Algerian insurance landscape remains tightly regulated by state mechanisms, thus impeding market competition and stifling innovation (Sadi & Achouche, 2016). Notably, specific segments of the Algerian populace, particularly those in rural hinterlands, exhibit low financial literacy levels and a steadfast adherence to traditional risk-sharing frameworks such as familial and communal networks, curtailing their inclination towards formal insurance (Boukhalifa & Benbouziane, 2016).

The spectrum of challenges encompasses exposure to an eclectic array of risks, spanning natural calamities, political turbulence, economic volatility, and pandemics, collectively exacerbating the intricacies and uncertainties inherent in the insurance realm (World Bank, 2019). Effectively navigating these multifaceted risks mandates comprehensive risk assessment, adept pricing strategies, robust management frameworks, and substantial capital and reinsurance capacities to cushion against potential losses and claims (Khan, 2013).

Despite encountering notable hurdles, the insurance industry in emerging nations harbours considerable potential for advancement and enlargement. An increasing need exists for insurance commodities and amenities, particularly among marginalised and financially vulnerable demographics. This underscores the pressing necessity for inventive and pioneering resolutions (World Bank, 2020). Microinsurance emerges as a pivotal strategy in tackling this disparity by furnishing economical and personalised insurance alternatives tailored explicitly to the requirements of individuals with limited means (Churchill, 2006). Moreover, embracing enterprise risk management (ERM) stands poised as a strategic imperative for harnessing the latent potential of the insurance sector in developing nations. Encapsulating a holistic and proactive risk management approach, ERM equips insurance entities with the requisite tools to

navigate the labyrinth of risks while fortifying organisational resilience and bolstering competitive prowess (COSO, 2004).

In summary, the path that the insurance industry is taking in developing countries, as seen through the lens of Algeria, shows a complex mix of challenges and opportunities. The historical background and current socio-economic factors greatly influence how risk management is done within this industry. Despite significant obstacles, the sector has many opportunities to grow and mature. By taking advantage of options like microinsurance and ERM (Enterprise Risk Management) and addressing challenges directly, the insurance industry in developing countries can move towards sustainable growth and success.

1.6 The Research Gap

The existing literature on ERM extensively focused on ERM adoption and implementation in Western countries (Dabari, 2015), and the emerging literature on ERM hardly addresses how insurance firms implement an ERM program (Altuntas *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, most of the studies are multidisciplinary, and their findings are generic and unable to address category-specific determinants of ERM implementation (Kerstin *et al.*, 2014). In addition, differences in ERM implementation encouraged many scholars to investigate ERM adoption in different industries and nations to evaluate how organisations attempt to adopt and implement ERM. Furthermore, although the number of ERM implementations across firms worldwide has grown increasingly, there needs to be more knowledge about the key elements to be recognised while adopting and implementing an ERM program. Finally, most studies investigating ERM adoption and implementation focused on Western countries as a geographical setting (Dabari, 2015).

1.7 Aim and objectives of the research.

This research explores the intricate landscape surrounding the initiation and acceptance of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) within the Algerian insurance sector. With a meticulous examination, the aim is to craft a comprehensive ERM adoption framework tailored to the unique requisites of the industry in Algeria. The objectives outlined within this study have been meticulously crafted to align with the overarching research goal:

- To thoroughly investigate the current status of ERM adoption within Cash Assurance Algeria, scrutinising its implementation and efficacy.
- To delve into the underlying catalysts propelling the adoption of ERM within the broader insurance landscape, discerning the primary drivers fuelling this paradigm shift.
- To meticulously explore and dissect the obstacles hindering the seamless integration of ERM practices within the Algerian insurance sphere.
- To methodically validate the efficacy and applicability of the proposed ERM framework through empirical evidence and rigorous analysis.
- To furnish pragmatic and actionable guidance derived from the developed ERM adoption framework, facilitating its practical implementation within the Algerian insurance environment.

Central to this research are the foundational assumptions posited on the premise that a bespoke ERM framework, meticulously tailored to suit the unique difficulties of the Algerian insurance industry, holds the potential to foster enhanced risk mitigation strategies and bolster resilience across the sector.

1.8 Research Questions

To achieve the aim of this research and its objectives, the Researcher has developed the following research questions:

- What is the current state of ERM adoption at Cash Assurance?
- What drives ERM adoption among insurance firms?
- What ERM adoption challenges are faced by insurance firms in general and Algeria in particular?
- What are the elements that form a practical ERM adoption framework?
- How can a proposed ERM adoption framework be adopted for insurance firms in Algeria?

1.9 The Value of the Research

The present research focuses on a specific regional setting, which is Algeria. The targeted firm to be studied is CASH Assurance, the case company and pilot for adopting the proposed ERM framework. Moreover, regarding industry significance, CASH Assurance is amongst the leaders in the Algerian insurance industry. Consequently, identifying the most appropriate components of a practical ERM adoption framework in CASH Assurance, as intended in this research, has significant relevance and implications for the firms operating within the Algerian insurance industry. The findings of this research would be of considerable significance in communicating essential lessons to prospecting regional and national insurers aiming to develop or adopt an ERM framework. The research will extend the knowledge of ERM by identifying the key motivating factors and elements of success in adopting an ERM framework.

From a practical context, this research strengthens the drivers for considering and adopting ERM systems across the insurance industry. Moreover, these research findings will

inform prospective ERM adopters about the components of a successful ERM framework, which may accumulate more benefits on various organisational dimensions. Identifying the most appropriate elements of an ERM framework for a successful ERM adoption within the insurance firm studied, as suggested by this research, has a broader significance and relevance to the various companies operating within the same industry.

Regarding the significance of geographical setting, the suggested ERM adoption framework is intended to be the foundation on which firms that belong to the same industry may build their risk strategy, make more informed decisions, and achieve a sustainable future.

1.10 Contribution to The Theory

This empirical study contributes to knowledge by adding an in-depth understanding of the risk management practices in the Algerian insurance industry by examining the primary factors driving ERM adoption and investigating the associated challenges. This research further contributes to ERM literature by proposing an industry-specific ERM adoption framework in a new geographical context of study that includes unique elements.

1.11 Contribution to The Practice

- To policymakers of the Algerian insurance industry: by providing more precise insights into factors that shape ERM adoption and addressing the main challenges that may impede its effective adoption and implementation.
- ERM implementers: findings will provide a more precise understanding regarding
- On the main factors that impact ERM adoption. Those findings may assist other insurance firms that have already initiated an ERM but have yet to process it due to the lack of information on the different aspects of its adoption.
- By providing a step-by-step adoption model of the proposed ERM framework.

- To Top management: by providing a clearer understanding of the main challenges facing.
- In insurance firms, senior management can consider these risks when setting up the firm's risk appetite and long-term strategic planning.
- To government and regulatory bodies: The research findings will help policymakers and regulators within the Algerian insurance industry identify the areas that need further developments in the different policies of risk management that may require imminent attention.

1.12 Outline of the research

There is a total of seven chapters that are explained below. All seven chapters include different components necessary to carry out the research, achieve the objectives set, and accomplish the main aim.

- **Introduction (Chapter 1):** This chapter has been designed to present a summary of the research topic to give the reader an idea and understanding of the studied phenomena. Furthermore, the background of the research highlights the phenomena studied in the business environment and their implications for the different stakeholders. The present chapter also establishes the research questions, aim, and objectives.
- **Literature Review (Chapter 2):** This chapter critically reviews what has already been written on the research topic (ERM). The first section includes an analysis of the findings of previous academic studies and industry reports that have been completed about the phenomena studied (ERM). In addition, this chapter presents the gap identified following the review of the literature.
- **Theoretical Framework (Chapter 3):** This chapter evaluates the widely adopted ERM frameworks worldwide and then presents the shortcomings of each framework to justify

the need to develop an ERM adoption framework tailored to the needs of the insurance industry in Algeria. In addition, it critically discusses the different theories related to the aim of the research. It accounts for the adopted theory, forming the basis for developing the proposed adoption framework. Moreover, it introduces the proposed ERM adoption framework, derived from the literature review's research findings and the identified gaps in chapters 3 and 4. In addition, its formulations, components, and benefits are also provided.

- **Methodology (Chapter 4):** The research methodology chapter has been designed to provide sufficient detail about the methodology used to collect the needed data for the research. Every step in the execution of the research study has been described in this chapter, including the research design, approach, and philosophy. In addition, this chapter specifies the participants, the plan for recruiting the participants, data sources, the data collection tool, and the data analysis method through which the research aim is attained. Further, limitations of the current research and ethical issues are also incorporated in this chapter to ensure that the research is carried out without any biases.
- **Research Findings (Chapter 5):** This chapter thematically presents the findings of the research objectives.
- **Analysis and discussion (Chapter 6):** This chapter critically analyses the findings and triangulates them with the existing literature, offering insights into emergent patterns; in addition, it validates the proposed ERM adoption framework, which was developed in Chapter Three based on the research findings. Moreover, it recommends several practical guidelines to assist the insurance firm in achieving an effective ERM adoption.
- **Conclusion, contributions, and Recommendations (Chapter 7):** This chapter summarises the importance of research findings and highlights the contribution of the current research to knowledge. Further, A specific guideline is provided depending on the

research findings and how they relate to the empirical and theoretical base. Depending on the research findings, a set of recommendations will be provided in the chapter.

1.13 Summary of Chapter One

Chapter 1 commences the investigation into integrating enterprise risk management (ERM) within the Algerian insurance sector. It establishes the foundation by contextualising the examination, illuminating the importance and challenges inherent in risk oversight within the insurance domain, particularly in developing regions. Moreover, it elucidates the research problem declaration, identifying the gap in current literature and application regarding ERM adoption and implementation in the Algerian insurance setting. The chapter then outlines the study's goal, objectives, and research queries, which focus on analysing ERM adoption drivers, obstacles, and elements while suggesting a customised ERM integration framework for the sector. Additionally, it explores the study's theoretical and practical ramifications, delineating the research approach and the structure of the dissertation. Finally, the chapter summarises its core points and prepares for the subsequent chapter, which will examine relevant literature on ERM and its associated principles.

2 Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The present chapter will start by demonstrating how Traditional risk management (TRM) has evolved in the past two decades to Enterprise Risk Management over the last two. Furthermore, it examines critical academic and industry literature on ERM practice across organisations in different sectors. Then, the chapter will review the literature on ERM drivers, determinants of ERM adoption, and challenges facing ERM adoption implementation. Finally, the gaps in the existing knowledge are identified.

2.2 Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) development and Definitions

Risk management evolved in the early 1950s when Wayne Snider perceived the scarcity of books and courses that cover risk management as a topic (Dionne, 2013). Despite the rising trend towards the RM approach, in the light of the 1950s and 1960s, theoretical and practical literature on the topic still needed to be developed (Crockford, 1982).

Earlier in 2004, Enterprise Risk Management was considered by the Harvard Business Review as the breakthrough revolution in risk management (Buchanan, 2004). Many legal institutions and associations have highlighted the importance of adopting an Enterprise Risk Management program and aligning it with the organisational strategy (Arena et al., 2010). ERM has emerged as the new modern approach to strategically managing risk (Andrén & Lundqvist, 2017).

The interest in adopting Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) has been growing over the past decade due to the several shocks businesses faced during the global recession (Arena et al., 2010). In addition, with the increase in organisational failures following the global

financial crisis in 2008, studies reported that managing risk has become vital for organisations to survive and thrive (Cohen et al., 2017). Besides, the high level of uncertainty surrounding the business era, competition, regulatory changes, and changing expectations of stakeholders were all contributing pressures to strengthening the risk function within organisations and implementing an ERM program (Cohen et al., 2017).

Several research have discussed the vitality of adopting a new risk management approach to manage risk by considering the different aspects of an organisation, which is the core of the concept of ERM (Eckles et al., 2014; Florio & Leoni, 2017).

The trend towards adopting Enterprise Risk Management has increased significantly in the past years. Previously, organisations managing their risks focused on mitigating financial and hazard risks (Farrel & Gallagher, 2015). In contrast, in the light of the enterprise-wide risk management approach (ERM), risks are managed from a more integrative approach, allowing organisations to manage risk from a more strategic and offensive perspective rather than defensive by considering both opportunities and downside aspects of risks (Nocco & Stulz, 2006). Furthermore, as compared to the traditional way of managing risk (TRM), an enterprise-wide approach allows organisations to assess and organise risks based on their priority and respond to more qualitative risks, such as reputational or operational risks, through a more centralised and structured framework (Whitman, 2015). Another benefit of managing risks from a holistic perspective is that it allows organisations to integrate an enterprise-wide risk-reward approach to strategic decisions (Che & Liebenberg, 2017)

Therefore, ERM is perceived as the new holistic approach deemed to lower overall risk and hazards and, in return, enhance organisational value by allowing those organisations to create improved efficiencies, lower costs, and decrease the uncertainty associated with its turnover (Hoyt & Liebenberg, 2003).

Scholars like Barton et al. (2002) recommended that an enterprise-wide approach to risks combines different risks and adopts an enterprise-wide view of risk management for the entire organisation, considering human resources, processes, and opportunities. Unlike traditional risk management (TRM), which applies a decentralised approach to managing risks, creating inefficiencies and poor coordination among different departments (Pagach & Warr, 2010), ERM allows organisations to manage risks more comprehensively (Renzi & Vagani, 2020).

In fact, unlike the traditional approach to managing risks that focuses primarily on a particular project, process, or function, ERM has a broader scope. This is also evident from Bailey et al. (2008) definition of ERM, who defines ERM as the new paradigm that employs a systematic approach that allows organisations to manage a larger spectrum of risks in a more integrative manner, promoting awareness throughout the organisation, leading to better coordination, allowing for better decision making. Therefore, from the above discussion, it is evident that ERM's approach towards managing risks is different and more structured, as it considers risks from all their forms at all segments of an organisation. It further aims to achieve organisational objectives and increase shareholder value (Bailey et al., 2008), which is opposed to the conventional way of managing risks, whereby every department within the organisation assesses their specific risks independently and determines how to moderate and tackle them individually (Lin et al., 2011). In addition, ERM supports an organisation's strategic processes by assisting them in turning their risks into more profitable opportunities.

Accordingly, it is very clear from the literature that there needs to be a general agreement on the definitions of ERM. This is explicitly revealed through the availability of the various ERM definitions based on different perspectives (Bromiley et al., 2015). Many studies attributed such disagreement to researchers' views of risk and its importance in achieving other organisational objectives. For instance, the AS/NZS standard (1995) argued that risk

management should be independent of the organisations' strategic goals, while others like the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA, 2001) and COSO ERM framework (2004) have explicitly highlighted in its definition of ERM the importance on linking risk to the organisational strategy to achieve the strategic objectives. On the other hand, others such as Standard and Poor and The Risk and Insurance Management Society RIMS (2011) considered risk an obstacle that should be reduced, with a different opinion; Perrin (2001) perceived it as the opportunity that allows creating organisational value.

Therefore, an ERM perspective on risk allows organisations to manage risks more comprehensively, integrated, and structured while considering their implications for the organisational strategy (Dickinson, 2001; Hoyt & Liebenberg, 2011). Consequently, because risk management should be incorporated into the corporate strategy, the ERM process should be directed from a top-down approach, in which its ownership should be the responsibility of the Board of Directors level (Aebi et al., 2012; Nair et al., 2014). Moreover, by considering the interdependencies between risks and consolidating risks in one risk portfolio, organisations can enhance their understanding of their risks and, therefore, gain a better insight into their risk exposure.

Enterprise risk management (ERM) plays a corporate governance role in the holistic management of all risks to aid in decision-making and increase the likelihood of achieving operational and strategic objectives. The effectiveness of managing interactively depends upon its precise definition and communication with all business levels of an organisation (Armstrong & Vashishtha, 2012; Sipa et al., 2016).

In the same vein, Wen and Yu (2012) considered ERM to be the new significant shift in the risk practices of an organisation that allows the establishment of the whole risk portfolio that an organisation faces. Furthermore, Lin, Wen, and Yu (2012) argued that ERM's benefits

include operational efficiency, cost-saving, and resource allocation, among other indicators that triggered organisations to shift their approaches to managing risks.

Therefore, from the extant literature presented on ERM, one can believe that the multitude of definitions, guidelines, principles, and standards on ERM makes risk management a mature discipline with clear concepts and tools to be used by organisations (Mikes, 2014). Nevertheless, this is far from the case, as risk management practices must still be emerging and proven (Mikes, 2014). Numerous organisations are still facing problems when considering adopting an ERM program (Viscelli, 2017), and if they proceed with its adoption, they tend to develop and design their framework for managing risks (Arena et al., 2010; Mikes, 2011; Jordan et al., 2013; Mikes, 2014).

The above section has discussed the transition from traditional risk management practices to an enterprise-wide risk management approach and the importance of adopting an ERM. The following section will examine ERM adoption and implementation within organisations in different industries and the various geographical challenges organisations face in this adoption to better understand the topic.

The table below highlights key differences between Traditional Risk Management and Enterprise Risk Management.

Table 2. 1 Difference between TRM and ERM

Traditional Risk Management	Enterprise Risk Management
Addresses risk independently. No clear understanding of the interdependencies of the risk portfolios	ERM deals with risks in a holistic manner. Interdependencies between risks are examined and recognised. Takes into consideration the internal and external contexts in examining risks.

<p>TRM provide limited insight into the impact of risks on the organisational strategy.</p> <p>Risk is not a critical component to be included in the strategic planning.</p> <p>It is not a fundamental component of corporate governance.</p>	<p>ERM considers risk appetite when analysing the strategic options established to achieve strategic objectives.</p> <p>ERM is executed through a top-down approach.</p> <p>Its role is vital when setting the strategic directions of the organisation.</p>
<p>Risk management is not considered in the capital allocation.</p>	<p>ERM is essential in capital allocation.</p> <p>Deciding on capital allocation maximises the risk-return.</p>
<p>TRM views risk as an adverse event.</p>	<p>ERM has a positive approach towards risks.</p> <p>ERM takes into consideration both aspects of risks, downsides, and opportunities.</p> <p>ERM further allows us to explore opportunities for risks and use them in value creation.</p>
<p>Ownership is unclear</p>	<p>Clear risk ownership of risk along with accountability, should be clearly defined.</p>
<p>TRM focuses on quantifying risks, for example, financial risks, whereas other risks, such as reputation or cyber risks, may be neglected or concealed.</p>	<p>An enterprise-wide risk oversight framework addresses the different types of risks. It allows us to determine and emphasise critical risks and understand their primary causes.</p>

Source: Adapted from (McShane, 2018)

2.3 ERM adoption and Implementation

2.3.1 ERM adoption drivers

According to literature in various industries, ERM implementation has been compelled by legal compliance and corporate governance requirements (Liebenberg & Hoyt, 2003; Manab et al., 2010). The majority of those drivers are legal and regulatory compliance requirements, such as the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002 (SOX,2002) and New York Stock Exchange corporate governance rules in the USA (NYSE,2014), and the non-mandatory reports or standards that created public pressures and benchmarks for sound management practices, such as the COSO ERM framework. Embracing ERM has been considered an excellent strategy to comply with these new risk-based governance requirements (Wu & Olson, 2009). Furthermore, because ERM can increase firms' value, the three leading rating agencies (Moody's, S&P, and Fitch) have included a firm's ERM system as an element in their rating methodology in various industries (Beasley et al., 2008). Thus, credit rating agencies' requirements could drive ERM implementation.

While compliance and corporate governance requirements have driven firms to adopt ERM, firms in many industries conduct ERM for benefits (Pagach & Warr, 2011). An overall perspective of the literature is that ERM implementation can ameliorate firm performance (Gordon et al., 2009). Some of the benefits that can be derived from the implementation of ERM include, but are not limited to, reduced costs and losses, reduced earnings volatility, improved decision-making, increased profitability and earnings, better risk reporting and communication, better resource allocation, increased management accountability; greater management consensus; competitive advantages, improved owners' satisfaction and enhanced control of an enterprise on its projects (Kleffner et al., 2003; KPMG, 2010; Liu et al., 2011;

Manab et al., 2010; Muralidhar., 2010; Narvaez, 2011; Nocco and Stulz., 2006). Moreover, a diversity of risks drives firms to adopt ERM as well. Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003) affirmed that the dangers of globalisation and the market moved firms to adopt ERM. At the same time, Pagach and Warr (2011) studies concluded that firms with more volatile operating cash flows and riskier stock returns were more likely to adopt ERM.

Furthermore, the use of advanced information technology (IT) was perceived as a critical external driver (Liebenberg & Hoyt, 2003) as ERM requires much computing power (Segal, 2011). This breakthrough has enabled firms to collect improved records for certain risks, model complex risks, measure risks more accurately, and enhance understanding of the interdependencies across a firm (Jablonowski, 2001). The improved accessibility of outsourcing possibilities for advanced IT modelling activities has made ERM available to firms that need specialised risk-related knowledge.

Nevertheless, new studies suggest that the implementation of ERM is slowed down by firms' perceived lack of technological tools (Liebenberg & Hoyt, 2003). Additionally, the external driving influences would require the board and senior management to request ERM implementation. Studies by Kleffner et al. (2003) reported that 51 per cent of Canadian firms viewed encouragement from the board as the fundamental element underlying their ERM implementation. Simultaneously, Narvaez (2011) asserted that top management should drive ERM implementation as ERM necessitates the commitment of the entire enterprise.

Kleffner et al. (2003) investigated the adoption status of ERM among Canadian organisations and the drivers that led to its adoption: respondents highlighted several factors. According to the findings, respondents indicated the following the main drivers towards adopting an ERM program: the influence of a risk manager (61%), the board of director's encouragement (51%), and compliance with the Toronto Stock Exchange (TSE) guidelines as the final driver. This denotes that regulations are one influence among others on ERM adoption.

The discussion above reveals that little is known about the adoption drivers of ERM in the insurance industry in general, and minimal empirical studies have been conducted to investigate ERM adoption in the insurance context of developing countries. Considering that regulations differ from one geographical context to another, there is a need to gain insights into the drivers behind ERM adoption from a developing market perspective.

2.3.2 Identification of ERM adoption and implementation within organisations

In the past few years, researchers demonstrated an increased interest in implementing ERM and its determinants (McShane, 2018; Bohnert et al., 2019). Generally, the literature on ERM topics involves two key research streams. The first stream comprises those examining the firm's characteristics that affect the implementation of the program, or as many authors referred to in the literature as "determinants of ERM implementation (Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003); (Lechner & Gatzert, 2018). Moreover, they comprise those studying the relationship between ERM implementation and a firm's value, for instance, Pagach and Warr (2010) and Bohnert et al. (2019).

Moreover, the literature review about identifying ERM implementation within organisations demonstrates that ERM scholars used four methods when measuring ERM implementation among those organisations. The first and most prevalent method in various studies is looking for the appointment of a Chief Risk Officer (CRO) or an equivalent position such as "Senior Manager" to determine the existence of an ERM program in place (Beasley et al., 2008; Pagach & Warr, 2011; Florio & Leoni, 2017). However, using this method has been widely criticised for providing insufficient evidence on ERM implementation by scholars like Sekai and Pagach (2019), who opined that many organisations with a Chief Risk Officer appointed implemented an ERM program. The second most employed method available in the

literature on ERM for identifying its adoption and implementation is to search by “keywords” for evidence of ERM implementation in secondary sources like organisation’s annual reports and databases like Dow Jones and Nexis databases by authors like Hoyt Liebenberg (2011); Berry-Stolle and Xu (2018); and Anton (2018). The keywords employed in the search are “ERM,” “CRO,” “Risk committee,” “strategic risk management,” “consolidated risk management,” “holistic risk management,” and “integrated risk management.” Despite the popularity of this method among ERM researchers (more than 35%), this method presents some limitations.

The third method uses the ERM ratings offered by Standard and Poor’s ratings as a “proxy” for identifying ERM in place. Many researchers employed the “proxy” method, for instance, Baxter et al. (2013), Eckles et al. (2014), and Bohnert et al. (2019). However, this method mainly considers banks and insurance firms, and its results are limited to only organisations operating within the financial sector. The final process is surveying firms directly to examine the level of ERM implementation among organisations (Zhao et al. (2014b); Zhao et al. (2016); Soltanizadeh et al. (2016); Strelcova et al. (2018); Moshesh et al. (2018); Neto et al., 2018; and Yang et al. (2018).

This method is more effective compared to other methods. It can allow the researcher to access information from the surveyed firms directly rather than through secondary data. On the other hand, its weakness is that among respondents, there may be some participants who may mislead the results of the survey by exaggerating and providing wrong insights regarding the degree of ERM adoption within their organisation, which may eventually result in achieving biased outcomes (Sekerci, 2015).

The extant literature reviewed reveals that research on ERM identification and measurement is scarce, and agreement is yet to be reached on the best method to identify ERM

in place; therefore, this section will scrutinise available ERM measurement methods in more detail to help the researcher to identify the more- suitable method in practice.

Keyword Search

Most of the past empirical studies used keyword searches, for instance, “Chief Risk Officer (CRO) appointment,” as a proxy to determine whether an organisation has implemented an ERM program. Annual reports, press releases, and organisations’ databases were among the most used sources to investigate ERM adoption in the light of this method by researchers like Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003), Pagach and Warr (2011); Eckles et al. (2014). In addition to the word CRO, other strings have been employed by scholars who scanned databases like the Dow Jones database. For instance, Hoyt and Liebenberg (2011), Berry-Stolzle and Xu (2018), and Anton (2018) have employed the following key works in examining the implementation of ERM among different organisations:

1. “Enterprise Risk Management”
2. Chief risk officer.”
3. “Risk Committee”
4. “Strategic risk management”
5. “Consolidated risk management”
6. “Holistic risk management”, and
7. “Integrated risk management”

However, the above method has been widely criticised for being disadvantageous sometimes and limited due to the lack of more reliable insights on how organisations have reached their ERM implementation (McShane et al., 2011). One of its biggest problems is that identifying the presence of a CRO in place does not help in overseeing whether he is in charge of the deployment of ERM within an organisation. Thus, many financial firms appoint a CRO

to manage their risk process, while other firms that belong to different sectors may delegate the duty of ERM implementation to the CFO (McKinsey, 2012).

Despite its limitations, scholars investigating ERM implementation still adopt the “proxy” method. For instance, following the study adopted by Hoyt and Liebenberg (2011) and Pagach and Warr (2011), Lechner and Gatzert (2017) investigated firm characteristics that influence ERM implementation and analysed ERM implementation effect on the value of a sample of companies that are publicly listed in the German stock exchange. The authors performed a keyword search, employing terms such as: “ERM,” “CRO,” “COSO,” “risk committee,” “holistic risk management,” and “Integrated risk management.” Findings indicated that firms' size, the industry's nature, and international diversification correlate positively with ERM implementation. In addition, findings confirmed that ERM enhances the value of the companies studied.

Using Standards and Poor (S&P's) Ratings

The ERM rating, established by Standard and Poor's, was first based in 2005. Since 2005, Standard and Poor have started assessing ERM implementation levels within insurance firms using four significant categories: Excellent, strong, adequate, and weak (S&P, 2005; S&P, 2013a). In 2009, S&P updated their system of rating the level of ERM implementation into soft, adequate, adequate with risk control, strong, and very strong (S&P, 2009; S&P, 2013, 2013a).

To examine the ERM engagement within insurance firms, S&Ps assessed whether the insurance company has deployed systematic and consistent strategic risk management that enables those firms to limit losses in the future. ERM assessment developed by S&P focuses on five main aspects of a firm: risk management culture, risk controls, emerging risk management, risk models, and strategic risk management (S&P, 2013a).

According to Standard and Poor’s rating criteria, insurance that rates “very strong” and “strong” uses an enterprise-wide risk management approach and belongs to the group of users that have high-quality risk management in place and take into account risk at the strategic level. In contrast, insurance firms that are rated “strong” tend to lack a clear vision of the firm’s overall risk profile and exhibit a traditional risk management approach; therefore, they belong to the group of insurers with less high-quality risk management (S&P, 2005; S&P, 2009; S&P, 2013a).

Table 2. 1 Description of the S&P ERM rating

ERM Score	Rating Description
Very strong	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="520 857 1394 1037">➤ The insurer demonstrates excellent deployment of the ERM framework components and exhibits a good economic capital model (ECM) assessment. <li data-bbox="520 1077 1394 1189">➤ Risk management and risk are effectively integrated within the overall organisational strategy. <li data-bbox="520 1229 1394 1408">➤ The insurer can determine, assess, manage, and control organisational risks consistently and a wide-enterprise approach within the established risk appetite.
Strong	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="520 1525 1394 1771">➤ The sub-factor's risk management culture, risk controls, and strategic risk management are scored “positive”. In contrast, one or both sub-factor's risk models or emerging risk management are achieved “neutral”, and no sub-factor is scored “negative”. <li data-bbox="520 1812 1394 1924">➤ The insurance company tackle its risks by adopting a synergetic and enterprise-wide perspective and considers risk in its

	<p>strategic planning process. However, the ERM deployment degree remains undeveloped within those insurance firms that score “very strong.”</p>
Adequate solid risk controls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The insurance firm’s risk control is considered “positive”, while the examination of other aspects of the ERM implementation remains “adequate”; for instance, this may be due to the incorporation of strategic risk management scores as “neutral”. ➤ The insurance company is still unable to identify its whole risk portfolio.
Adequate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The assessment of the insurance company implementation regarding risk controls and risk management culture is “neutral”. ➤ An enterprise-wide and precise coordination of risks in the insurance firm is absent, even though the insurance firm can identify and manage risk.
Weak	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The insurance firm is assessed as “weak” because its risk culture and risk control score are “negative.” ➤ The insurer has limited capabilities regarding identifying and managing risk exposure.

Source: (Adopted from S&P, 2009; S&P, 2013a).

Among the most cited studies in the literature using S&P’s rating is the study of McShane et al. (2012), which aimed to measure ERM implementation. By adopting a sample of 82 US insurers, McShane et al. (2012) they investigated the impact of the stage of ERM adoption on firm value. Using Tobin’s Q as a vital value measurement, McShane et al. (2012)

tried to measure the ERM stage effect on the value of the firms studied. The findings of their study demonstrated that a positive relationship exists between “score 1: weak and score 2: adequate” and the firm's value. However, the McShane et al. (2012) study did not provide any insight into the degree of value created by those companies that have scored “excellent” and “Strong.” Accordingly, following the same method as McShane et al. (2012) and using a sample of 165 companies in the financial industry, Baxter et al. (2013) found that there is a positive correlation between the quality of ERM scoring and Tobin’s Q and return on investment (ROA).

Similarly, Bohnert et al. (2019) aimed to investigate the drivers and ERM's added value. The primary purpose of their study

The aim is to extend the literature on the effect of ERM implementation among European insurance firms on the shareholder’s value by adopting the S&P’s ERM rating method to identify the ERM activities among those insurers. Their sample consisted of 41 European insurance companies operating in different European nations from 2007 to 2015. The result indicates that ERM implementation positively impacts those insurance firms’ Tobin’s Q, which was, on average, 6.5% higher for the firms with higher-quality ERM systems.

ERM index research

Authors like Mike and Kaplan (2014) noted that previous empirical studies measuring ERM implementation among organisations need more consistency and scope. The authors argued that variables used in earlier research failed to capture how ERM is implemented in each organisation and that the presence of a “risk manager” or a risk management department provides very little evidence about the quality, scope, and impact on the risk management processes (Mike & Kaplan, 2013). The limitation in measuring ERM implementation effectively led many academics to identify new measurement methods to investigate ERM

implementation, such as the ERM index method (Mike & Kaplan, 2014). This method consists of adopting already existing ERM frameworks and data that are published to determine the critical elements of the framework, for instance, Quon et al. (2012) (Grace et al.,2015) and Sithipolvanichgul (2016).

For instance, Gordon et al. (2009) used the COSO ERM framework to set their own ERM index. Similarly, Quon et al. (2012) developed their own ERM index. At the same time, scholars like Grace et al. (2015) combined both the keyword method and their index methods to measure ERM implementation.

On the other hand, authors like Desender and Lafuente (2009), through the use of the COSO ERM framework, have developed their ERM index questionnaire by adopting the eight elements of the framework to identify ERM implementation. A year later, the authors upgraded their method and combined two methods, namely the “index” and “keyword search” methods, to investigate ERM implementation among their sample companies. The methodology followed by both authors was based on a hundred and eight (108) ERM scoring questions covering the eight elements of the ERM COSO 2004 framework (Desender & Lafuente, 2011), even though it demonstrated a positive correlation between the presence of ownership structure, audit department a, and ERM adoption, their investigation has limited scope due to the employment of secondary sources data s, such as using companies’ websites or conducting searches annual reports.

The above section has identified the different methods followed by many scholars to investigate and measure the effect of ERM implementation among firms. The following section will discuss the various determinants for adopting an ERM.

2.3.3 Determinants of ERM adoption

Numerous research has been conducted in different countries and geographical settings, covering other types of industries, and have studied several organisations adopting ERM and the determinants of its adoption. The adoption and implementation of an ERM program progress throughout different stages; from the primary stage to full adoption and implementation, the process should pass several stages. Thus, before adopting any ERM framework, several factors should be considered. These factors to be considered by CEOs before the adoption and implementation stage are the organisation's size, organisational complexity, industry, Big Four presence, BOD independence, and the organisation's country of operation. By considering these factors before proceeding with ERM implementation, organisations may understand the real benefit behind its adoption and implementation and how its downsides could be reduced.

Moreover, Previous research investigating ERM determinants tends to explore specific firms' determinants or contextual variables driving the adoption and implementation of an ERM program, such as the presence of a chief risk officer within the organisation (CRO). However, these researchers tend to search for publicly available information to investigate determinants of ERM adoption within organisations because organisations need to disclose more information regarding their risk management procedures. Other authors, such as Colquitt et al. (1999), considered other factors that may determine ERM adoption and implementation among organisations, such as the size of the company, the company's industry of operation, and the educational and professional background of the risk managers risk manager's academic and professional background.

Kleffner et al. (2003) investigated the status of ERM adoption among Canadian organisations and the drivers that boosted this adoption: participants in this study highlighted

several factors. According to the findings, the participants indicated the following as the main drivers towards adopting an ERM program:

- Risk manager influence (61%)
- Encouragement received from the board of directors (51%)
- Complying with the regulations of the Toronto Stock Exchange (TSE) guidelines as the final driver

This denotes that regulations are one influence among others on ERM adoption.

Similarly, Beasley et al. (2005) in a more comprehensive study that included a larger sample of US and international organisations. Their study targeted members of the Global Audit Information Network (IIA), mainly Chief Auditors. Out of 1770 requested to participate in the research and received the survey, only 175 surveys were completed and returned, among which 52 had incomplete data, bringing the study to a final sample of 123 US and international organisations.

Beasley et al. (2005) study was conducted to explore the relationship between different organisational factors and the stage of ERM adoption and implementation, based on the 123 completed surveys. The authors have used a dependent variable representing ERM adoption that varies from 1 =not planned to adopt an ERM to 5 = fully developed ERM programmed. Their survey results showed that revenue size was positively related to the stage of ERM implementation. In addition, the study further indicated that organisations with 1) a Chief Risk Officer, 2) a high number of independent directors, and 3) support of CEO and CFO for ERM adoption and implementation were likely to have a well-developed ERM in place. The study outcomes concluded that top management support is critical for ERM implementation. Organisations that seek the expertise of one of the four auditing firms have demonstrated that they are at a further stage in their ERM implementation, followed by those organisations that have outsourced their ERM implementation to smaller audit firms (Beasley et al., 2005).

With regards to the ERM implementation stage, Beasley et al. (2005) found that 41% of the studied organisations were at the fourth stage (partial ERM in place), with only 9% which were at the final stage of ERM adoption (complete ERM in place). Although the 50% adoption rate found is encouraging, out of the remaining 50%, 19% declared to have no plan to initiate an ERM, with 16% still investigating its adoption and the remaining 15% its adoption (Beasley et al., 2005).

Beasley et al. (2005) findings further revealed a positive relationship between factors such as a CRO within an organisation and the ERM adoption stage. This is congruent with Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003), who argued that the presence of a CRO is a "catalyst" to the adoption of an ERM. Beasley et al.'s (2005) study further evidenced a positive relationship between BODs being more autonomous and ERM implementation. This was also when CEOs and CFOs explicitly called for internal audit involvement to implement ERM. This advocates that leadership is also among the critical factors in ERM implementation, where the senior management and BOD set the tone for ERM implementation. Moreover, the research also concluded that larger organisations and customers of the big auditing firms were more disposed to and advanced in ERM adoption. Thus, organisations belonging to specific sectors were found to be early implementers of ERM programs. Sectors include insurance, banking, and education, though this could be attributed to regulation scrutiny within these sectors that explicitly stipulate better and more efficient risk management.

Similar to the studies illustrated above, Bailey (2015) investigated the effect of the chief risk officer (CRO) and the risk committee members on achieving a successful ERM program. The findings of their study showed that the CRO position positively affects the quality of an ERM program. Moreover, it was found that the role of CRO has a significant implication in lowering the level of internal control and strategic risks. In addition, findings highlighted the positive effect of the role of the risk committee members in lowering the levels of the total

risks. Accordingly, the study's findings concluded that the CRO expertise and the risk committee positively influence the ERM program's quality (Bailey et al., 2019).

More recently, Al-Farsi (2020) examined the effect of having a CRO in place of the effectiveness of the ERM adoption among ninety-four (94) publicly listed Omani organisations. The author has employed an online survey method sent to top-level managers of the chosen companies. The online survey findings revealed that a high level of ambiguity surrounds ERM adoption across Omani companies; therefore, ERM adoption remains immature within this particular geographical setting.

In their pioneering study, Pape and Spekle (2012) conducted a survey through which they aimed to investigate ERM implementation among 825 Organisations belonging to the public sector, non-profit organisations, and SMEs headquartered in the Netherlands. Pape and Factors that the study has adopted to investigate the development stage of ERM across those organisations studied were regulations' influence, internal factors, auditors' influence, ownership, and the nature of the industry. Moreover, to determine the ERM adoption stage among those organisations, Paape and Spekle (2012) followed the categories recommended by Beasley et al. (2005). However, for every development stage, Pape and Spekle (2012) added some further characteristics for the configuration of the program as demonstrated below:

- Stage 1: Risk management is driven by incidents; no implementation is planned
- Stage 2: Top management actively controls risks in particular areas, and complete ERM implementation is planned.
- Stage 3: Top management is already identifying, analysing, and controlling risks in particular areas, and complete ERM implementation is planned.
- Stage 4: Top management already controls strategic, operational, and financial risks; ERM implementation is in progress.

- Stage 5: Top management is controlling strategic, operational, financial, and compliance risks; ERM is already integrated into the strategic planning process (Paape & Spekle, 2012)

The study findings revealed that the 825 participating organisations in the study were at different ERM implementation stages, with only 14% at stage 1, managing risks driven by incidents mainly, 38% were at stage 2, considering implementing ERM, in contrast, only 23% out of all organisations were at stage 3 planning for a full ERM implementation.

Furthermore, Paape and Spekle (2012) concluded that ERM was more mature across publicly traded organisations rather than other types of participating organisations (Paape & Spekle, 2012). The presence of a CRO and an Audit Committee were the contributing factors toward the progression of ERM implementation. Thus, the size and the operating sector were influential factors, as the outcomes show that larger organisations and those operating in the financial industry tended to have a more sophisticated ERM system (Paape & Spekle, 2012).

Furthermore, numerous factors, such as the experience of the CRO and the Board independence, which have been proven by multiple studies, for instance, Liebenber and Hoyt (2003) and Kleffner et al. (2003), to be of a significant influence in prior research, in different regional contexts like USA and Canada, turned out to have less or no impact upon the stage of ERM implementation among organisations in the Netherland context. As per the study's outcomes, institutional ownership, regulations scrutiny, and auditor quality had no effect on ERM development, which is inconsistent with research conducted earlier in the Canadian and US contexts.

Hence, Enterprise risk management relevance has increased lately against the background of an increase in risk complexity, dependencies of risk sources, advancement in risk quantification and information technologies, as well as the regulations scrutiny in the

aftermath of the financial crises are amongst the factors that drive ERM adoption (Hoyt & Liebenberg, 2011; Pagach & Warr, 2011).

In addition, Gatzert and Martin (2015) investigated the factors driving the implementation of an ERM program by examining and comparing the existing literature on ERM adoption. The research finding indicates that company size is one of the leading determinants of ERM implementation. Larger business organisations are likely to necessitate a robust risk management practice to improve the risks' scope and complexity. Volatilities of stock prices and earnings are positively associated with adopting an ERM system. Companies with more volatile earnings, stock prices, and cash flows benefit from the ERM system because of better control of stock prices and smooth earnings.

Golshan and Rasid (2012) opined that organisations affiliated with specific industries are more likely to adopt ERM due to the degree of risk complexity existing in those respective industries than others that belong to less regulated sectors. Among those industries that faced regulatory pressures regarding adopting an ERM program are the banking and insurance industries due to regulations such as Basel III and Solvency II in Europe, respectively (Gatzert & Wesker, 2012). Thus, insurance firms and Banks are facing regulations from rating agencies such as A.M. Best, Standard and Poor's, and Moody's, where adopting a holistic risk management approach is part of the credit rating process (Beasley et al., 2008).

More recently, Mardessi and Arab (2018) aimed to investigate the determinants of ERM implementation among Tunisian companies. A survey questionnaire was designed in 2016 and sent to 80 public companies. Most respondents were the Chief Risk Officers (CRO) and, more often, the financial directors and internal auditors. Mardessi and Arab (2018) concluded that a CRO's presence positively affects ERM adoption among Tunisian public companies. However, it is argued that an organisation's CRO must explicitly indicate that no ERM is in place, as some companies can include ERM responsibility in the CEO function (Pagach & Warr, 2011).

Recruitment of an internal auditor is also positively associated with ERM implementation. Firm size was another factor that may drive the adoption and implementation of an ERM program. As Paape and Spekle (2012) concluded, larger companies tend to exhibit more interest in implementing ERM than SMEs.

The above discussion shows that most research investigating the determinants of adopting ERM tends to vary across organisations in different industries and countries of operation. Moreover, it used quantitative methods of inquiry (e.g., surveys and questionnaires). Thus, they tend to agree that company size is one of the main factors determining ERM adoption, among other factors. However, using simple proxies, like the presence of CRO to identify ERM adopters and implementers like Liebenberg and Hoyt's (2003) study, seems superficial. According to Lundqvist (2014), CRO appointments cannot reflect the quality and depth of risk management processes of an organisation. Thus, the presence of a CRO needs to reflect the level of support from the chief executive officer (CEO) and the board regarding the production of the risk information. Different resources are deployed to manage organisational risks (Mikes & Kaplan, 2014). Some organisations may not have appointed a CRO, but they might have good risk management practices. In this case, they would be judged as non-RM adopters and implementers when, in fact, they do.

Most studies that explore ERM adoption tend not to address its adoption among insurance companies in a specific context. Therefore, there is a need to examine ERM determinants of adoption within this context.

Another study by Nguyen and Vo (2017) aimed to investigate whether the adoption of ERM differs across European insurers. The study used 101 European insurance companies as a sample operating from 2007 to 2013, which the researcher analysed. The result indicates that larger insurance firms in size are more likely to adopt and implement an ERM program. ERM is appreciated when the companies perform better and operate in the developed markets.

Researchers exploring ERM adoption's determinants tend to agree that a firm's size is one of the significant factors driving ERM implementation; hence, many additional factors are identified, as stated above.

In shedding light on different factors driving the adoption of ERM, Aksel (2009) and Mehta (2010) concluded that organisations with a well-defined" governance structure of risk" tend to achieve a well-developed ERM adoption. A clear governance structure of risk defines how risk management will be structured within the organisation. The risk governance structure defines how ERM roles and responsibilities are divided (Mehta, 2010).

Kerraous (2018) investigated how ERM impacts the performance of 37 large and medium Moroccan companies in Casablanca and Rabat, which were considered the research sample. The result indicates that ERM implementation increases turnover, return on asset (ROA), net income, and operating risk. An organisation that integrates ERM is more likely to identify and control the risks, which positively impacts reaching the organisational goals.

After examining the studies above, it is essential to note that most studies investigating ERM adoption among insurance firms need to provide clear insights into the factors contributing to ERM adoption, and their findings tend to be inconclusive. Moreover, most of those studies have been mainly conducted in developed countries like Europe and the USA, leading to a gap in the knowledge on ERM adoption from a developing market perspective. Moreover, providing the importance of the insurance industry to the global economy, a better understanding of the drivers leading to ERM adoption across developing economies can extend the knowledge of those factors (Saeidi et al.,2020)

Moreover, a review of the literature demonstrates a systematic dominance of studies investigating ERM determinants and value-creating effects in developed countries, for instance: Gordon et al. (2009); Hoyt and Liebenberg (2011); Altuntas et al. (2011); Baxter et

al. (2013); Farrell and Gallagher (2015); Khan et al. (2016); Florio and Leoni (2017); Lechner and Gatzert (2018); Silva et al. (2019); Hanggraeni et al. (2019); Nasr et al. (2019).

Furthermore, the limited number of studies investigating ERM adoption in the context of developing countries, such as the study of Merdasi and Arab (2008) or the study of Kerdoussi (2016), concentrate on one aspect of ERM adoption: the effect of ERM adoption and implementation on firm performance. Therefore, it is clear that empirical studies on how individual or organisational factors influence ERM adoption, apart from the performance metric, in emerging economies are scarce.

The lack of clear evidence on the factors that may impact ERM decisions and successful ERM adoption may obstruct its development and effectiveness among developing countries. Consequently, this research will try to fill this gap by investigating the factors that may affect the decision of ERM adoption and implementation in the context of the Algerian insurance industry. ERM adoption and implementation in firms in developing countries is crucial, as the benefits of the outcomes are the same in developed countries (Suttipun et al., 2018)

Ultimately, it is about ERM determinants being controversial.

This section has examined the determinants of ERM adoption. The following section of this chapter will investigate the different challenges confronting organisations when adopting an ERM program.

2.3.4 ERM Implementation and Challenges

The literature review indicates that there needs to be more research studies on the determinants of ERM adoption for organisations operating in North African countries. In particular, to the best of my knowledge, no published studies have investigated ERM adoption in Algeria. Moreover, regardless of the external pressures, ERM implementation still needs to

be consistent amongst practitioners. This section presents previous research examining the potential challenges to ERM implementation.

Waseem-Ul-Hameed, Ali, and Arif (2017) focused on investigating the problems facing ERM implementation. The research finding indicates that implementing risk management practices is essential for any firm. ERM allows the organisational management to identify and manage the risks effectually. The level of RM implementation leads the ERM system. ERM implementation in most companies still needs to be developed and is still immature. It is the main reason the ERM system fails to meet a reasonable level among most companies.

Lermack (2008) suggests four areas of analysis when considering implementing an ERM program:

- Organisations need to identify their long-term strategic objectives and adapt their efforts to add value before initiating the ERM process.
- Scrutinising the competitive environment in which the organisation operates to benchmark themselves alongside others that work under similar conditions.
- Establishing a corporate culture is crucial. It helps to indicate how change management will be perceived and what perspective would be taken vis-à-vis strategic initiatives.
- Prior to any ERM implementation, a clear understanding of the primary risk exposures that may impact long-term corporate goals is required.

As it is not possible to eliminate risk, organisations may consider ERM as the new strategic management tool that will allow them to identify, mitigate, and confront those risks more effectively (Beasley et al., 2008a; Francis & Paladino, 2008) to develop a better understanding of the portfolio, while creating a solid and aware risk culture across the whole organisation (Hanssen, 2005).

Managing risks effectively helps organisations cope with the adverse effects of different risks, creating business opportunities that could reduce inconsistencies in organisation earnings (Torben, 2009).

However, despite the greater attention that this approach has received, very little is known about the stages of its deployment or factors affecting its acceptance among organisations (Paape & Speklé, 2012; Wawru Kisaka, 2013).

Beasley et al. (2010) indicated that some corporate failures during the recent economic crisis were primarily driven by the lack of a risk management system that can effectively identify, analyse, and manage emerging risks. Other corporations' failures were attributed to senior managers' inability to identify unknown risks due to the lack of a clear and rigid infrastructure to identify, assess, and manage emerging risks.

Annamalai et al. (2018) investigated the importance of implementing an ERM program to identify and manage risks. Likert-scale-based questionnaires were sent to 120 respondents who were senior officials of 15 selected oil and gas companies. Companies must have an in-house department or committee of ERM in their organisations to identify ERM's risk factors and objectives. The influence of risk should be recognised as this information is crucial for the shareholders to assess the future of their investments. ERM improves business performance regarding shareholders' value, profitability, and cost of capital.

2.4 Review of Studies on Enterprise Risk Management implementation in the MENA Region

Ahmed and Manab (2016) studied how board equity ownership moderates the connection between enterprise risk management (ERM), regulatory compliance, and firm performance in Nigerian listed firms. Their research revealed that both ERM and regulatory compliance positively influence firm performance, with board equity ownership enhancing

these effects. They suggested that board equity ownership aligns managerial and shareholder interests, thus enhancing the efficiency of ERM and regulatory compliance. A different investigation by Al-Tayan (2022) performed scrutiny of ERM in Middle Eastern nations, scrutinizing 120 non-financial companies across Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates. He constructed an ERM index based on the COSO framework to assess ERM adoption levels and its impact on firm value and performance. His findings indicated low ERM adoption in the region, yet it positively affected firm value, albeit not accounting performance. Al-Tayan also identified determinants and barriers to ERM adoption, including firm size, industry, ownership structure, board characteristics, and institutional factors.

Aljughaiman and Salama (2019) explored the influence of risk governance on risk management effectiveness in banks across the MENA region. They analyzed 77 banks from 11 countries, assessing risk governance through board independence, expertise, diversity, and risk committee dimensions, and risk management effectiveness through credit, liquidity, and insolvency risk indicators. Their results demonstrated a positive and significant relationship between risk governance and risk management effectiveness, varying across bank types and countries. They recommended banks enhance risk governance practices to improve risk management capabilities and performance.

Ali et al. (2022) investigated the interplay among competitive strategies, ERM practices, and firm performance in Islamic and conventional banks with Islamic windows in Pakistan, surveying 150 bank managers. They measured competitive strategies by cost leadership and differentiation, and ERM practices by risk identification, risk assessment, risk control and risk monitoring. They measured firm performance by financial and non-financial indicators. They found that both competitive strategies have positive effects on firm performance, and that ERM practices mediate these effects. They also found that the mediation

effects differ between Islamic and conventional banks, and that Islamic banks have higher levels of ERM practices and firm performance than conventional banks. They suggested that banks should adopt appropriate competitive strategies and ERM practices to gain competitive advantage and improve performance.

AL-Tayan, Coleman, & Ahmad (2023) study investigated the relationship between enterprise risk management (ERM) and firm value, using a novel dataset for Middle Eastern firms. The researchers found that ERM implementation has significant positive effects on firm value in this region. However, the results varied depending on the ERM measure used and the type of firm (financial vs. non-financial). The study suggested that the benefits of ERM in this region may be industry-specific and depend on the measure of the ERM. Therefore, assumptions about the benefits of ERM should not be made lightly.

Ben Selma Mokni, et al (2014) research examined the risk management tools used by Islamic banks in the MENA region. The study found that Islamic banks extensively use traditional tools to mitigate risk. It also found differences in the level of risk perception across funding modes. The article examined and evaluated the present procedures utilized in the risk oversight of Islamic financial institutions and recognized the instruments and techniques employed in handling credit risk, market risk, liquidity risk, and operational risk by Islamic financial institutions. Another study by Derah (2020) sought to explore the influence of enterprise risk management (ERM) on the operational effectiveness of oil corporations in Qatar. The study found that the critical success factors for the effective implementation of ERM were culture, risk appetite and top management commitment. With respect to culture, the promotion of an organisational culture that is attuned to risk mitigation is significant. Organisational performance was assessed in respect to profitability, improved decision making, strong shareholder' confidence and compliance with the government requirement¹². The study highlighted that there were no significant differences observed in the companies at either 5%

or 10% significance level in 5 aspects (internal environment, objective setting, risk assessment, control activities, and information and communication).

Elamer, Ntim, & Abdou (2020) paper examined the relationships among religious governance, especially Islamic governance quality (IGQ), national governance quality (NGQ), and risk management and disclosure practices (RDPs) in MENA countries. The researchers found that RDPs are higher in banks with higher IGQ and in banks from countries with higher NGQ. They also found that NGQ has a moderating effect on the IGQ–RDPs nexus. These results imply that the quality of disclosure depends on the nature of the macro-social-level factors, such as religion that have remained largely unexplored in business and society research, and, therefore, have important implications for policymakers.

E'Leimat et al. (2022) investigation examines the influence of embracing Business Intelligence (BI) on Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in corporate enterprises in Jordan. The researchers strive to grasp how utilizing BI tools and methodologies can amplify the efficacy of ERM practices, thus enhancing decision-making procedures and overall firm performance. The inquiry delivers an in-depth scrutiny of the function of BI in ERM, deliberating the diverse BI tools and methodologies employed, their advantages and hurdles, and their impact on various facets of ERM, such as risk recognition, evaluation, response, and supervision. The examination also delves into the factors affecting the adoption of BI in ERM, including organizational ethos, configuration, and assets, technological infrastructure and capacities, and external environmental elements. The inquiry culminates with pragmatic ramifications for administrators and policymakers, along with proposals for prospective research.

Ghenimi, Chaibi, & Omri (2017) study scrutinizes the repercussions of liquidity risk and credit risk on the steadiness of banks in the MENA region. The exploration utilizes a specimen of 49 banks functioning in the region from 2006 to 2013. The discoveries divulge

that credit risk and liquidity risk do not exhibit a noteworthy reciprocal correlation, either simultaneously or with temporal delays. However, both risks autonomously impact bank stability, and their interplay contributes to bank instability. The analysis provides an exhaustive examination of the gauges of liquidity risk and credit risk employed, the methodologies of gauging bank stability, and the statistical tactics used to scrutinize the data. The exploration also contemplates the implications of the findings for bank administrators, regulators, and policymakers, and offers recommendations for managing liquidity risk and credit risk to bolster bank stability.

Kannan (2009) doctoral thesis investigates the application of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in the oil sector, specifically concentrating on its execution in the Middle East. The exploration aims to comprehend the present condition of ERM practices in the oil industry and pinpoint areas for refinement to enrich the efficacy of risk management. The analysis provides a thorough inspection of the literature on ERM, explores the theoretical underpinnings of ERM, and introduces a conceptual framework for ERM in the oil sector. The exploration also carries out an empirical scrutiny using data from oil firms in the Middle East, and presents case studies of triumphant ERM implementation in the oil industry. The thesis concludes with pragmatic recommendations for oil corporations to enhance their ERM practices, and proposes for future exploration.

Jaber & Shah (2023) article examines the literature on Enterprise Risk Management (ERM), spotting emerging themes and proposing future research directions⁷. The authors assess the publication stage, performance, and scientific contributions of research papers linked to ERM. They also depict the emerging themes in tackling volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA). The research offers a thorough overview of ERM research evolution, deliberates the major contributions and constraints of existing studies, and pinpoints gaps in the literature.

Rosman & Abdul Rahman's (2015) study investigates the nature of risk management practices of Islamic banks as advised by the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB) in handling their distinct risks. The study also probes into the discrepancies in risk management practices based on the country, size, type, and age of the bank. The researchers devised a questionnaire to scrutinize the risk management practices, with the primary point of reference for the questionnaire being the IFSB Guiding Principles of Risk Management. The participants were either the chief risk officers or occupants of other senior positions engaged in risk management in the Islamic banks. The study unearthed a deficiency in effective risk management practices concerning liquidity risk, displaced commercial risk, and equity investment risk by Islamic banks. Nonetheless, Islamic banks demonstrated relatively adeptness in managing operational risk/Shari'ah non-compliance risk.

Saleem (2013) analysis delves into the role of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector in terms of its contribution to GDP and employment generation, particularly in emerging economies⁸. The analysis underscores that formal SMEs contribute up to 45 percent of employment and up to 33 percent of GDP in developing economies. The analysis also explores the hurdles confronting MSMEs in the MENA region, particularly in terms of access to finance⁸. The total financing gap for MSMEs in MENA is approximated at \$210 to \$240 billion. The analysis proposes that diversification of bank funding sources, enhancement of a country's financial development, the adoption of explicit deposit insurance, and macroprudential policies, such as countercyclical liquidity buffers, can aid in addressing these challenges.

Shaddady (2022) study investigates the influence of business environment, political risk, governance, and Shariah compliance on efficiency in the insurance market from 2007 to 2017 using unbalanced panel data from 125 listed insurance firms across MENA countries. The study emphasizes that a less favorable business environment exerts pressure on insurance

firms and also identified an improvement in efficiency over the sample period, which may be attributed to the role played by challenging business conditions in increasing efficiency. The study also found that Islamic insurance's relative failure to enhance efficiency may be attributable to its failure to establish a distinct identity or draw a clear line between its mode of operation and that of conventional insurance, as well as the issue of customer confidence.

Shatnawi & Eldaia (2020) paper investigates the factors influencing the enterprise risk management practices and firm performance in Jordan and Malaysia. The study emphasizes that a less favorable business environment exerts pressure on firms and also identified an improvement in efficiency over the sample period, which may be attributed to the role played by challenging business conditions in increasing efficiency. The study also found that there was a significant difference in the practice of equity investment risk management based on the size, type, and age of the Islamic bank.

Sisodia et al., (2020) paper projects business risk through different industrial scenarios in concentrated solar investments in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The study proposes that a higher NPV is expected if the concave solar panel project is financed 50% by Khalifa funding. The study also proposes a robust policy and highlights the opportunity for business profitability if the government subsidizes land leasing with respect to each scenario. Wang, & Luo (2020) paper empirically tests the effect of oil price movements on bank credit risk by using a sample of 279 banks in the Middle East and North Africa countries from 2011 to 2017. The authors find robust evidence that the credit risk of bank loan portfolios is negatively associated with increased oil prices. Yuan's (2022) paper discusses the guiding significance of COSO-ERM for enterprise risk management in the post-epidemic era. The paper emphasizes the importance of controlling business environmental conditions in cross-country efficiency studies. The paper also discusses the implications of the findings for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers, and provides a roadmap for future research on ERM.

2.4.1 Challenges of ERM implementation

At its core, ERM endeavours to improve the organisational culture, ensure a good flow of information, and enhance communication regarding risk events. Hence, the objectives alone do not automatically enhance the firm's value or result in better risk management practices.

Our review of the risk management literature has found that minimal articles explicitly seek to identify the challenges to effective ERM implementation; however, for the current study, we identified salient themes that approximate the barriers to effective ERM implementation.

One of the critical objectives of ERM is to achieve strategic objectives and support the board of directors and management in making informed decisions (Fraser & Simkins, 2010). However, the literature reviewed does not explicitly demonstrate that organisations link ERM to their strategy (Viscelli, 2013). Embracing an ERM approach entails changes in firm culture, which necessitate the support of the management board to ensure success (Shayan *et al.*, 2019). Hence, the board of directors is responsible for determining the risk appetite and developing the risk management policies that guide employees in the risk activities. Therefore, the board's incompetence or insufficiency of risk management knowledge and its compromising attitude could be an obstacle to ERM as it hinders and obstructs risk discussion and decisions.

Organisational culture was a significant constraint to an effective enterprise risk management implementation. In a study conducted by Kimbrough and Compensation (2009) to investigate the connection between organisational culture and ERM implementation, the findings suggested that a positive correlation exists between corporate culture and ERM programs. Findings from recent research on the impediments of ERM by Hosseini *et al.* (2016), Hwang, Zhao, and Ong (2015) confirmed that high commitment of management is an internal

impetus power for the implementation of a comprehensive risk management approach within a firm, in a sense that other elements consider the process as a priority and crucial to the firm, which enables a smooth alignment of the firm's risk strategy to its corporate objectives (Agarwal & Ansell, 2016; Kasim, 2016; Mensah & Gottwald, 2016).

ERM has been seen as a top-down approach (Dickinson, 2001; Olson & Wu, 2008) that involves strategic planning and decision-making (Aon, 2010).

According to Cendrowski and Mair (2009), an organisational risk culture is essential to adopting ERM. There exists a strong relationship between considering culture into account and a successful enterprise risk management implementation. Thus, Keeler (2008) argues that forming a culture for risk management is fundamental to implementing a successful ERM system.

Risk culture is defined by Lamarre and Twinning (2010) as the norms and traditions of individual behaviour within an organisation that define the way this group of individuals understands, identifies, discusses, and acts on the potential risks the organisation could be confronted as well as could take.

One study's findings suggested that organisational culture may be an obstacle to ERM implementation, notably for organisations that are resilient toward change (Kleffner et al., 2003). A supportive culture is crucial to ERM implementation (Cendrowski & Mair, 2009; Brooks, 2010). As such, culture is known as well as risk management culture (Santori et al., 2007), or risk culture (Collier, 2009; Zhou et al., 2010) increases staff vigilance (Cendrowski and Mair; 2009) and promotes the freedom of speech between employees and organisation's decision makers (Brooks, 2010).

Fraser and Simkins (2016) opined that enterprise risk management would only fit some corporate cultures. According to the authors, successful ERM implementation depends on an organisation's willingness and openness to change.

Harner's (2010) study found that among significant barriers to effective risk management is the lack of communication and integration as a failure of risk managers to discuss and assess the firm's overall risk profile and instead confines risk management to separate and individual silos.

Risk communication is among the significant hindrances to ERM implementation in various industries. Risk information received from different sources should be communicated and signalled transparently amongst all departments of a firm. Transparency and fluidity of risk communication at the various levels of management allow and promote individual and expert sights, which could have an impact during the development of risk management strategies considering more awareness of risks from all parties involved within the firm (Hwang et al., 2015; Kasim, 2016).

Mikes and Kaplan (2014) concluded through a ten-year field study that guidance and mechanisms for implementing a firm's comprehensive risk management processes are still immature and emerging. The authors emphasise that effective ERM implementation depends upon an adequate fit between ERM identification processes, risk tools, risk function, and other contingents' variables.

Moreover, from an emerging market perspective of barriers to enterprise risk management implementation, the literature has revealed a need for more knowledge. In Africa, only one study has been conducted by Yusuf T. Olekan and Abass O. Adebowale (2014) to explore factors affecting ERM implementation within the Nigerian financial industry. The study concluded that there needs to be more knowledge from an emerging market perspective in terms of aspects of implementation. Therefore, grounded on the above, questions arise as to whether different drivers of ERM implementation exist and are experienced from an emerging market perspective.

2.5 ERM in the insurance industry

In the light of the new regulation scrutiny following the financial crisis of 2008, for instance, the introduction of Solvency II in 2016, managing risk from an enterprise-wide perspective became significantly relevant for firms operating within the insurance industry. Consequently, the improvement of risk management practices among insurance firms is attributed to regulatory pressures. Insurance firms worldwide were encouraged through new reformed legislation to enhance their risk management practices by defining a well-developed risk governance system and establishing comprehensive standards around risk reporting, aligning risk management with the firm's strategic decisions, among other regulations (Bohnert et al., 2019). However, few insurance firms have been able to develop an ERM that creates business value and supports the firm's strategic decisions (McKinsey, 2014).

When specifically considering the insurance industry, the fundamental improvements of enterprise-wide risk management approaches are, to some extent, also induced by regulatory pressure in the wake of the implementation of Solvency II. The introduction of the reformed European insurance legislation at the beginning of 2016 has been a significant milestone in the development of ERM. Insurance companies are encouraged to strengthen their risk management approaches by developing and defining an adequate risk appetite, well-conceived risk governance systems, and comprehensive standards regarding risk reporting, among other requirements. The second pillar of Solvency II also aims to align risk management more closely with the fundamental strategic decisions of the insurer (Bohnert et al., 2019). This emphasises that a holistic risk management system is a crucial component to satisfying the requirements of Solvency II, and an ERM system is a possibility to fulfil these requirements (see, e.g., S&P, 2016).

In 2002, Tillinghast-Towers Perrin conducted a web-based survey on Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). One hundred fifty executives from different insurance firms worldwide

have responded to the survey. Findings revealed that those insurance firms consider ERM adoption as a “good business practice,” and the main objective behind its adoption is to enhance shareholder value through better risk-informed decision-making.

In 2016, Jabbour and Abdel-Kader (2016) examined the drivers behind ERM adoption in the insurance industry. They focused their research on ten large and medium insurance firms in the UK. Their findings revealed that external and internal institutional pressures have shaped ERM adoption. The cultural influences in the insurance companies can be institutional pressures. The organisational culture and the related objectives impact the norms and values of the institutional rules. ERM is generally adopted for its direct economic benefit (Pagach & Warr, 2011) rather than to comply with regulatory demands. Internal social institutions have imposed another pressure on adopting ERM because larger companies consider ERM a social responsibility.

Similarly, Duran and Otero (2020), through a survey administered to CROs working in Spanish insurance companies, investigated what boosted the implementation of an ERM program across insurance firms in Europe. The survey findings revealed that ERM among European insurers has been boosted by the introduction of Solvency II (Duran & Otero, 2020).

In rating procedures, ERM adoption in the insurance industry has also been considered and standardised by rating agencies such as Standards and Poor’s and A.M. Best (Hoyt & Liebenberg, 2011; Eckles et al., 2014). ERM assessment set by rating agencies was created to evaluate the financial strength and solvency (Best, 2013; Standard and Poor’s, 2013).

Nowadays, Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) is recognised by insurance firms as a fundamental practice that allows organisations to create and enhance shareholder value through more intelligent risk-based decisions and resource allocations (Tola, 2020).

Providing that risk management is the primary function of an insurance firm, there is a need to investigate and understand the factors that have boosted ERM adoption in this industry

from a developing market perspective where research is scarce. Moreover, the literature evaluation indicates that findings regarding the drivers of ERM adoption within this industry still need to be more conclusive and tend to focus significantly on the factors associated with regulation pressures (Jabbour & Abdel-Kader, 2016). However, the adoption of ERM has been boosted by authors like Pagach and Warr (2011) for its economic benefits. Given the lack of scholarly literature addressing the factors behind ERM adoption from a developing market perspective where regulations and laws differ, this research seeks to address this gap and provide insights

2.6 Gaps in the literature

The literature on ERM extensively focused on ERM adoption and implementation in the context of US firms. Moreover, most of the research studies performed are multidisciplinary, and their findings need to be more specific and able to address specific determinants of ERM deployment. In addition, limited studies have been published investigating the risk management practices among Algerian insurers. Thus, it is yet to be identified whether the available ERM implementation frameworks are practical and adapted to the economic and regulatory environment of this geographical setting since Algeria belongs to a different regulatory and economic environment where those frameworks have previously been adopted.

Moreover, the literature review reveals that no preceding studies have explored the determinants of ERM adoption and challenges encountered during its adoption and implementation amongst insurance firms in the geographical context of the current research. Only a few research studies in the literature that explore ERM in the geographical area of North Africa, including Morocco and Tunisia, are present. However, no academic studies covering the Algerian insurance industry have been published. Therefore, the interest and motivation

call for exploring the application of Western Literature, where only developed countries have studies on ERM, to the context of a developing country, which is Algeria.

2.7 Chapter Summary

In the past two decades, ERM has developed significantly, affecting an organisation's identity by affecting its particular governance process. Regardless of this development, contributions made to date regarding ERM remain descriptive rather than offering clear implementational guidelines, leading us to the identified gaps in knowledge regarding ERM adoption. As organisations are constantly aiming to manage risks that arise from their operating environment, managers need clear and well-defined guidelines that can direct the practical steps toward an effective and sustainable ERM. Moreover, even if these guidelines exist and are not tailored to industry-specific needs, they do not allow organisations to retrieve the expected benefits of an ERM adoption. Accordingly, before initiating an ERM, management should clearly understand the concept of the ERM process and what can be improved or developed within their organisation before its implementation.

In summary, the gaps addressed in this chapter involve the ambiguity surrounding the ERM concept, which leads to deficiency in allocating the required resources, lack of appropriate support from the senior management and the board of directors, lack of clear guidance on ERM implementation and practical directions; Ambiguity on how to link ERM to the organisation's strategic planning and decision-making and unclear risk culture across organisations. Accordingly, organisations, specifically those in the insurance industry, need more clear ground to create value and improve their performance.

This chapter discusses the available former studies and research on the ERM topic, its adoption determinants, drivers for its adoption, and challenges. However, the chapter also forms the grounds for the present research by providing a detailed literature review from

different aspects. Alongside, a literature review revealed that organisations are continuously faced with a risk arising from their operating environment, calling for adoption and implementation guides that are deemed to assist management towards the practical steps in executing ERM. Despite several ERM frameworks offering guidance, they dictate a general approach to managing risks; therefore, if practical guidance is not tailored to a specific industry's needs and operating environment, ERM adoption benefits cannot be retrieved.

In conclusion, the literature review has revealed that studies on ERM are scarce, mixed, and inconsistent and cannot be generalised. As per our review, most studies on ERM implementation were predominantly focused on Western countries. Moreover, our review reveals that most prior studies were biased, mainly giving attention to financial factors associated with ERM implementation and claiming that financial distress is among the significant factors leading toward ERM implementation, ignoring other non-financial factors that could be of influence. In other words, the literature reviewed must explicitly provide general evidence on the factors associated with ERM implementation. Thus, the literature highlighted to some extent that ERM adoption and implementation are associated with the firm's characteristics. Insights from the literature provide evidence that ERM implementation varies from one firm to another; it may also vary across regulations, mainly where different corporate governance and rules and jurisdictions are applied (Otero et al., 2017)

The Findings of this chapter demonstrated that organisations need a clearer understanding of the strategic value of ERM. Hence, senior management should opt for the full adoption of ERM to ensure sustainable business performance. Findings further revealed that a crucial challenge that organisations encounter is the lack of clear, practical guidelines on how to achieve an ERM that is aligned with the organisational strategy, which, if developed, would allow managers to focus on establishing a risk structure that aligns strategies and culture; all

incorporated in the decision-making process. Thus, decision-makers within the insurance industry lack clear grounds upon which they can add value and, therefore, improve organisational performance. Hence, if such challenges are not tackled, ERM adoption and implementation will not fulfil their benefits, and consequently, organisations will not be able to create value. Ultimately, since insights on ERM adoption are unclear and inconclusive in terms of addressing challenges faced by insurers through the adoption of ERM from a developing market perspective, as well as the steps to be followed to overcome ERM introduction and adoption challenges, this research will endeavour to extend the knowledge of its adoption in a new geographical setting. The next chapter will discuss the theoretical framework of this research.

3 Chapter Three Theoretical Framework

3.1 Introduction

The present chapter will critically review the widely available ERM frameworks among organisations, describe their shortcomings, and discuss the theory that underpins the present research. In addition, this chapter will discuss the basis for deriving the elements deemed appropriate for the proposed ERM adoption framework.

3.2 Rationale for developing the proposed ERM framework

During the past two decades, the concept of ERM has developed significantly and started to be considered the best practice approach to managing risk. It has evolved to embrace an enterprise-wide perspective, leading to the development of several conceptual ERM frameworks. However, the literature analysis on ERM has revealed that the existing ERM frameworks retain their theoretical nature, lack precise strategic alignment with organisational strategies, and address ERM from a specific perspective, which calls for developing an industry-specific framework.

Following the 2008 global financial crisis, organisations have been moving away from the traditional way of managing risks (TRM) towards an enterprise-wide approach known as ERM. The different corporate scandals that the world has witnessed have emphasised the limitations of organisations in identifying and managing risks effectively.

Accordingly, organisations have increased their awareness and understand that effective management of risks increases their ability to achieve their goals (Rubino, 2018).

Several ERM standards and frameworks have been developed to enhance organisations' risk management practices. Frameworks like the COSO 2004 ERM framework, ISO 31000,

AS/NZS 4360 standard, Standards and Poor's Risk management framework, and the framework for the management of Risk-Canada are the most popular and cited in the ERM literature (Frigo & Anderson, 2014; Agarwal & Ansell, 2016). Despite being updated over time, these frameworks have many shortcomings. It is important to note that the available ERM frameworks have different structures, requirements, and definitions, leading to high ambiguity among organisations regarding choosing the best framework to adopt (IRM, 2018a). Following the 2008 global financial crisis, organisations have been moving away from the traditional way of managing risks (TRM) towards an enterprise-wide approach known as ERM. The different corporate scandals that the world has witnessed have emphasised the limitations of organisations in identifying and managing risks effectively.

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The literature gap revealed that organisations recognise ERM as the new strategic way to manage risks and allow them to retain their market position. Nevertheless, firms within the insurance industry still need guidance and a framework that responds to the nature of their operations and allows them to coordinate strategy, process, and industry-specific requirements. Consequently, the present research aims to propose a coherent and effective ERM adoption

framework that responds to the needs of the Algerian insurance industry, which includes necessary elements and steps for aligning ERM with the internal and external environment of the Algerian insurance industry, along with practical guidance intended to achieve successful adoption and implementation of ERM program and improve organisational performance. The following section will provide details on the development and components of the proposed ERM adoption framework. Following the 2008 global financial crisis, organisations have been moving away from the traditional way of managing risks (TRM) towards an enterprise-wide approach known as ERM. The different corporate scandals that the world has witnessed have emphasised the limitations of organisations in identifying and managing risks effectively.

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3.3 Evaluating existing Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) frameworks

The growing market competition, the change in the global business landscape, and the increase in the complexity of risks have all contributed to the emergence of ERM as the new paradigm of risk management. One of the reasons for the rising trend toward developing an enterprise-wide risk management approach is its capability to identify, assess, and respond to the whole risk portfolio within the organisation. This would enable ERM adopters to enhance their competitive advantage by increasing their risk-return trade-off (Farrel & Gallagher, 2015; Lechner & Gatzert, 2017). Moreover, ERM addresses risks in an interdependent manner across the organisation, which enables these organisations to consider opportunities, threats, and downside risks (Tufano, 2011; Lechner & Gatzert, 2017). Regardless of the benefits of ERM

and its capabilities in creating value for organisations, a limited number of organisations could clearly understand its integrated framework (Agarwal & Ansell, 2016), leading to inconsistency among organisations regarding the benefit of adopting an ERM program and hindering its implementation. Consequently, international standards organisations and bodies have developed various risk management frameworks that assist organisations in their ERM implementation process. Some of the widely available and known frameworks that have been published are the COSO ERM framework, ISO:31000, Casualty Actuarial Society framework (CAS), Standard and Poor's ERM framework (Ahmad *et al.*, 2014; Agarwal & Ansell, 2016).

However, standards like ISO31000:2009 tend to focus on a large business scale. They are more suitable for businesses with developed processes and systems that are in place, plus on-duty risk management professionals (Samantha Perera, 2019).

Given that the COSO ERM framework, ISO31000, and S&Ps are significantly cited in the risk management and insurance literature, The following section will define them, evaluate them, and present their limitations.

3.4 COSO Enterprise Risk Management Framework

The Committee of Sponsoring Organisation of the Treadway Commission developed the COSO framework in 2004 (COSO, 2004). COSO body is a private organisation that is led by IIA (The Institute of Internal Auditors), IMA (Institute of Management Accountants), Financial Executives International (FEI), the American Institute of Public Accountants (AIPA), and the American Accounting Association (AAA).

COSO 2004 defines ERM as:

“A process, effected by an entity's board of directors, management and other personnel, applied in strategy setting and across the enterprise, designed to identify potential events that

may affect the entity, and manage risks to be within its risk appetite, to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objectives.” (COSO, 2004, p 2).

According to Goldstein and Pierce (2016), the COSO ERM framework was developed to be adopted by any type of business organisation, private or public, for design, implementation, and assessment of internal control. The COSO 2004 framework was established to assist different organisations in preserving shareholder value and improving it

through risk linked to the organisational strategy and strategic directions (COSO, 2004).

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Figure 3. 1 COSO Framework

Source: (COSO, 2004)

COSO (2004) portrayed its ERM Integrated Framework as the ultimate guide towards achieving an effective ERM. The framework proposes that organisational leaders at the

planning and decision-making levels can view ERM as a supporting instrument to achieve strategic directions. The framework further guides organisations in designing the risk management strategy and adopting ERM effectively. As demonstrated in Figure 3.1, the far three-dimensional matrix has eight interrelated components, four categories of objectives, and four business entities within the organisation. Organisations must implement and integrate all of the framework's components to adopt an effective risk management program and achieve its goals and strategic objectives (COSO, 2004; Rubino, 2018).

The eight COSO 2004 ERM framework components are provided and discussed in Table 3.1 Below.

Interrelated Components of the COSO ERM Framework

Table 3. 1 Interrelated Components of the COSO ERM Framework

Component	Description
Internal Environment	This reflects the alignment of the firm’s risk management philosophy, risk appetite, risk management and ethical values, policies and practices, setting the tone, and the organisational structure to manage the risks.
Objective Setting	This includes setting organisational objectives in line with the organisational mission and accordance with the risk appetite.
Event Identification	Identifies potential internal and external events that may impact organisations' ability to achieve their objectives. Positive events “opportunities” are redirected to strategic planning, whereas adverse impact events are risks that ERM should manage to help determine how those risks should be managed.

Risk Assessment	Assess the likelihood, frequency and consequence (e.g., financial, reputation, etc.) of risk events across a range (from best to worst case) of possible results associated with the events.
Risk Response	Identifies, examines and selects risk response options that align with the organisation's risk tolerance and appetite. Response options include risk avoidance (e.g., not engaging in an activity), risk reduction, risk sharing and risk acceptance.
Control Activities	Ensures that necessary risk policies and procedures are established and implemented appropriately and that risk management processes are effective. Control activities may include, for instance, authorisations, segregation of duties, supervision, reconciliations, and recognitions.
Information and Communication	Appropriate and timely risk information must be communicated to allow different stakeholders to execute their responsibilities.
Monitoring	Ensures that an ERM is in place and determines its efficiency. As a result, it could be improved, updated or extended.

Source: COSO ERM (2004)

The COSO-ERM 2004 framework distinguishes between objectives as follows:

- Strategic objectives: These objectives are aligned with an organisation's mission
- Operations objectives: These objectives are related to the effectiveness of operations within an organisation.
- Reporting objectives: These objectives are related to the internal and external financial and non-financial reporting of the organisation and

- Compliance objectives are related to the laws and regulations an organisation may be subject to and must adhere to.

3.4.1 COSO ERM Framework 2017

Due to the continuous changes like risk and the business landscape, in 2017, COSO updated its framework. The new framework is entitled “ERM -Integrating Strategy and Performance”. The COSO ERM updated framework highlights the crucial role of management and BOD in enhancing the ERM process and the risk reporting process. It considers the evolution stages of ERM adoption and the need for organisations to update their risk management processes to survive the changes happening within the business environment (COSO, 2017). What distinguished the COSO’s ERM updated framework is the updated perspectives on the fundamentals and implementation of ERM for organisations to survive the dynamic environment (Onay, 2021).

The updated framework comprises five segments that different organisational structures can implement to improve organisations' decision-making processes. This is attributed to the framework’s involvement and consideration of the technologies and change factors in the markets and demographics, which have increased the expectations of ERM managers (Mary, 2017).

One of the main requirements of the updated 2017 COSO ERM framework is that ERM should be incorporated into the organisation’s practices, along with the mission, vision, and values. For example, when an organisation sets its corporate strategy and main performance goals, organisations should consider the impacts of its chosen corporate strategy (COSO, 2017; Pierce et al., 2017; IRM, 2018)

By joining COSO to update and review the ERM framework, PwC states that the updated framework has, without a doubt, linked the various stakeholder’s expectations with

ERM, integrated risk into the organisational performance, and facilitated risk prediction (COSO and PwC, 2017).

Figure 3.2 demonstrates COSO guidance and its five components. The principles supporting each framework component are also presented in Figure 3.2. Full implementation of the following principles indicates that ERM is well-developed and its implementation is mature and able to increase the firm's value (COSO,2017; IRM,2018)

Figure 3. 2 COSO 2017 framework 2017 (COSO, 2017)

Considered as the widely recognised and implemented framework across organisations, the framework still has limitations. Many scholars have articulated the limitations and shortcomings of the COSO ERM frameworks (1992, 2004, 2013, 2016) discussed above regarding managing risks. Samahan (2005) considers that the COSO 2004 overlooks operational risks because of organisational risks to support the organisation's objectives. Hence, COSO (2004) ignores actual areas of risk that require effective management due to a lower level of control; in contrast, it focuses most of the time on overcontrolled risk areas. On the other hand, Leech (2012) pointed out the shortcomings of the COSO ERM frameworks published in 1992 and 2004, which neglected both objective setting and communication.

Bonich (2012) considered that all COSO's frameworks focus on minimising disasters while disregarding upside risk. Moreover, all published COSO ERM frameworks require an annual review of the risk management process, leading organisations to waste time and resources since it necessitates a significant number of employees to perform it.

Similarly, Purdy (2010) pointed out some limitations of the COSO ERM frameworks (1992, 2004) and argued that the framework is complex and needs more appropriate practical guidance for organisations to implement an ERM process. The author further considers that COSO frameworks ignore the effect of external factors such as the business environment, government, and other factors; instead, they focus on the reflection of internal factors on the organisation's success. Purdy (2010) further criticised the COSO ERM frameworks for considering risks as sudden events and ignoring risks that could result from slow-paced events. Ultimately, Purdy (2010) pointed at another structural shortcoming of the COSO framework (2004) and indicated that the framework combines the risk management process and the risk management framework. The framework consists of the organisational structure that supports organisations in improving the management of risks, using specific methods that form the process for achieving the organisation's objectives. How about the present research? You need to explain why this framework does not apply to the research.

3.4.2 ISO 31000:2009 The International Risk Management Standard

The second most widely known and recognised framework for managing risk among organisations worldwide, after the COSO ERM framework, is the ISO 31000 Framework. ISO 31000:2009 was first introduced in November 2009 by The International Organisation for Standardisation, and it is the result of a four-year consultation among risk and standards experts in 30 countries. The ISO Technical Management Board Working Group developed the

standard on risk management to achieve various objectives. ISO is considered one of the largest standards developers worldwide, and its ISO 31000: 2009 has been classified as principle-based instead of perspective-based. Unlike the COSO ERM framework, the ISO31000 framework is only a guide. It cannot provide any certification for its users and needs fundamental requirements for effective risk management. However, it is providing its users with several best practice standards that can be followed as guidelines to assist organisations in increasing the likelihood of achieving their objectives.

The concept of the ISO:31000 standard is that the risk management process is integrated into organisations' decision-making processes. It further encourages business leaders to be driven and consider the need to identify and manage risks across the organisation.

The International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) highlights that, by applying ISO 31000 principles, organisations would become more efficient and productive. Through this, the organisation can establish solid decision-making, planning, effective allocation, and use of resources for risk treatment.

Unlike other risk management frameworks, the ISO:31000 standard adopts the term “risk management” in its standards and guidelines. Furthermore, ISO:31000 defines risk management as “coordinated activities to direct and control an organisation about risk” (ISO31000, 2009, p 2). It also explains the risk management framework as a “set of components that provide the foundations and organisational arrangements for designing, implementing, monitoring, reviewing and continually improving risk management throughout the organisation” (ISO31000, 2009, p 2).

As shown in Figure 3.3, ISO 31000:2009 presents several risk management tasks to support the organisation's decision-making process. Organisations can refer to the diagram. However, it must be adapted to unique organisational needs before implementation is ordered to fit in.

As Florea and Florea (2016) stated, ISO 31000 implements several principles that must be satisfied to make risk management practices effective. The international standards allow an organisation to develop, establish, and continuously improve a risk framework that aims to incorporate the risk management processes into the organisation's overall governance, reporting process, culture, and values. Nevertheless, one of the critical strengths of ISO31000 standards is the risk Identification proposed by the standard, which identifies clearly who should own the risk within an organisation, which is necessary for ensuring that responsibilities are well allocated (Gjerdrum et al., 2011)

Figure 3. 3 ISO31000 ERM framework

Source (ISO,2009)

According to Florea and Florea (2016), managing risks refers to the infrastructure to effectively manage risks. The international standard enables an organisation to enhance the likelihood of attaining its objectives, improve control, decrease loss, and improve organisational resilience and learning.

In February 2018, ISO re-published its framework under ISO 31000:2018 Risk Management Guidelines, considering organisations' changes and challenges (Fox,2018). The updated published framework highlights some changes similar to the ones addressed by the COSO ERM framework. However, changes have yet to be made to the objective, which entails integrating risk management of the first framework in the organisation's strategic and operational processes. The significance of top management role, organisation's governance, and risk management integration were stressed in the updated version of the ISO 3100: 2018.

The upgraded version of the ISO 31000:2009, published in 2018, is shorter than the primary version. It gives organisations a holistic view of how risk management could be effectively implemented. Furthermore, it outlines the different principles and processes that can ensure the effective management of risks. It is argued that the upgraded version of the ISO 31000 guidelines follows a similar risk management approach as recommended by the updated COSO ERM framework, emphasising the decision-making process that should be supported by risk knowledge. Moreover, it places value creation and protection at the centre of its principles and suggests technology integration for achieving successful risk management (IRM, 2018, p. 9).

The new guidelines of ISO 31000:2018 suggest that ERM principles must be applied by every employee who is accountable and responsible for risk within the organisation for creating and sustaining value in risk management, decision-making, goal setting, and performance improvement activities. These principles can be applied to any type and size of organisation.

ERM principles suggest that risk management must support organisations in strategy-setting, attaining strategic directions (objectives), and a better-informed decision-making process.

The eight principles of the new ISO 31000 guidelines are (IRM, 2018, p.10):

1. ERM framework and processes should be tailored to the organisation's needs
2. Appropriate and prompt participation of different stakeholders is necessary.
3. A well-structured and understandable approach is necessary.
4. Risk management should be incorporated into organisational activities.
5. Risk management should predict, identify, and respond to changes.
6. Risk management should consider any problems caused by the information available.
7. Human and cultural factors can impact all aspects of risk management.
8. Risk management can be constantly enhanced through learning and experience.

It is clear from the above discussion that the changes made in the ISO31000 guideline emphasise the need for top management and the board of directors to be more involved in corporate risk management, and that risk management should be more aligned with strategy setting and objectives, and that processes responsible for evaluating the performance of the organisation must be incorporated with risk management.

In summary, the two versions of the ISO31000 guidelines highlight the process through which organisations could create value through risk management and emphasise the need to place responsibility for risk management decisions at the heart of risk management through the organisation of employees, processes, and technology (Sobel, 2018; IRM, 2018).

Moreover, as compared to the COSO ERM framework, which concentrates mainly on the internal stakeholders within organisations, the ISO 31000 standard has been designed in a way to respond to the needs of a wider group of stakeholders, including those accountable for the development of the risk management policies within the organisation; those responsible for ensuring that risk is managed effectively within the organisation or a particular organisational area, activity, or project; and those who are required to assess the effectiveness of the organisation in managing risk. In addition, the ISO 31000 standard suggests that organisations

should develop and implement a plan to communicate with the different external stakeholders. This is the engagement of the most appropriate external stakeholders and effective exchange of information and external reporting to adhere to the different regulatory, legal, and governance requirements through requesting feedback on the level of communication and consultation. In summary, communication is used to manage stakeholders' risks and build within the organisation among the various external stakeholders.

Several researchers have criticised and identified the limitations and shortcomings of the ISO31000 standards. For instance, Purdy (2010), Leech (2012), Lalonde and Boiral (2012), and Duojia and Xiaohong (2013) opined that ISO 31000: 2009 does not provide a clear description of how different organisational tools should be adopted in the performance process, consequently, it has been criticised for overlooking and neglecting the dynamics that exist between processes and the risk framework of the organisation. Therefore, the ISO31000:2009 standard needs clear, practical implementation guidance. Furthermore, another criticism goes to the ISO framework; according to Purdy (2010), a risk management process needs to be incorporated with the whole management system of an organisation, and it should receive a firm commitment from senior management. Purdy (2010) opined that the ISO 31000:2009 framework needs to provide clear insights into the risk management process; instead, it recommends that organisations fully integrate and personalise the framework to fit the organisation's needs. Therefore, the framework should be customised to respond to the organisation and consider the organisation's internal and external environment. In addition, organisations must allocate sufficient resources, invest in internal capital and risk management, and set internal and external reporting mechanisms to integrate risk management into organisational processes fully. Once fully adopted, the framework should be continuously monitored and revised to ensure that the feedback progresses the organisation in constantly

improving the framework. Therefore, the framework can only be applicable if an organisation has decided to invest in its human resources and risk management.

3.4.3 Standard and Poor's ERM Rating

Following the financial crisis of 2008, ERM has become increasingly relevant for insurance firms (Bonhert et al., 2019). In the context of European financial organisations, the emergence of Solvency II regulations has urged organisations to adopt an enterprise-wide approach to risk management on the entire risk portfolio and require them to have a risk management system that is consistent with the overall business strategy (Gatzert & Wesker, 2012; Bonhert et al., 2019). In 2005, rating agencies like Standard and Poor's started considering specific ERM rating categories to evaluate insurance companies' financial strength and creditworthiness (S&P, 2013a). Thus, according to the standards and Poor's publication, any company that adopts and implements an ERM framework, like the COSO ERM framework, will be recognised. The standard will not consider organisations implementing a widely recognised ERM framework as evidence of a successful risk management system or a robust ERM system. However, the standard's rating will mainly focus on the organisation's risk culture and strategic risk management as rating categories to rate the organisation's risk management effectiveness (S&P, 2015).

In 2007, Standard and Poor included a specific risk management rating in its overall rating for insurance firms. The index rating assesses the insurer's risk management culture, systems, processes, and practices. S&P assigns "ERM ratings" over five categories to rate the effectiveness of ERM practices within insurance firms.

The standard considers that having a strong and effective ERM indicates that firms are covering their entire risk portfolio and have developed their risk appetite and a risk strategy that allows them to avoid or manage risks outside the firm's risk tolerance (S&P, 2008). Top

management and BOD should own the ERM process and be fully accountable for its adoption. A firm with an ERM program must have a risk philosophy that considers risk from a risk/reward perspective rather than cost/benefit and understands that risk may have profitable opportunities.

Since risks and uncertainty have emerged and become an ongoing threat to organisations operating in various industries, S&P has developed 2008 an ERM rating for non-financial as part of their credit rating (Juthamon, 2016).

Figure 3. 4 S&P's ERM evaluation framework

(S&Ps, 2015)

To meet the rating criteria S&P, firms operating in the financial and non-financial sectors must focus on their risk management strategy, culture, and risk management. Firms

with high credit rating scores will benefit from lowering their borrowing costs and gaining the trust of both shareholders and investors (Hoyt & Liebenberg, 2011). The S&P standard did not provide a new enterprise risk management (ERM) definition; however, Hampton (2014) argued that though many organisations and industry professionals have guided ERM evaluation, the evaluation of S&P's remains the most effective.

3.5 Research Gap

The table below summarises the gap in the literature in the following areas of ERM: ERM evolution, integration of ERM, ERM integration with the strategy, ERM culture, ERM structure, ERM benefits, and ERM challenges.

Table 3 2 Research Gap

ERM Area	Gap	Research Author (Years)
ERM evolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Silo risk management approach -Immaturity of the ERM concept -Lack of understanding of how to customise ERM for an organisation -Perceiving ERM as an additional risk process -Weak understanding of the ERM concept 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Beasley <i>et al.</i> (2010). Lam (2010); Yin (2010); Leech (2012) Ashby (2011); Sadgrove (2016)

<p>ERM Integration with strategy</p>	<p>-Scarcity regarding the importance of incorporating ERM into the organisation's objectives and strategy (goals and strategic plans)</p> <p>-Overlooking the changes happening in the internal and external environments</p> <p>-Lack of understanding of the importance of integrating ERM with organisational factors</p>	<p>Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003); Chapman (2006, 2007) Frigo (2008, 2010) Killackey (2008; 2009) Beasley <i>et al.</i> (2010) Pape and Spekle (2012)</p>
<p>ERM culture</p>	<p>-Ambiguity on how to create an enterprise-wide culture that supports the adoption and implementation of ERM</p> <p>-Fear of disclosing information to top management</p> <p>-Lack of risk mindset and awareness among employees</p>	<p>Brooks (2010) Ashby, Power and Palermo (2012) Althonayan <i>et al.</i>(2012a;2012b;2013) Andronache <i>et al.</i> (2019)</p>

<p>ERM structure</p>	<p>-Ambiguity to define the appropriate structure of the ERM framework</p> <p>-Dismissing the effect of the ERM champion and the CRO on effective ERM adoption</p> <p>-Lack of or inadequacy of resources</p> <p>-Difficulty in defining an effective ownership structure.</p>	<p>Mikes (2007)</p> <p>Arena, Arnaboldi and Azzone (2010)</p> <p>Shortreed (2010)</p>
<p>ERM benefits</p>	<p>-Ambiguity surrounding long-term ERM benefits.</p> <p>-Lack of transparent and effective measures of the benefits of an ERM.</p> <p>-Not understanding the full potential of ERM</p>	<p>(Chapman,2007);</p> <p>(Fraser and Simkins, 2007)</p> <p>(Frigo,2008)</p> <p>(Gates,2009)</p> <p>Beasley <i>et al.</i> (2010)</p> <p>(RIMS, 2011);</p> <p>Olson (2015)</p>
<p>ERM challenges</p>	<p>-Compliance and regulatory pressures drive ERM adoption</p> <p>-Lack of understanding of the value added by ERM</p>	<p>(Liebenberg and Hoyt, 2003);</p> <p>(Kleffner, Lee, and McGannon, 2003);</p> <p>Power (2007);</p> <p>Lam (2007);</p>

	-Lack of clear, practical guidance on how ERM can be adopted effectively -Unwillingness to change current practices	Fraser and Simkins (2008) Stulz (2008); COSO (2010a) (Mikes and Kaplan, 2013)
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Source: Researcher's Construct

3.6 Evaluation of Relevant Theories to the context of the current research

Adding to the research, ERM research is still emerging, and a theoretical foundation is yet to be fully established (Lundqvist,2015). This section discusses the theories relevant to studying enterprise risk management. This section will examine open system theory, contingency theory, scientific management theory, and situation-specific theory.

3.6.1 Systems Theory

The open systems theory approach is considered one of the most modern means of thinking in the organisation; it aims to overcome the shortcomings of the traditional concept of organisation, which is built on the assumptions that an organisation is a closed system and detached from the external environment (Scott, 1994). In contrast, the open systems approach rejects the assumption that only a single universal model of organisations exists. Instead, it considers organisations as available and in continuous contact with the environment they operate for (Valeri,2021).

According to Burnes (2004), open systems theory refers to the concept that the environment influences organisations since those organisations depend on and serve in the context of their work environment. Similarly, Ansoff and Mc Donell (1990) postulate that

organisations are environment-serving and dependent on their occurrences. The environment is formed by social, political, economic, or technological forces (Wernerfelt, 1984). Those external forces are outside of the organisational boundaries. Therefore, they cannot be controlled, and hence, could cause uncertainty but also could provide resources that permit corporate survival and sustainability, thereby pressurising organisations to consider adopting a strategic way for risk management to minimise the uncertainty arising from the external environment while exploring accessible resources to survive (Carpenter et al., 2004). This implies that upon developing strategies within the organisation, management leaders should consider macro-environment forces and continuously ensure that the decision-making process considers risks spanning the external environment (Ansoff & McDonnell, 1990).

Advocates of the open systems theory argue that the survival of an organisation depends merely on its relationship with the outside environment (Scott & Davis, 2016). However, the approach of this theory has been widely criticised due to the need for more adoption of an integrated and interactional perspective using multiple resource dependence strategies (Otieno et al., 2019). Moreover, more information about the interaction between the theory and risk management practices, such as enterprise risk management, is needed. This leads to exploring different resource dependency and strategy relationships (Kim & Lim, 1988).

3.6.2 Contingency Theory

This theory is a modern organisational theory (Islam, 2015). It was first initiated in 1776 by Adam Smith (Hatch & Cunliffe, 2013). The particularity of contingency theory, as identified by Hatch and Cunliffe (2013), lies in its ability to identify the contingencies particular to a specific situation to derive the most appropriate fit among them. Weil and Olson (1989) referred to the "fit" perspective as the "variables fit."

According to Fisher (1998), the contingency theory falls between two different theories: the scientific management theory and the situational specific theory. While the former theory considers that a management approach can fit every type of organisation, the latter argues that the control systems of an organisation can only be determined by specific factors. Moreover, situation-specific theory considers that adopting governmental standards for different types of organisations will take much work. Accordingly, contingency theory, which postulates tailoring processes in a way that fits the situational contexts, has emerged (Donaldson, 2001). The contingency theory suggests there are only appropriate ways to manage the organisation across numerous situations and circumstances. In contrast, it holds that organisations act according to their assessment of their operating internal (culture, etc.) and external environmental factors (Kaplan & Mikes, 2014).

Enterprise risk management is still emerging and has been studied by several researchers. Risk management frameworks, like COSO (1992; 2004; 2013; 2016), ISO 31000 (2009; 2018), and AS/NZS 4360, have designed and provided generalised ERM frameworks and standards which could be risky to adopt by any organisation (Beasley et al., 2010)

Kaplan and Mikes (2014) advanced the contingency theory of ERM by studying enterprise risk management implementation among three different organisations, in which the senior managers and the BODs supported the implementation process. The findings of their study indicated that each sampled organisation had its specific approach toward ERM adoption. Therefore, the authors could not anticipate which ERM would be the most effective process. Therefore, all frameworks were considered adequate for adoption and implementation within the organisation. Mikes and Kaplan (2014) concluded that organisational effectiveness depends upon establishing an adequate fit between the ERM mix and contingent variables. People identify, analyse, and act on risk information that should be investigated. Not the framework,

as the same framework applied to different companies results in different outcomes due to the different organisational and cultural contexts.

In the same vein, Sae-Lim (2017) argues that, depending on the contingency theory, ERM must rest upon several factors and, importantly, divide into external factors. ERM significantly depends on internal factors like ERM resources and organisational context, and their concept of contingency theory is about the best way to embed specific systems in an organisation. The best way to embed any system relies on the company's internal context.

Accordingly, the researcher will only recommend implementing one framework over other existing frameworks in some situations and different types of organisations. Therefore, the contingency theory is most relevant for developing the proposed ERM adoption framework.

Vorbeda et al. (2011) argued that contingency theory in practice represents the position of managers when making decisions based on their organisational characteristics and the different internal factors that interact with the organisation. Therefore, a SWOT analysis was conducted to analyse the proposed ERM adoption framework, allowing top management and executives within the insurance firm to identify their organisations and strengths and the external threats and opportunities (Kaplan & Mikes, 2014).

3.7 The Proposed ERM Adoption Framework

Developing an ERM adoption framework that specifically targets the Algerian insurance industry represents the main aim of this research because of the lack of ERM adoption frameworks that consider the nature, the operating environment, and the specific needs of firms operating in this industry and geographical context. Our review of the literature on Enterprise risk management in Chapter 2, along with the evaluation of the widely existing frameworks in this chapter, have revealed a lack of clear, practical guidance necessary for top

management in order to tackle organisational risks effectively, guided the researcher to the development of the theoretical framework for the present study.

The proposed ERM adoption framework is developed to fulfil different objectives concerning the Algerian insurance industry:

- Address both changing factors of the internal and external environment of the Algerian insurance industry in the ERM process;
- Integrates organisational culture and strategy when developing ERM;
- Assist the insurance firms studied in adopting the proposed ERM framework;
- Considers the particular needs of the Algerian insurance industry;
- Developing a comprehensive framework that allows firms operating in the insurance industry to align organisational objectives and management processes with ERM practices.

3.8 The components of the proposed ERM adoption framework

The proposed ERM adoption framework is developed from the critical shortcomings identified in the literature. The proposed framework will act as a tool to demonstrate the critical organisational factors that should be aligned within the internal and external environments to achieve an effective ERM. The proposed framework is simple, well-defined, transparent, and provides clear guidance for adopting an ERM.

The proposed framework presented in Figure 3.5 comprises four interrelated components that represent the critical elements of the organisation's internal environment. Each component comprises several elements that can be impacted by political, financial, legal, economic, and cultural changes surrounding the external environment.

Figure 3.5 The Proposed ERM Adoption Framework

Source: The researcher

The proposed ERM adoption framework aims to articulate the core risks of an organisation and offer practical ways to tackle those risks. At its core, ERM focuses on establishing reliable and consistent enterprise-wide communication at all organisational levels (Shimpi, 2005). Therefore, senior managers would be able to communicate their actions and decisions only if credible risk information is available instantly (Miller, 1992)

Financial institutions, in general, and insurance firms, in particular, face various complex risks at their operational and strategic levels. Therefore, Enterprise Risk Management

should be aligned with developing the organisation's strategy and consider the principal risks facing the critical areas of the organisation's operations (Althonayan et al., 2011b). As top management develops the organisation's strategic direction, attention should be paid to developing the strategic objectives in line with the overall business strategy (Noy, 2003). Accordingly, ERM should be integrated within the organisation's strategic process and become attached to achieve the organisational objectives (Althonayan et al., 2012b).

ERM should be highly integrated within the business and corporate strategies of an organisation so that, when organisations establish their vision, mission, and objectives, risks will be transformed from being "individual hazards" into risks at "the strategic level" (Oldwisk, 2012). However, when incorporating ERM with business and strategic plans, senior management should focus on ensuring that this alignment will contribute to achieving organisational objectives, thereby optimising shareholder value (Monahan, 2008).

According to Simkins (2008), a transparent business and corporate strategy aligned adequately with a well-defined ERM process is the key to achieving the organisation's goals and objectives. In the meantime, if the risk management framework is not adequately aligned with strategies, organisations could engage in business activities that could lead to unjustified risks (Simkins & Ramirez, 2008).

Of importance, though, is the identification of the possible vital risks that an organisation could confront, which is a crucial step when designing and proposing a practical ERM framework. Moreover, for ERM to be incorporated into business and corporate strategies, proper coordination among groups of employees involved in the various departments and at different levels of the organisation should exist. Moreover, A thorough comprehension of ERM strategies by top managers and employees at other levels of the organisation promotes their commitment to fulfilling the ERM process (Teuten, 2005). furthermore, as discussed by Beasley et al. (2010), ERM and strategy should be integrated, and their alignment should be

well-defined and understood to promote positive actions among employees about the ERM process.

The proposed adoption framework should cover vital organisational functions and the critical roles for integrating the management processes. This is important in order to minimise the isolation of the various silos within the organisation, which tends to argue against the benefits of ERM and decrease risk transparency. Another significant factor, as Mylrea and Lattimore (2010) emphasise, is that identifying and understanding the organisation's risks helps top management determine that appropriately can trigger downside impacts and exceed the organisation's risk tolerance. Hence, the senior management should have the ability to ensure that information flow is transparent enough in order to end silo reporting. Operating in a complex environment surrounded by complexity and different risks, insurance leaders face the challenge of understanding how the different business departments and organisations interact and how specific risks are managed interdependently (Shenkir & Walker, 2006).

The following subsection addresses the input factors vital to the developed ERM adoption framework.

3.8.1 The Input Factors of the proposed ERM adoption framework

The input factors of the proposed adoption framework arise from the vision and mission determined by the organisation (Figure 3.5). The input factors significantly affect the organisation's strategic direction (AON, 2007).

Every insurance firm has its specific input factors for the ERM embedding. According to Wilson (2009), the input of an organisation may be established only when top managers have an in-depth understanding of their organisation's strategies and objectives.

Based on the review of different academic papers, findings, and gaps in knowledge identified in Chapter 2 and extended in this chapter, the primary inputs of the developed framework are:

- Mission, vision, and values of the organisation
- Strategies and objectives
- Risk appetite that aligns with risk tolerance
- Risk oversight
- Corporate governance

Since risk forms a vital component of the business environment, organisations are urged to establish a well-defined strategy that considers risk to cope with the market's unpredictability and volatility (Althonayan et al., 2011b).

The organisation's strategy is considered an input for the proposed framework to incorporate its risk appetite with its established risk tolerance. The researcher regards ERM integration with strategy as crucial for the organisation to map high-priority risks at the corporate strategy and strategic planning levels (RIMS, 2012). An in-depth understanding and awareness of the constraints guiding organisational risk appetite and risk tolerance would help business leaders become more prepared to control any unforeseen risks. Accordingly, having a clear and balanced risk appetite that is well-aligned with the risk tolerance of the risk appetite and the organisational strategy is deemed crucial in ERM alignment (Konarsky, 2010).

According to Lam (2010), aligning ERM with the strategy helps the organisation build a balanced risk appetite and exposure to the strategic business goals. One essential way to integrate risk with the strategic setting is by defining it from an enterprise-wide statement. Instead of concentrating on implementing a strategy relevant to the strategic objectives,

organisations should examine the level of the risks that are key to reaching their goals (Beasley et al., 2010).

Another critical factor that is relevant to the proposed ERM adoption framework is senior management support. The engagement of the senior management in ERM is critical to establishing a sustainable and effective program (Beasley et al., 2010). Senior managers are challenged to understand the ERM concept well (Deloitte, 2011).

Beasley et al. (2010) suggested a few recommendations in order to achieve the active involvement of top management:

- Ensure that ERM is considered a top priority by top management;
- Ensure that top management is committed to ERM;
- Include ERM within the financial compensations of top management;
- Provide examples of real success stories of ERM implementation;
- Use ERM as an opportunity that can lead to the development of the organisation (Beasley et al., 2010)

The proposed ERM adoption framework (Figure 3.5) promotes continuous communication among "the top" (top management), "the middle" (mid-level management), and employees at various other levels or dimensions within the organisation (AON, 2007). According to Arena et al. (2010), encouraging enterprise-wide communication at all organisational levels makes employees more committed and engaged in discussions and risk-based processes.

It is argued that there is a link between risk management and corporate governance. Some of the two subjects are related to ERM integration in the organisation. In general, organisations develop strategies in order to achieve a set of goals. However, every single strategy has a set of different risks that should be tackled to meet the set objectives (Aven,

2010). In this context, corporate governance principles can be used when setting risk management policies to allow organisations to reach their goals. Sound corporate governance clearly defines the roles of the management, the BOD, and shareholders while focusing specifically on ERM (Manab et al., 2010). The proposed ERM adoption framework takes into consideration three main pillars of corporate governance: 1) the board supports corporate governance, 2) the culture of performance and reward included by top management, and 3) the consideration of shareholders' requirements (Richard et al., 2010). Furthermore, senior management needs to align corporate governance with organisational strategies to reach an appropriate level of transparency in risk-taking, leading to better and more informed decisions (Beasley et al., 2010).

According to Tonello (2007), several strategic benefits can arise from aligning corporate governance principles with risk management: first, reducing cost and inefficiency by aggregating risks through allowing adequate quantification of risks and risk response since business synergies are created; Second, it allows the identification of risk interdependencies; and third, help management reach better investment decisions that are based on risk-based decision (Frigo & Anderson, 2011).

3.8.2 The Core components (elements) of the developed framework

This section presents the core elements of the proposed ERM adoption framework. The proposed framework aims to assist organisations in establishing sustainable and well-informed decision-making that includes risk and improving organisations' financial and non-financial positions. The following subsections will identify some of ERM's key components, such as risk culture, infrastructure, and processes, that are crucial to achieving a competitive edge.

3.8.3 ERM Culture

It is argued that an enterprise-wide risk culture is a critical element of an ERM (Ashby et al., 2012). Risk Culture comprises awareness, attitudes, and behaviours of people within an organisation toward risk (Deloitte, 2012). Details on the importance of enterprise-wide risk culture to achieving a successful ERM adoption were discussed earlier in chapter two.

Wong (2020) states that an enterprise-wide culture is fundamental to effective risk management. In managing risk effectively, it is essential to identify what drives and motivates top management when taking risks (Deloitte, 2012b). Following the global financial crisis 2008, a weak risk culture was one of the main contributors to the failure of many financial organisations (Ashby et al., 2013; De Jonghe et al., 2013; Wong, 2020). Culture has been identified as the most crucial element for making organisations risk-intelligent, where everyone becomes more liable and takes responsibility for managing risks, protecting the organisation, and adding value (Deloitte, 2011).

An organisation's culture is significant in directing how key risks should be managed within a highly volatile and uncertain business landscape (Shein, 1990). A strong, developed, and solid enterprise-wide risk culture can lead organisations to achieve competitive advantage and become more resilient. However, an underdeveloped culture towards risks would make organisations unstable and cause them to lack confidence (Deloitte, 2012b). However, transforming risk into a competitive advantage requires significant accountability. Critical risks should be well-defined and understood by the organisation's management and all other stakeholders to achieve a consistent risk approach.

Transparent communication, culture, and appropriate understanding of policies governing risks, appetite, and tolerance are fundamental elements of an enterprise-wide risk culture. Transparent communication of timely risk information from top-down, bottom-up, and across all organisational levels is essential for developing an ERM culture (Deloitte, 2012; EY,

2014b; IRM, 2012; Protiviti, 2014; PwC, 2012). Regular dialogue about risk can create a common risk language and an intimidation-free atmosphere and further develop the ERM culture (Hallowell et al.,2013). Mikes and Kaplan (2014) found that the support of senior management towards creating a no-blame culture would encourage employees to communicate their ideas and discuss issues related to risk, which they were worried about.

The transparency and fluidity of the communication process and discussion between business leaders, employees, and all business levels can assist all the stakeholders across the organisation in having a better understanding of the risk appetite and risk tolerance levels that their organisation can bear (Wong, 2020)

Respect for norms, ethics, and behaviours, which illustrates key characteristics of cultural attributes such as respect for rules, contributes to enhancing the planning process within an organisation (Pagach & Warr, 2010). Responding to risks is the next level of an enterprise-wide culture. This involves promoting the importance of reporting and responding to risks proactively while being oriented toward risk. The process entails identifying stakeholders, evaluating their commitments, and developing robust communication channels to ensure continuous feedback. This demonstrates that an organisation's well-developed and strong ERM culture is critical in encouraging both top-down and bottom-up communication (Althonayan et al., 2012b).

At last, the mindset of risk is another critical component of an enterprise-wide culture. It demonstrates the criticality and significance of risk information, information-sharing, and awareness (Althonayan et al., 2012). This is because some organisations tend to face problems like top management lacking vital data that is necessary to tackle risk effectively; this is sometimes because employees retain information that is crucial to the top management in the decision-making process just because they fear that if that information is shared, it may affect their performance negatively (Bloomberg Business Week, 2010).

It is worth mentioning that the inclusion of the element ERM in the proposed ERM adoption framework is influenced and supported by the academic and empirical research reviewed in Chapter 2 of this study. The literature reviewed has revealed that developing and sustaining a regime ERM risk culture is critical to maintaining an effective ERM.

3.8.4 ERM Process

ERM process is another critical core component of the ERM adoption framework; it is crucial to have a process that assists in identifying, analysing, quantifying, mitigating, treating, and monitoring risks that can hinder the achievement of organisational objectives (ISO, 2009). Risk management is how an organisation aims to enhance its capabilities for attaining its business, operational, and strategic directions (COSO, 2017). Therefore, for organisations to maximise ERM, ERM must be incorporated with the existing strategies, processes, and plans at all levels (Smart & Creelman, 2009). The planning process entails establishing and implementing actions to assist organisations in meeting objectives.

Figure 3.6 shows the ERM process aligned with strategic and operational planning.

Aligning ERM with strategic and operational planning can benefit the organisation by improving its performance, implementing its strategies, and attaining key objectives (Frigo, 2008). As demonstrated in Figure 3.6, linking the ERM process to the planning process is the key that ensures constant communication of the objectives, planning, and risk.

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Figure 3. 6 Aligning ERM with strategic planning processes

Source: (AS/NZS, 2004)

The “Establish the context” process focuses on organisations implementing strategies, including possible risks that may affect business activities (AS/NZS, 2009; COSO, 2004b; CSA, 2003; IRM et al., 2002; ISO, 2009).

By identifying its objectives, an organisation needs to formulate its main strategies and ensure that they can be implemented in its structure. Risk-tackling is a critical element of the ERM process; therefore, it should be closely aligned with risk identification and assessment. Hence, inputs from identifying and assessing risk can determine the most appropriate strategies (AS/NZS, 2009; ISO, 2009). Once appropriate strategies are formulated, the organisation can receive ERM feedback. This would assist the organisation in reviewing its assumption regarding risk and strategies, resulting in more preparation to adjust to internal and external conditions.

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3.8.5 ERM Integration

ERM integration is another fundamental element of the proposed framework. The ERM integration has five components: strategic planning process, operational processes, ERM structure and ownership, performance management, and enterprise-wide communication. According to Lam (2010), ERM should be integrated into an organisation's critical processes to optimise the organisation's risk profile. In addition, when ERM is aligned with organisational strategies, it provides a significant opportunity for ERM integration. Nevertheless, a critical yet vital element towards establishing an ERM is the availability of a transparent risk ownership structure and good communication among ERM resources and critical risks (IRM, 2012).

According to Beasley *et al.* (2003), *brainstorming within the organisation can contribute to creating value for ERM if individuals openly and freely converse about risks and challenges.*

Researchers like Power (2004) and Archer *et al.* (2010) *argue that a consistent well-balanced enterprise risk culture that supports an organisation's risks and objectives is crucial to achieving an effective ERM integration.* Nevertheless, in order to achieve this, ERM integration must become a part of the natural risk mindset of employees and management (Dafikpaku, 2011)

3.8.6 ERM Infrastructure

The final element of the proposed ERM adoption framework is a unified enterprise-wide risk infrastructure. As highlighted in Figure 3.5 (the proposed framework), ERM infrastructure comprises six core elements: risk management policies and frameworks, governance, ERM oversight structure, risk appetite and tolerance, risk data, and technologies and tools supporting ERM.

The complex nature of financial institutions like insurance firms and the increasingly volatile operating environment made those firms face difficulties in creating a fixed-risk platform. Nevertheless, transparent and well-incorporated risk data are highly significant in formulating a solid risk reporting strategy and ensuring senior managers' excellent flow of risk-based information (Hofmann, 2009). Thus, a timely generation of data and risk reports is required to ensure adequate and proper adoption and implementation of ERM alignment. According to Althonayan et al. (2011b), risk architecture that facilitates transparent collection, processing, storing, presenting, and reporting data is fundamental.

Another element of the ERM infrastructure is having well-defined risk tolerance and risk appetite. Risk tolerance refers to the amount of risk an organisation can tolerate (IRM, 2011); on the other hand, risk appetite represents the willingness and ability of an organisation to take risks (IRM, 2011). According to Pagach and Warr (2010), an organisation's top management is responsible for establishing the amount and risk the organisation can bear without exposing the organisational performance to risk.

3.9 The benefits and outcomes of the developed ERM adoption framework

The outcomes of the proposed ERM adoption framework reflect the organisational standing in which the proposed adoption framework acts as a driver that motivates the attainment of the benefits of the proposed adoption framework. A primary indicator of the success of the proposed framework would be reflected by creating a competitive advantage and value for the organisation adopting it (Elahi, 2010). Based on findings from Chapter 2, key ERM benefits can be classified into three main categories, namely, business, corporate, and operational.

As illustrated in Figure 3.5, the proposed ERM adoption framework focuses on value

creation at the organisational level and, in particular, helps organisations target deficiencies that can affect their business performance, for instance, failing to embed ERM into the overall business strategy. Additionally, the proposed framework assists management in identifying effective risk management practices, allowing them to incorporate those practices at other levels of the organisation (Fraser & Simkins, 2007). Understanding its existing practices and the risks that might be considered, mitigated, transferred, avoided, or explored will help decrease disagreements among top management about the organisation's capabilities to bear those risks (Frigo & Ramaswamy, 2010). All the benefits (outputs) of the proposed ERM adoption framework will be further investigated in detail and discussed in the following chapters.

3.10 Importance of developing Key Risks Indicators (KRI's) and Key Performance Indicators (KPI's)

Relying on key performance indicators, KPIs that examine past events have proven ineffective and resulted in a deficient risk management strategy (Kaplan, 2009). While Key performance indicators (KPIs) ask questions such as "Are we achieving the desired organisation's performance?", key risk indicators (KRIs) report how the risk profile of the organisation is changing and whether this change is by the acceptable risk tolerance level of the organisation or not. In addition, KRIs could provide data on potential risks that an organisation may face (Taylor & Davies, 2003), which happens by anticipating the downside of risk on the organisation's performance (Smart & Creelman, 2009). For instance, KPIs can measure the anticipated performance, and KRIs can foresee the potential downside risk or predict the instability of the performance (Smart & Creelman, 2009).

It is argued that KRIs are a critical element of a risk management framework (Al-Farsi, 2020). For example, suppose an organisation adopts its assessment tool for identifying and controlling risks. In that case, using key risk indicators enables the organisation to monitor this process at different stages and helps them determine the level of their risk appetite (Immaneni et al., 2004). KRIs could help organisations identify whether risk tolerance levels have been exceeded, inform management, and recommend actions and necessary changes (Beasley & Frigo, 2010; COSO, 2012). Thus, when used appropriately, those tools can provide organisations with a clearer vision that permits the tracking of corporate strategies and hence driving them through the benefit of change (Frigo, 2002)

Nevertheless, Althonayan et al. (2011) advocate that KRIs have better efficiency in practice if they are developed parallel to Key performance indicators and in line with the thresholds system. The importance of developing key risk indicators lies in assisting top managers in producing specific procedures that help them provide insight into the effect those risks could have on achieving the organisation's strategic goals. To achieve this, business leaders and the overall management team should understand the organisation's objectives in-depth before establishing KRI. Most organisations recognise that the development of critical risk indicators is not an easy task. Therefore, some organisations tend to develop risk indicators that are less important to their area of specialisation, and financial institutions usually focus on developing indicators related in general to market or credit risks. Therefore, they face challenges when developing KRI's for financial, technology, or operational risks (Lam, 2005). Regarding this, Lam (2005) recommended various areas within an organisation where KRIs could be developed from 1) policies and regulations, 2) strategies and objectives, 3) previous losses and incidents, 4) shareholders' requirements, and 5) risk assessments.

Initiating KRIs could happen through a top-down or bottom-up approach (Immaneni et al., 2004). The top-down approach permits the assessment of different risks and objectives, proceeds with developing the most suitable KRI risk, and ensures they are communicated toward the bottom. In the meantime, the bottom-up approach can do this by developing KRIs for every business level (Immaneni et al., 2004). KRIs and KPIs are considered components of the proposed ERM framework as they are developed for top management to keep track of constant threats that could develop internally or externally and review its ERM strategy accordingly (COSO, 2010b).

3.11 Chapter Summary

Regardless of the increased attention and awareness of adopting an ERM approach, organisations lack an understanding of its benefits and added strategic value. Accordingly, top management should adopt ERM to ensure sustainable business performance.

According to findings from Chapter 2, one of the critical challenges organisations face is the lack of practical guidance to develop an effective ERM. Having clear guidance towards ERM adoption would assist senior management in deploying the appropriate structure at an enterprise level, which would be integrated with the business's core strategies and organisational risk culture, all embedded within the business processes.

The present chapter discussed the development of the proposed ERM adoption framework. The proposed framework has been mainly developed to overcome the current gaps highlighted by the literature reviewed in chapter two. The framework will assist organisations in upgrading their risk management processes to cope with the volatile business environment by aligning the key elements with the strategic risk approach. Accordingly, the proposed framework aims to enhance organisational performance, manage potential risks that could negatively impact organisational performance, and improve methods to achieve strategic

objectives.

The next chapter will present the research methodology and methods adopted to conduct this research.

4 Chapter Four: Research Design and Methodology

4.1 Introduction

After reviewing the relevant literature and identifying the research gap in the previous chapters, the present chapter will discuss the choice of the methodology for this research, research design, research methods, and instruments and methods used to achieve the research objectives. This exploratory research will adopt the interpretive inductive research approach and use non-probability purposive sampling to conduct 25 qualitative semi-structured in-depth interviews. Moreover, this research will adopt the thematic analysis technique to analyze and present the data collected.

The following figure will illustrate the chapter structure.

Figure 4. 1 Chapter structure

Source: Researcher's construct

4.2 Research Paradigms and Research Philosophy

The current section demonstrates the research philosophy among other philosophies that direct the current research. Research philosophy provides a philosophical viewpoint on the meaning of knowledge acquisition. Research philosophy refers to the way researchers view the world. In essence, it reflects the set of assumptions and beliefs of the researcher when embarking upon developing knowledge (Saunders et al., 2019).

Each philosophy comprises different types of assumptions: ontological and epistemological (Saunders, 2015). For both social and scientific researchers, ontology and epistemology play an essential role in the choice of research methodology (Gill et al., 2014). Ontological assumptions of social research include subjectivism, constructionism, and phenomenology. Since the current study falls into the social research category, the ontological assumptions are based on social ontology, where organisations are considered social entities (Bryman & Bell, 2011)

Ontology is defined as "the study of being or the science"; it is concerned with the form and nature of reality (Fletcher, 2017) in a study conducted by Hatch and Cunliffe (2006), which defined reality by two contrasting positions, where participants were asked to describe their perceptions of reality. In conclusion, individuals define reality from two broad contrasting positions- objective and subjective.

Objectivism embraces the idea that reality is independent of the researcher; in contrast, subjectivism holds that reality is the outcome of social processes (Neuman,2003). Epistemology refers to the nature of the relationship that exists between the researcher (the knower), and it denotes "the nature of human knowledge and understanding that can be acquired through different types of inquiry and alternative methods of investigation" (Kothari, 2004). epistemology poses the following questions: What is the relationship between the knower and what is known? Oh, do we know what we know? Does that count as knowledge?

Gill, Johnson and Clark (2014) opined that a well-developed and consistent set of assumptions to establish a reliable research philosophy underpins the choice of the research approach, research strategy, data collection process, data analysis, and interpretation of the findings. Therefore, it is essential to highlight the research paradigms based on their assumptions.

Paradigm reveals how individuals view the world. Creswell (2015) stated that "we all bring a worldview (or paradigm) to our research, whether we make it explicit or not" (Creswell, 2015, p. 16). Reswell (2015) claims that the values that form the way we conduct research "may relate to what type of evidence we use to make claims (epistemology) or whether we feel that reality is multiple or singular (ontology)". Any research paradigms, such as interpretivism, positivism, constructivism, and critical realism, are used in research. The following section will outline the most adopted research paradigms in business and management research and provide justifications.

4.2.1 Positivism

The positivism paradigm is a philosophical stance that advocates applying natural sciences methods to study social reality (Malhotra, 2020). This paradigm assumes objective facts offer the best scientific evidence to be tested and confirmed objectively by collecting measurable and quantifiable data (Saunders et al., 2019). Furthermore, positivist researchers often use existing theories to develop and test hypotheses using quantitative methods (Bell et al., 2019). As a justification, advocates of positivism believe that using a highly structured methodology facilitates replication (Uma et al., 2019).

Nevertheless, according to Zikmund et al. (2013), the law-like generalisation of the positivism paradigm is less likely to offer a rich and complex understanding of reality, in

contrast to the subjective view of knowledge that appreciates differences in individual experience and contexts and seeks to understand the phenomenon in its natural settings.

As the study aims to gain a rich understanding of the adoption of ERM, practices, and challenges in a new geographical context and a specific industry, the insurance industry, a positivist research paradigm would not be appropriate for this study. Moreover, having no previous reference or research in the geographical setting studied that can be tested and confirmed for generalisability validates this study's unsuitability and inappropriateness of positivism.

4.2.2 Critical Realism

The critical realism paradigm considers reality as external and independent yet not directly accessible through observation (Ntseane, 2012). Instead, what individuals experience are sensations that are manifestations of the things in the real world instead of the fundamental things (Saunders et al., 2019). According to Bhaskar and Hartwig (2011), the reality could only be understood if we understand the social structures that gave rise to the phenomenon studied. In other words, critical realism philosophy emphasises that reality is separate from our description of it (Zikmund et al., 2013). Most critical realist studies take the form of in-depth historical analysis investigating the social and organisational structures and how they change over time (Reed, 2005). Accordingly, critical realism philosophy has yet to be used for this study.

4.2.3 Interpretivism

According to the researchers' objectives, interpretivism focuses on understanding the world based on an individual's perception of the world. In the opinion of Mohajan (2018), interpretivism has allowed the adoption of the qualitative methodology. It has also allowed for measuring people's behaviours and conducting interviews.

Myers (2013) argued that "interpretivism, as the name implies, involves researchers interpreting study elements. Thus, interpretivism integrates human interest into a study." The interpretivism paradigm allows the researcher to be part of society. As stated by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, reality within the interpretive paradigm is socially constructed and "the interpretive researchers assume language, consciousness, shared meaning, and instruments".

Researchers like Hill and Harrison (2009) and Zikmund et al. (2013) advocated that the social worlds of a human being cannot be studied similarly to physical phenomena, which requires a subjective approach to understand social reality. Moreover, different people from different cultural backgrounds, in different circumstances, and at different timeframes can provide different meanings, creating and experiencing various social realities (Saunders et al., 2019). These differences cannot be ignored or generalised objectively (Burrell & Morgan, 2016). Accordingly, it is essential to take an interpretive approach to create richer understandings, perceptions, and interpretations of the contexts and social worlds to generate new knowledge. This approach is particularly appropriate in business and management studies as different individuals within an organisation come from different professional and educational backgrounds and perceive reality differently. Therefore, a subjective approach can be more suitable to understand complex and multiple realities. Nevertheless, interpretivism as a philosophical stance has often been criticised for the biases of the selectivity and interpretation of reality (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018)

This research selects and adopts the interpretive philosophical stance because the challenges of ERM adoption and implementation in the Algerian insurance industry cannot be generalised at this stage, with no previous studies informing the adoption and implementation challenges of an ERM program or the key factors that are necessary for its adoption and implementation within the Algerian insurance industry. Furthermore, through the adoption of

the interpretivism philosophy, the research aims to enhance the understanding and explanation of the process of adoption of ERM among insurers as well as the challenges associated with this adoption through the lens of different individuals participating in the research along their personal experiences (Blumberg et al., 2014; Gray, 2014; Taylor et al., 2016). Such an approach is most appropriate for this research. It is justified by the lack of literature on clear insight concerning the adoption of ERM within the Algerian insurance industry and the scarcity of challenges affecting this adoption within the context studied, where practical insights and meaning prevail (Thomas, 2017).

4.3 Research Approach

This section of the chapter highlights the different research approaches and justifies the chosen research approach for the study.

A research approach represents the plans and procedures upon which decisions underpin data collection, analysis, and interpretation (Creswell, 2014). Given the exploratory specificity of this research, the research study is based upon an inductive approach because data collection and analysis intend to explain patterns, facts, causes, and meanings (Sanders et al., 2009; Blumberg et al., 2014; Gray, 2014; Saunders et al., 2019).

The research approach involves the most appropriate logical reasoning for the research. The proper selection of the research approach allows for emphasising the importance of explaining the findings and outcomes of the research paper (Wiek & Lang, 2016). Therefore, correctly applying the research approach is essential in developing the validity and reliability of the findings.

The extent to which the researcher is clear about theory raises an essential question regarding the research design adopted for the study. This is frequently portrayed as two contrasting approaches, deductive and inductive. Two approaches to theory development exist:

Deductive and Inductive; the former entails theory testing, whereas the latter involves theory building (Creswell, 2014). The differences between the two approaches are reflected in two main scientific paradigms: the deductive approach is represented in the positivist paradigm, whereas the inductive approach is represented in the interpretive paradigm (Suddaby, 2006; Bell et al., 2019).

4.3.1 The Deductive Approach

According to Mackey and Gass (2015), the deductive approach is about establishing hypotheses that must be empirically justified. Hypotheses are designed depending on what we know about the phenomenon and its theoretical foundation. Research entails developing a conceptual and theoretical structure tested through empirical observation (Bryman et al., 2011). In the context of ERM and as per the literature, little is known about the introduction and adoption of ERM among Algerian insurers. Therefore, there needs to be more foundation to develop a hypothesis. Consequently, it is imperative to investigate the ERM practices, adoption, and factors determining its effective adoption to propose a specific framework in the context and nature of the industry studied. As a result, deductive reasoning is unsuitable for the current study and needs to fit the research objectives.

Figure 4. 2 Illustrates the process of theory testing in a study following the deductive approach.

Source: Burney (2008)

Deductive research has been criticised for its limited capability to comprise unpredicted factors that may emerge in theory development, regardless of its potential significance that could contribute to the research.

4.3.2 The Inductive Approach

The inductive reasoning progresses in contrast to the deductive reasoning. Inductive research allows the generation of new theories or conceptual frameworks from the data collected (Trochim, 2000; Walliman, 2011). Thus, Inductive research moves the study from particular to general, as general assumptions are induced from an individual's observation of general patterns (Creswell & Clark, 2007). Accordingly, inductive reasoning follows a 'bottom-up' approach. Therefore, the study outcomes would appear based on the investigation of the research problem, and the theory would be established post-analysis (Saunders et al., 2019).

After careful consideration of both deductive and inductive research approaches, an inductive approach is considered most appropriate since understanding ERM adoption challenges and factors that shape its adoption in the context of Algerian insurers is academically unknown. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the practice and the challenges facing ERM adoption in Algeria in order to propose an ERM adoption framework that is specific in nature and context.

Carson et al. (2001) argued that inductive and deductive approaches should be combined because using a solely inductive approach ignores current theory, while a deductive approach may not create relevant or new theories. The current researcher disagrees with the

above standpoints. When adopting inductive reasoning, existing theories are not ignored; by adopting an inductive research technique, the researcher only investigates a subject once they develop an in-depth understanding of it (Saunders et al., 2007). The current research uses an inductive approach and builds a theoretical framework based on the literature reviewed in chapter two, which will serve as a foundation for the research.

Nevertheless, this theoretical framework is not considered or viewed as a restrictive set of assumptions congruent with the interpretive research philosophy(Saunders et al., 2019). Accordingly, this research adopts an inductive approach to draw broad conclusions on ERM, which is still considered an uncharted topic in developing countries such as Algeria (Edmondson & McManus, 2007). By adopting an inductive approach, qualitative research seeks to understand better the factors shaping influences and clarify the researcher and participant experiences (Bryman & Burgess, 2002). Thus, this type of research focuses on building and developing a design rather than being based on an existing prior theory to begin the research since it is sometimes impossible or even hard to predict results due to the diversity in viewpoints that researcher and participant share (Bryman & Burgess, 2006).

Figure 4. 3 Inductive Approach

Source: (Burney,2008)

Table 4.1 Outlines critical perspectives of the deductive and inductive research approach that justify further the adoption of the induction approach and the unsuitability of the deductive approach to the current study.

Figure 4. 4. Key perspectives of the deductive and inductive research approach

	Deductive	Inductive
Meaning	It begins with theory-driven hypotheses that guide the data collection and analysis process.	It begins with research questions and empirical data in order to generate theories.
Logic	Logic and reality are valid.	Logic, however, may or may not be accurate in reality.
Generalisability	Moves from general to specific	Moves from specific to general
Data Usage	The collected data is used to assess the hypotheses that relate to existing theories.	The collected data is used to investigate the topic, identify patterns, and generate a conceptual framework.
Theory	It entails testing or verifying theory.	It entails Generating and building theory.

Source: Adapted from Cameron and Price (2009), Bell, Bryman and Harley (2019), Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019), and Malhotra (2020)

This section presented the research approach selected for the present research. The following section will highlight existing research methods and provide justifications for the chosen research method.

4.4 Research Method

As highlighted by the above chapters, the current study is exploratory research, which aims to scrutinise the potential strategic challenges managers perceive in introducing enterprise risk management to an Algerian insurance company. Therefore, to achieve the purpose of the study, appropriate research methods that can demonstrate the perception of managers, experience, and insight should be employed. Hence, the research method that is considered most suitable for the current study will be adopted by Guba (1981, p.76). Thus, considering the lack of empirical knowledge on the challenges facing the adoption of an ERM, there is a need to explore this phenomenon from an individual point of view; qualitative research is seen as more appropriate than quantitative research methods to explore the problem (Malhorta, 2020). Thus, the current study deals with the social world rather than the world of nature, making the quantitative research method inappropriate in the current investigation.

Studying the social world is different from studying natural events. The qualitative research method is a type of social inquiry that deals mainly with how individuals interpret and view their experiences within the social world. In contrast to the quantitative method of inquiry, qualitative research helps build holistic pictures, analyse words, and report human views in detail. Thus, quantitative methods rely on numerical data such as numbers and figures, whereas qualitative studies consider words and textual narratives as the primary source of data (Blumberg et al., 2011)

Merriam (2009) states that researchers who ought to conduct a qualitative research approach are those who are willing to understand how reality is constructed from an individual's point of view in the world they live in, the thing that cannot be achieved by the quantitative research approach where mostly methods are based on laboratory tests and questionnaires which is not congruent with the purpose of this study.

The table below discusses the differences between the quantitative, qualitative and mixed research methods.

Table 4.3

Figure 4. 5 Comparison of quantitative, qualitative, and mixed research methods

	Qualitative method	Quantitative method	Mixed method
Goals	It allows one to gain an in-depth understanding of the reason and motives (Bryman & Harley, 2019)	Quantifying and generalising the findings from the representative sample of the population (Saunders et al., 2019)	It allows for a better understanding of the phenomenon investigated and yields strong evidence that covers depth and breadth (Wedawatta & Ingirige, 2016)
Advantages	It enables the researcher to provide an in-depth understanding of the subject studied (Silverman, 2016) It can be conducted with the use of a small sample (Bell et al., 2019)	Ensure high validity as the analysis of the data collected is performed straightforwardly, therefore, outcomes are bias-free (Cameron & Price, 2009; Rich, 2018)	It allows the triangulation of data collected, which strengthens the outcomes of the research (Nyanga, 2012)

		It requires less time compared to the qualitative method (Malhortra, 2020)	
Disadvantages	It is too subjective, and findings cannot be generalised or duplicated like for like. Often criticised for the transparency issue (Gupta, 2015) Criticised for the sample bias (Bell et al., 2019)	Highly structured Requires a larger sample of the population (Rich, 2018) Proving no insights into the findings, a thing which can be misleading (Bell et al., 2019)	Time-consuming. It necessitates both types of resources, qualitative and quantitative (Camero. Require skills in both methods qualitative and quantitative (Cooper & Schindler, 2014) Necessitate two different sampling strategies and samples (Wedawatta <i>et al.</i> , 2011)
Type of data	It uses mainly words and phrases and presents participant's viewpoints (Silverman, 2016)	It uses numerical data and represents the view of the researcher (Cooper & Schindler, 2014)	Employs both qualitative and quantitative data (Zakari, 2020)

Approach	It observes and interprets the data (Zikmund <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	It measures and then tests (Zikmund <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	Generate data and test (Zikmund <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
Purpose	It is adopted in exploratory studies to discover ideas. It generates theory from natural settings (Gummerson, 2001)	It is adopted in causal or descriptive research designs (Bell <i>et al.</i> , 2019) Hypothesis testing in an artificial setting (Johnson & Clark, 2014)	Combine both research approaches, inductive and deductive, which allow for both building and testing theory in the same study (Wedawatta & Ingirige, 2016)

Source: Researcher's construct

4.4.1 Rationale for the chosen research method

As discussed in Chapters 2 and 3, little is known about enterprise risk management adoption and implementation within the insurance industry in developing countries, particularly Algeria. This study aims to establish an in-depth understanding of the ERM adoption challenges, practices, and benefits of the insurance industry in Algeria to propose an industry-specific framework that will assist Algerian insurers in effectively implementing an ERM program.

Access to limited previously published empirical evidence on the adoption challenges associated with the introduction of ERM and the factors that can affect this adoption

requires deep understanding through an in-depth discussion with most informed individuals and directly or indirectly involved individuals in ERM introduction and adoption. At this early stage, developing a hypothesis that can be tested statistically seems unrealistic (Fleck & Lloyd-Reason, 2009).

The qualitative method of inquiry has been widely criticised for needing to be more representative, and outcomes cannot be generalised (Zikmund et al., 2013; Silverman, 2016; Bell et al., 2019). However, it is argued that the richness and quality of data overcome the deficiency of limited generalisability and representativeness (Silverman, 2016; Hanell et al., 2019).

Therefore, using the quantitative method of inquiry would only be hypothetical and have no credibility at this stage to investigate ERM adoption. The quantitative method must be adopted, with a previous reference to the challenges and factors associated with ERM adoption among firms in Algeria, that can be tested numerically and statistically.

Furthermore, the mixed method of inquiry could have been appropriate if only the outcomes of the research were to investigate and generalise. However, as stated in Chapter One, this research aims to develop an industry-specific framework that can be achieved through the qualitative method. Therefore, the mixed method was not considered appropriate for this research.

This section discussed the different research methods and justified selecting the qualitative method of inquiry. The following section will discuss the research design.

4.5 Research Design

This section illustrates the different aspects of the three research designs, namely, exploratory, descriptive, and causal, followed by the justification for the research design selected for this research.

Figure 4. 6 Presentation of exploratory, descriptive, and causal research designs

	Exploratory	Descriptive	Causal
Key research statement	Research questions	Research questions	Hypothesis
Research approach	Highly Unstructured	structured	Highly structured
Results	Research adopting this design is discovery-oriented. However, they are speculative. Further research on the topic needs to justify the study's findings.	Results can be confirmatory, yet further investigation may be needed sometimes. Findings can be managerially actionable.	Fairly conclusive as results tend to be more confirmatory-oriented. Obtained findings are often managerially actionable.

Source: Adapted from Zikmund *et al.* (2013), Bell, Bryman and Harley (2019), Babin *et al.* (2019) and Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019).

4.5.1 Justifying the chosen research design

After evaluating the literature, it was established that the understanding of enterprise risk management (ERM) adoption challenges, practices and benefits in Algeria is understudied and lacks empirical research and evidence. Accordingly, the exploratory research design is most appropriate for several reasons. First, the experimental research design is right where the knowledge of the topic studied is poor, and through adopting this design, research can clarify situations and discover potential business opportunities (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Babin *et al.*,

2019). Here, factors influencing ERM adoption and challenges facing insurance companies in Algeria when introducing and adopting an ERM system are still being determined, with empirical data documenting its adoption. Secondly, whether the widely available and used ERM frameworks suggested in the literature are practical and fit the Algerian insurance firms is still being determined.

Finally, in reviewing prior studies on ERM adoption and implementation in different geographical contexts in the financial and insurance sectors, there has been increasing recognition and adoption of the exploratory qualitative design in investigating ERM adoption. For instance, Jabbour (2016) adopted a similar approach while investigating ERM adoption and implementation among UK insurers. Moreover, researchers like Alajemi (2019) adopted a similar approach while investigating ERM implementation challenges with an organisation operating in Kuwait's oil and gas industry.

This section demonstrated the research designs and provided the rationale for the exploratory research design that was selected for the study.

4.6 Research Strategy

Research strategy refers to the plan for carrying out research. It helps the researcher design, carry out, and monitor the study (Johannesson & Perjons, 2014).

Surveys, grounded theory, action research, experiments, and case study research are primary methodologies adopted in business and management studies (Creswell, 2013; Saunders et al., 2009; Yin, 2003). Saunders et al. (2019) note that selecting the most appropriate research strategy should be based on the research objectives, research questions, philosophical foundations, the degree of knowledge based on the researched topic and the availability of resources and time. With a different perspective, Yin (2003) recommends that an appropriate research strategy be chosen based on the type of research questions, the degree of influence a

researcher can have over specific behavioural occurrences, and the degree of attention on historical or current occurrences.

The following section will justify using the case study as the research strategy for the present study.

4.7 Case Study Research

Over the years, using case studies as a strategy for research has become popular in social science studies (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008; Trochim, 2000; Gustafsson, 2017). Case study research entails studying complex phenomena in nature based on an in-depth understanding of those phenomena (Noor, 2008; Vissak, 2010).

The case study methodology is suitable for studying risk management systems as it involves the role of control, which cannot be isolated when investigating such phenomena, and it allows in-depth examination of the empirical target over a period (Lukka, 2005; Otley & Berry, 1994). The in-depth understanding is achieved through extensive description and examination of an analysis of the phenomena taken in the context of a particular organisation (Yin, 2009).

The case study is deemed more appropriate when a researcher seeks to explore and comprehend complex subjects such as Enterprise risk management and related processes. Further, “it can be considered a robust research method, particularly when a holistic, in-depth investigation is required” (Zainal, 2007, p.1). It involves combining data collection methods (Yin, 2009). The employment of case study methodology helps in understanding the dynamics of a particular phenomenon within a specific context (Eisenhardt, 1989; Yin, 1994). Thus, it involves focusing on a single unit of analysis and gathering in-depth, contextualised data on that unit of analysis. Case study research allows a variety of research methods and is adopted when an in-depth understanding of a topic is required (Gerring, 2007; Yin, 1994). Moreover, a

case study can include qualitative and quantitative data, enabling the researcher to obtain diverse data (Gerring, 2007; Yin, 2003).

The case study is considered the most relevant method for the current study as the research questions formulated in chapter one strives to clarify and present circumstances and how and why the social phenomenon works. An in-depth description and extensive understanding of the social phenomenon are needed to answer the research questions formulated by the researcher for the context of the study. As the current study aims to understand ERM processes as well as actual practice and details of an organisation's activity, the case study approach is seen to be very useful, as it will enable the researcher to look beyond statistics in order to analyse the conditional behaviours as perceived by the agents (managers) themselves.

The present study agrees with Stenhouse (1985, p. 49) that interviews are the primary means when seeking to access "multiple realities" and follows Yin's (2003) approach, as stated earlier that the selection of the most appropriate research strategy is based on: 1) the type of the research questions, 2) the degree of influence a researcher can have over specific behavioural occurrences, 3) the degree of attention on historical or current occurrences. Accordingly, the case study strategy has been selected as a suitable strategy:

The questions of this research are in the form of "how" and "what" (i.e., what are the critical risk challenges facing ERM adoption? and how can a personalised ERM framework be adopted and implemented by an Algerian insurance firm?).

When conducting this study, the researcher remained outside the case (Cash Assurance) and did not have any control over the respondent's views and at any point tried to influence the behaviour of the participants in the study (interviewees).

The context of the current study is the adoption of ERM programmes in the insurance industry. As indicated by Yin (2003; 2006), adopting a case study strategy results in

discovering novel insights that cannot be obtained by adopting a technique like a survey. This is relevant for the current study as the extant literature on ERM adoption in developing countries is still emerging and scarce.

This research adopts a single case study. According to Yin (2003), a single case study is an ideal approach if the research aims to explore one object (one individual from a particular group) or a single group (a group of individuals). The current research focuses on one organisation that belongs to a specific sector, the insurance sector, and a specific geographic area (Algeria). Therefore, by adopting a qualitative research method and using qualitative semi-structured interviews for collecting data, and by focusing on a single case study, the researcher would have the ability to comprehend data in a natural setting and examine complexities in their actual context, which the quantitative method of enquiry lack of (Nock et al., 2007).

Like any other research strategy, case study research is not without criticism and shortcomings. The academic community has widely criticised specific characteristics of the case study. Lack of rigour, the challenge of generalisation, subjectivity, spending too long, and the generation of a significant amount of data are some aspects of the case study that have received criticism (Yin, 2003). However, scholars like Denscombe (2008), who raised concern about its primarily descriptive nature, suggest that the importance of case study as a strategy should not be overlooked because of this criticism, having stated its benefits and shortcomings in this section.

Case studies permit the examination of control roles that cannot be isolated in other research methods. Risk management relies on oversight, control mechanisms, governance structures, etc. Case studies allow researchers to study these control factors in their real-world context rather than trying to extract and isolate them.

4.7.1 The case company

The insurance firm selected in CASH Assurance Algérie is located in Algeria, North Africa, with international operations and standing among the top five insurers in Algeria.

Cash Insurance Organisation The Hydrocarbon Insurance Company, or Cash Spa, is the youngest public capital damage insurance company. Founded in 1999, it is a leader in advanced risk insurance and the third largest player in the coverage of damage risks other than automobiles. CASH Assurance intervenes in three areas of activity: the high-tech risks of construction, operation, and transport, for which it has strong and recognised expertise; the risks of SMEs/PMIs that it continues to increase; and finally, those of individuals. It effectively and sustainably supports its clients, providing the necessary advice to ensure the optimal protection of their property and people and then providing them with the best benefit in a disaster. The CASH Hydrocarbon Insurance Company is the youngest public-owned property and casualty insurance company, created by Order 95-07, which liberalised the sector in Algeria. Created in 1999, it started its activities in 2000 to operate in all branches. The CASH is a subsidiary of the SONATRACH group (Naftal and SONATRACH), the main shareholder holding 82% of its share capital under the Ministry of Energy, the remaining 18 held by two companies under the Ministry of Finance: Compagnie Centrale "CCR" and the Algerian Insurance and Reinsurance Company "CAAR". When it was created, the CASH's vocation was to specialise in managing risk insurance related to hydrocarbon activities. However, it quickly evolved to gain the status of a full-fledged company like other insurance companies. The CASH is now one of the national leaders in the coverage of significant risks, which is why it enjoys an excellent reputation with reinsurance companies and uses, in addition to the capacities of the national reinsurer (CCR Alger), to the best reinsurers worldwide. CASH has been involved in a dynamic diversification of its business portfolio for more than a decade. In addition to its dominant segment, it has enriched its offers to businesses, including SMEs (all sectors), one of

its main strategic development areas. At the end of 2017, the company posted growth of 9%, well above the market rate.

The following section outlines the data collection process of the research.

4.8 Data collection

Data collection refers to the gathered data to meet the research objectives (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Data can be either primary data collected by the researcher or secondary data collected by other researchers (Babin *et al.*, 2019). This research collected empirical data through semi-structured interviews to understand ERM adoption challenges and its practice among insurance firms.

4.8.1 Interview Phase

Interview structure guide

The gap informed and guided by the literature in section 2.10 helped the researcher formulate the interview guideline, which comprises a list of the most important topics the current research study aimed to cover in the interview process (Newcomer *et al.*, 2015).

- The interview questions concentrated mainly on four key areas:
- Participants' perception and awareness of ERM adoption.
- Organisational factors that can influence ERM adoption.
- ERM adoption challenges
- The effectiveness of the available international ERM frameworks

The researcher has selected different business levels to ensure the data quality for performing a good analysis and achieving validity of outcomes. From each business department, interviewees were selected about their unique position within their departments and experience (executive level) (Yin, 2009.pp91) within their respective organisations and their ability to provide perspectives on the challenges associated with introducing and adopting

ERM in their respective operations. The reason behind this choice is because of the unique position they occupy. According to Yin (2009), the business function acts as a centre where the senior executive, supported by mid-level management and executive managers, implements decisions such as ERM. The decision to include top-level management, mid-level and executive level employees and above was mainly based on whether the level of experience, understanding, attitude and perceptions of mid-level management and managers differs from those of their seniors concerning the factors affecting ERM introduction and adoption.

4.8.2 Pilot Interview

A pilot study is essential when conducting research (Kim, 2010; Majid et al., 2017). The prominence of performing a pilot study is explained by its usefulness in helping the researcher perceive potential weaknesses in the research mechanisms before interviewing all respondents targeted for the study (Uma et al., 2019). The current study is based on qualitative methods, which include in-depth interviews; the researcher will pre-test the interview questions on a small group of participants (two respondents) as part of the pilot interview.

Van Wijk and Harrison (2013) claimed that pilot studies will help the researcher by demonstrating how well the instrument in question is coherent with the purpose of the study and highlighting potential areas for adjustment. Therefore, trying the interview protocol in this research study helped verify the interview protocol design, identify uncertainty and unnecessary questions, and manage time. Further, the sampling technique the researcher selects involves classifying subjects regarding specific principles based on the research issues (Kim, 2010; Majid et al., 2017).

The two participants of the pilot study involved one top-level manager and one mid-level manager who are involved in risk management activities and decision-making processes. The pilot interviews conducted face-to-face in the participant's respective organisation aimed

to check the communication skills of the researcher as well as the viability of the interview structure. Following the pilot interviews, participants were asked for their opinions and criticisms about the interview process and the researcher's communication style and questions.

One significant correction was made following the two pilot interviews as per the participants regarding the interview questionnaire and interview process. The two participants considered that there were technical terms, for instance, the use of "silo", that required the researcher to simplify them or provide clarifications when asking the question not to mislead the research study. Therefore, following the participants' recommendations, technical and academic terms were highlighted and replaced with simple terms so that all future participants would be comfortable responding to the questions.

4.8.3 Data collection techniques

Data collection is essential to every research, as inaccurate data collection would affect the study's outcomes and lead to invalid results. Qualitative research is interpretive and descriptive as such, i. Asenera,l data come in sentences, speech, stories, and words instead of numbers (Liamputtong, 2013). Generally, the data sources for qualitative studies are focused groups, interviews, records, observations, etc. (Clandinin, 1986).

Numerous data collection techniques are employed when doing case study research to achieve rich information surrounding the central research phenomenon and capture the contextual complexity (Yin, 2014). Multiple data types can be used in case study research, including direct observation, archival records, documentation, and participant observation. Each source of data individually relates to evidence or a group of data. In the qualitative method, three types of interviews exist: structured, unstructured, and semi-structured (Whiting, 2008). As little is known about ERM adoption and practice in Algeria, this research study analyses the insights using in-depth semi-structured interviews. According to Schindler (2014),

semi-structured interviews are essential to understanding what is happening and gaining insight into an understudied topic.

Structured interviews are usually used for qualitative research and involve straightforward pre-decided questions with almost no flexibility and no incentive for probing questions (Saunders et al., 2019). This type of interview entails the interviewer setting pre-planned questions that should be written clearly and concisely. Generally, the questions involved are closed and require clear-cut answers. Structured interviews are easy to carry out and can be analysed statistically as all study participants answer identical questions.

In the discussion of Gill et al. (2008), structured interviews are primarily appropriate for modern research as they enable defining and meeting the objectives. Therefore, it provides no room for follow-up questions requiring further explanation.

For the current study, this type of interview will not be considered as using predetermined questions is not congruent with the aim of the study research where in-depth understanding is required (Robson, 2002).

Unstructured interviews are conducted with little or no organisation and do not reflect pre-determined beliefs (Brinkmann, 2014). This type of interview is usually used when addressing a broad topic of interest (Robson, 2004). A significant limitation of this category is the amount of time it requires to conduct it, as it might take a long time, making it challenging to adopt in research. This type is unsuitable for the present study as the absence of pre-set questions makes it difficult for the researcher to manage it and inconvenient for respondents (Gill et al., 2008).

Semi-structured interviews: This type of interview consists of the characteristics of both structured and unstructured interviews (Bryman, 2012). Consequently, this form of interview benefits both natures of the interview. In a semi-structured interview, the interviewer prepares

a list of questions or specific topics to ensure consistency and for guidance purposes to enable him or her to cover the same topics with the remaining participants.

This method is appropriate for the current study because it allows the researcher or the respondent to deviate and delve deeper into a response (Brinkmann, 2014). Unlike other types of interviews, semi-structured interviews allow the interviewer to probe arguments and clarify some points misunderstood by participants (Dorneyei, 2007), which results in obtaining more accurate data, which adds validity to the data collected (Alshenqeeti, 2014). Consequently, the current study adopts the interview method, precisely the semi-structured in-depth interview method, as the means to collect data for the case study as it provides a distinctive chance for exploring the main factors obstructing ERM introduction and adoption from manager's experience, opinions and understanding of the social world (Miller & Glassner, 1997; Mack et al., 2005).

Furthermore, adopting a semi-structured interview allows the interviewer to glean how participants view the social world and that the interview will be flexible.

For this research study, semi-structured interviews were conducted using an audio recorder with the written consent of participants to record the discussion held, which was transcribed and validated by the interviewees. Notes were taken during interviews, and detailed notes were written following each interview.

Every interview lasted between 55 minutes and a 1hr and 30 minutes, depending mainly on the participant's knowledge of ERM. The researcher has sought the permission of the interviewees to record the interview in every instance and to guarantee anonymity to interviewees.

Figure 4. 7 Interview duration in minutes with each of the participant

Respondents Number	Interview Duration in minutes
1	59
2	65
3	82
4	60
5	53
6	84
7	90
8	68
9	73
10	52
11	66
12	55
13	59
14	72
15	98
16	56
17	58
18	63
19	83
20	92
21	74
22	77

23	61
24	78
25	93

Source: Author

4.9 Sampling

Sampling in qualitative research is considered a complex issue. This is because the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings are determined by the researcher's accuracy of the sampling strategy (Marshall & Rossman, 2016). Sampling methods usually fall into two main categories: probabilistic and non-probabilistic (Schutt, 2011; Liamputtong, 2013). In qualitative research, sampling is not a rigidly imposed task, unlike in the compulsory quantitative approach (Coyne, 1997; Curtis, 2000).

Sampling is" choosing subjects to participate in a research study. To achieve the objective of the research aim and objectives, it is essential to consider the most suitable method. However, the selection of samples will usually depend upon the nature of the study" (Babbie & Mounton, 2001). The current study intends to explore the challenges of adopting ERM within an Algerian insurance company. Therefore, in order to conclude the best outcomes from the research study, the researcher will be adopting purposive or non-probability sampling, which is defined as an intentional selection of particular participants, groups, settings or events due to the critical information and details they can provide on the research, which cannot be achieved through other means (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018; Saunders et al., 2019).

This research on Enterprise Risk Management has mainly focused on gaining insights into the adoption challenges of enterprise risk management at Cash Assurance; purposive sampling requires the researcher to select logically and systematically participants with relevant experience and knowledge in risk management rather than randomly choosing

participants that cannot help achieve the aim of the study (Padgett, 2008). The sampling strategy used, based on the researcher's judgment of participants in the study, would enable the researcher to elicit information, allowing the study to achieve its aim (Saunders, 2012). The participants in this study are primarily heads of their respective divisions or key individuals who are mainly involved in the decision-making process.

Thus, the sampling strategy adopted in the current study is consistent with the study's philosophical reasoning. This study focuses on a single case that necessitates an in-depth understanding of a handful of participants (Saunders et al., 2012) from the case study and the risk landscape within the organisation to provide the investigator with rich information.

Thus, according to Patton (2002, P. 230), the strengths of purposive sampling "lie in selecting information-rich cases for study in-depth". Patton (2002) refers to information-rich cases of people, groups, settings or events from which the researcher can deeply understand the investigated phenomena. In general, purposive sampling embraces a small number of contributors and researchers who, by this means, seek to build meaning and insight rather than rate of recurrence (Morse, 2007).

The population of interest for the current research study are the individuals who work at the insurance firm studied and are directly or indirectly involved in the adoption process of the ERM program.

4.9.1 Selection criteria for the study participants

- Respondents must occupy a top-level or mid-level management position.
- Respondents must be directly or indirectly involved in the adoption process of the ERM program.
- Respondents must have been directly or indirectly in the decision-making process about ERM adoption and implementation.

4.10 Data Analysis

The present research used the thematic analysis method to analyse the primary data collected, allowing flexibility to interpret and present rich and complex data (Braun & Clarke, 2006; O'Connor & Joffe, 2020). Thematic analysis refers to the process of identifying themes or patterns within a set of qualitative data (Braun and Clarke; Denzin & Lincoln, 2018)

The qualitative data from the semi-structured interviews are thematically analysed and will be presented in chapter five. The research followed the six steps of data processing as recommended by Braun and Clarke (2006).

4.10.1 Familiarising with the data

The recorded interviews were immediately transcribed on the same date as the interview. For every interview, the researcher listened to and read the interviewee's responses to the probe questions many times to familiarise more with the data collected. In order to familiarise more with the meaning of the interviews, the researcher read the transcripts multiple times.

4.10.2 Generation of the initial codes

The next step was to generate the codes. For this, the researcher attentively reviewed the interview transcripts line by line, then started to manually assign an initial code to every chunk of data in the transcript. Some codes were words, and others were as elaborate as a whole phrase. The following are some of the initial codes generated from the first interview:

- Top management not committing to the process
- Resistance to change
- Employee rewards can improve their interest towards ERM

4.10.3 Identifying themes and ideas

The researcher classified the initial codes in this phase to discover themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The researcher has reviewed the transcripts several times; some codes that were generated have been renamed and restructured, and similar codes were grouped, and then themes started to emerge.

4.10.4 Review of the themes

In this step, the researcher started to refine the themes and then organised them into the main themes for the study.

4.10.5 Defining and naming themes

At this stage, the researcher has decided on the main themes according to their main idea, which part of the data, and which research objective the generated theme corresponds to (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Four main themes were created for the data presentation

4.10.6 Presenting the findings

Finally, the four major themes created with their relevant sub-themes will be discussed in chapter five; every theme will be supported by a quote or an extract from the interview transcript to support them (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

The following section will discuss how qualitative research would ensure trustworthiness and authenticity.

4.11 Research Quality

In the following section, the researcher will address the quality criteria of a qualitative method of inquiry to reach considerably credible outcomes (Lincoln & Guba, 2000). In contrast to evaluating credibility in quantitative research, which is founded upon the positivistic paradigm, the principle of quality in qualitative research could be more straightforward due to

the multiple ontological viewpoints (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Lincoln & Guba, 2000). Qualitative research is considered multifaceted as its outcomes represent different meanings to different researchers.

In quantitative research, the ontological standpoint of positivism is that reality is objective and ascertained. At the same time, the ontological underpinnings of qualitative research present multiple realities and viewpoints, which results in incompatibility between the concept of validity and reliability and the ontological and epistemological underpinning of quantitative inquiry (Carpenter & Suto, 2008). Remember that the study cannot be replicated when conducting qualitative research methods to confirm reliability since it is revelatory and unique to a definite social, historical, and cultural viewpoint (Johnson & Waterfield, 2004).

Qualitative inquirers believe that reality is socially constructed. Therefore, reality cannot be measured but can be deducted or interpreted. Therefore, qualitative data cannot be evaluated for validity following similar criteria and rules established on the beliefs of objective reality (Johnson & Waterfield, 2004). Thus, in qualitative research, inquirers with similar ontological interpretations work on what is usually considered quality criteria within their area of research (Guba & Lincoln, 1994).

Unlike quantitative research, qualitative research has often been criticised for its generalisability and transferability issues (Babin et al., 2019). Nevertheless, Guba and Guba (1994) recommended four criteria to ensure trustworthiness and authenticity when adopting a qualitative method.

4.11.1 Credibility

Credibility when doing qualitative research reflects the confidence that could be placed in the research outcomes and to which extent findings reflect the truth (Johnson, 2020)

The credibility criteria have been suggested by Lincoln and Guba (1985) as equivalent to the internal validity criteria in quantitative research. Credibility is concerned with the authenticity of the outcomes of the qualitative study (Bryman, 2012). It analyses the issue of "fit" among the data obtained from the participants and the investigator's representation of these points of view (Padgett, 2008). Lincoln and Guba (1985) recommended several strategies to ensure credibility, including triangulation, member validation, peer debriefing, and previous research references. The researcher reduces the credibility challenge by triangulating the findings using member verification to validate the interpretations and outcomes of the interview (Birt et al., 2016; Yin, 2003). Participants were provided with the interview transcript to validate their accounts.

4.11.2 Transferability

Transferability criteria refer to the degree to which the study can be replicated (Nowell et al., 2017). It deals with the issue of to what degree the research could be generalised to other contexts or settings with other participants (Bryman, 2012). Transferability relates to the degree to which qualitative study outcomes could inform understanding within different contexts to the context in which the study is carried out (Padgett, 2008).

Therefore, the current study cannot be replicated like for like. Nevertheless, to ensure the transferability criteria, the researcher explains the nature of the research, objectives, methodology adopted, research context and sampling strategy followed, and the research outcomes. So, if related purpose research will be conducted in the future in other contexts based on the information provided in this study, transferability could be achieved (Hays et al., 2021)

4.11.3 Dependability

Dependability deals with the consistency of the findings (Carpenter & Suto, 2008). It is concerned with the conformity of the outcomes (Bryman, 2012) and ensures that the analysis

process is in line with the design chosen for the study. Dependability represents reliability criteria within the quantitative research. It entails the respondent's evaluation and validation of the interpretations made by the researcher and ensures that outcomes are correct (Cohen *et al.*, 2011; Tobin & Begley, 2004). In the present study, semi-structured interviews will focus on the participant's experience with the implementation of ERM and ensure to report findings using their own terms and given examples during the interviews. Eventually, they seek their validation to confirm that the researcher's interpretations are correct.

4.11.4 Confirmability

When conducting social research, achieving objectivity seems unattainable (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Confirmability in qualitative research is concerned with the neutrality of the research; in other words, it is used to ascertain that the interpretation of data has not been based on the inquirer's particular preferences but rather is grounded in the data (Moser & Korstjen 2017).

To avoid misrepresentation of data and ensure the confirmability and transparency of the research process, the researcher will adopt the audit trail strategy as suggested by Lincoln and Guba (1985), where the researcher will seek the audit of a professional supervisor who will review the research process, analysis, and codes to confirm that they followed from the data, then suggest any rooms for improvement.

4.12 Ethical Consideration

This research study fully adheres to the University's ethical regulations and guidelines. Before starting the research, the researcher has gained the approval and permission of the UWS ethics committee (Appendix 3).

4.12.1 Participant's selection and written consent

Initially, the participants will be contacted via email or over the phone. A brief on the research will be given, and then an appointment will be requested to provide a detailed information sheet about the study. Then, the confidentiality and rights of participants in the study will be raised. Written consent and willingness to participate in the study will be sought from the participants, who will be informed about their right to withdraw from the research prior to any data publication.

4.13 Identity Protection

The anonymity of the participants will be respected in the disclosure of their identity in the research. The researcher will use codes to refer to the individuals who are interviewed.

4.13.1 Data Storage

To ensure the proper security of the data and information of participants, the researcher needs to store the data properly. Each participant's personal identity, information and data have been stored in password-protected software.

4.13.2 Data Protection Act 1998

The study will follow the principles of the Data Protection Act 1998, which should be followed if a researcher holds personal data about individuals. The 1998 Data Protection Act preserves participants' research rights and applies obligations to the researcher who records interviews or uses personal information.

4.13.3 Informed Consent

Preceding any data collection or information, inquirers must get informed consent from all participants in their study. Informed consent indicates consciousness and the willingness of participants in an apparent and evident way to confer their consent and be part of the study.

Fouka and Mantzourou (2011) opined that informed consent is the primary ethical concern in performing qualitative research. Informed consent must entail an outline of the research, the motives of the study, the objectives behind the choice of the subject, and the different processes involved. It is vital to highlight any discomfort or physical harm to participants and threats to privacy and dignity, and it is worth pointing out how the affected subject will be paid.

Thus, data collection techniques in qualitative research, such as interviews or observation, tend to have unclear direction, and a single consent could not be appropriate for the research (McDonnell *et al.*, 2006; Holloway & Wheeler, 2002).

4.13.4 Interview Phase

The interviews started with a detailed illustration of the main aim of the research as well as the objectives (Yin, 2009). Respondents were invited to talk about their risk management experience. These main motivating factors led their organisation to introduce and adopt an ERM and identify the critical challenges associated with it. The preference for keeping the interviews semi-structured was to permit the participants to talk about their experiences without interruption, hoping that numerous research questions would be covered without having to probe questions from the researcher.

4.14 Chapter Summary

The present chapter discussed the research design and methodology followed in this research to investigate the challenges facing ERM adoption and the factors that can influence this adoption within the Algerian insurance industry. Due to the subjective nature of the topic investigated, the interpretive paradigm was considered the most appropriate research philosophy to underpin the research. Furthermore, the present study used inductive reasoning since it allows the researcher to make various interpretations in different circumstances.

The case study strategy was chosen, and the researcher selected a single case study design, as this is considered the most suitable approach when the study is exploring a single group of individuals. Considering the adopted paradigm, the researcher selected a qualitative method of inquiry and used in-depth semi-structured interviews to collect empirical data. The data analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-stage thematic analysis approach to analyse the data retrieved from the semi-structured interviews. The chapter ended with discussing the research's quality and how the research intends to establish trustworthiness and ethical consideration. The following chapter presents the findings of the data analysis.

5 Chapter five Findings

5.1 Introduction

The data collection involved 25 interviews with top-level managers due to their level of involvement in adopting ERM at Cash Assurance Algeria. This chapter records the opinions, perceptions, and views of the interviewees. The chapter begins with investigating the state of Enterprise risk management adoption (ERM), according to the opinions and views of the interviewees. This helps to provide an overview of the risk management practices at the insurance studied. This is followed by a discussion of the factors driving ERM adoption to complement the Western literature reviewed in chapter two.

As stated in Chapter One Section 1.5, this study aims to explore the challenges associated with introducing and adopting ERM within an Algerian insurance company (Cash Assurance, Algeria). Chapter Four identified and justified the methodology adopted for collecting data and analysis. The current chapter presents the findings from the 25 qualitative semi-structured interviews conducted with top-level and mid-level management in Cash Assurance, Algeria.

Findings in this chapter are influenced by the direction and the scope as demonstrated in the methodology chapter (chapter 4), which have played a vital role in constructing theoretical knowledge that is deemed to overcome the challenges associated with introducing and adopting ERM at Cash Assurance, Algeria. Five themes were developed by the researcher from the data obtained. These themes were formed to better perceive, explore, and explain the research phenomenon. Themes were created and then integrated with the findings. Further, themes have been presented about the obtained responses from participants.

The present chapter serves the aim of the study and analyses the challenges associated with introducing and adopting ERM in Cash Assurance, Algeria. The analysis of findings has

revealed different views regarding the difficulties related to the introduction and adoption of ERM; hence, it is vital to analyse these findings on existing studies and the literature review on ERM to achieve valid and reliable conclusions at the end of the research.

5.2 Background of respondents

Table 5.1: Respondent's Information

Respondents Number	Respondents background	Years of experience	Qualification
1	Mathematics	17	PhD
2	finance and economics	21	Master degree
3	actuary	12	Engineer
4	accounting and finance	15	Master degree
5	auditing	10	Master degree
6	accounting and finance	25	Certificate
7	mathematics and computer science	19	PhD
8	Finance	14	Master degree
9	actuary	12	Bachelor degree
10	Financial Engineering	16	Master degree
11	Mathematics	13	Bachelor degree
12	Statistics	10	Engineer
13	actuary	14	Engineer
14	accounting and finance	21	Master degree
15	Risk management	15	Master degree

16	Insurance studies	11	Bachelor degree
17	actuary and mathematics	9	Engineer
18	Audit	7	Bachelor degree
19	accounting and finance	13	Master degree
20	economics	17	Master degree
21	business and finance	12	PhD
22	mathematics	18	Bachelor degree
23	finance	22	Master degree
24	audit and finance	25	Bachelor degree
25	actuary	28	Bachelor degree

Source: The researcher

5.3 Theme 1: Current Risk Management Practices at CASH Assurance

This part delves deeply into the nuanced landscape of risk management practices at CASH Assurance, offering insights garnered directly from respondents intimately involved in the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). The purposive sampling technique facilitated the selection of participants deeply engaged in ERM processes, enriching the research with invaluable perspectives. The prevailing sentiment among most respondents underscores a gradual progression in ERM adoption yet reveals that full integration across organisational domains remains a distant goal. Thirteen top-level managers interviewed unanimously acknowledged the formal initiation of ERM within their respective organisations, albeit still in developmental stages.

Respondent 13 candidly shared, "... *We have officially initiated an ERM within the organisation since 2016. However, it is not yet fully developed or integrated yet.*" This

admission reflects a common thread among respondents, indicating a trajectory towards ERM maturity yet underscoring the need for further consolidation and embedding within organisational frameworks. Similarly, respondent 17 recollected, "*Well, I remember when first ERM landed on our CEO's top priority list around the first quarter of 2016 if I remember exactly (laughed).... on one of the meetings, where the CEO officially informed us that an official ERM initiative will start taking place*" This acknowledgement of ongoing analysis and introspection highlights the dynamic nature of ERM implementation, wherein organisations continuously reassess and refine their strategies to align with evolving risk landscapes.

Furthermore, respondent 21's observation, "*Risk is not incorporated in our strategic plans yet, so I cannot tell that we have achieved an effective ERM adoption yet*", underscores the pivotal role of strategic alignment in fostering robust risk management practices. This sentiment highlights the symbiotic relationship between strategic foresight and effective risk governance, emphasising the need for holistic integration of ERM within organisational vision and mission statements. Echoing these sentiments, respondent 24 elucidated, "*...We still have a long way to achieve fully developed and mature ERM that is well incorporated in all business areas or at least on the key ones, but you know we are working rigorously on it; Humm... Well, I remember when we started in 2016, we asked a few team members to start mapping all our risks in one database; we requested others to go around the organisation and conduct some focus groups and interviews with colleagues at different levels of the organisation,..... mmm yeah we are getting there, and that is pretty much how we initiated it*". This acknowledgement of the ongoing journey towards ERM maturity underscores the iterative nature of risk management processes, wherein organisations navigate a continuum of development and refinement.

Inquiring into the utilisation of existing ERM frameworks, respondents revealed an awareness of various frameworks worldwide, with the COSO ERM 2004 framework emerging

as a prominent reference point. However, respondents expressed reservations regarding its complexity and applicability to their organisational context. Respondent 3 articulated, "*... We investigated the COSO 2004 framework when we decided on adopting ERM, but it is quite complicated, and its blocks are quite ambiguous*" This critique underscores the need for clarity and specificity in framework design, highlighting the importance of frameworks tailored to organisational imperatives and contextual nuances.

Similarly, respondent 6 opined, "*The COSO one, yes, it is the one the chief audit officer was discussing with us in one of the meetings, but to be fairly honest, it is very theoretical; I think we need to simplify it or probably design our framework that responds to our business needs*" This call for customisation underscores the imperative of flexibility in framework design, emphasising the importance of aligning risk management strategies with organisational objectives and operational realities. Supporting this sentiment, respondent 17 emphasised, "*I am aware of the ERM frameworks like COSO and ISO. There is also COBIT, but I think their direct applicability to any organisation is impossible; those frameworks are highly structured, and we need some flexibility in structure and so*" This plea for adaptability underscores the inherent complexity of risk management frameworks, highlighting the need for iterative design processes that accommodate organisational idiosyncrasies and evolving risk landscapes.

The insights garnered from the respondents provide a comprehensive and multifaceted understanding of the prevailing risk management landscape at CASH Assurance. These insights offer valuable guidance on Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption within organisations. They emphasise the incremental nature of progress, with organisations moving gradually towards maturity. While ERM initiation is explicit, ongoing developmental stages highlight the need for sustained integration and refinement efforts. This dynamic nature of risk management processes underscores the iterative approach necessary to align with evolving organisational needs and external risk factors. Discussions on framework selection and

implementation show a nuanced understanding of the challenges inherent in ERM adoption. Existing frameworks like the COSO ERM 2004 are recognised, indicating a proactive approach to leveraging established methodologies. However, concerns about complexity and applicability underscore the need for customised and flexible framework designs. This balance between theoretical rigour and practical utility prompts organisations to tailor frameworks to their unique contexts and operational realities. These insights lay a foundation for further exploration, guiding efforts to enhance risk governance and fortify organisational resilience. By illuminating the complexities of ERM implementation and framework choice, organisations can more effectively navigate the intricacies of risk management and take advantage of opportunities for enhancement. This encourages a culture of ongoing learning and adaptation, empowering organisations to pre-emptively tackle emerging risks and exploit strategic openings in a constantly evolving environment.

Here is a summarised table capturing the key points from Theme 1:

5.2: Key Points from Theme 1

Key Points	Interpretation
- ERM adoption at CASH Assurance is in the early stages	- Despite formal initiation, full integration across organisational areas is pending
- Strategic alignment with ERM is evolving	- Risk not yet fully incorporated into strategic plans, indicating ongoing alignment efforts
- Awareness of existing ERM frameworks, with reservations	- COSO ERM 2004 framework commonly known but perceived as complex and impractical for organisational context
- Calls for customisation of frameworks	- Desire for frameworks tailored to organisational needs and realities, emphasising flexibility and practicality

Source: The researcher

This table succinctly summarises the findings and interpretations from Theme 1, offering a clear snapshot of the current state of ERM adoption and the challenges faced by CASH Assurance.

5.4 Theme 2: Factors driving the adoption of an ERM

This theme provides a comprehensive exploration of the myriad factors propelling the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) within the context of CASH Assurance. Drawing on insights from respondents, the research endeavours to validate or challenge prevailing literature on the drivers influencing ERM adoption.

5.4.1 Competition as a Catalyst for ERM Adoption

A prevalent narrative among respondents underscores the role of competition as a pivotal driver of ERM adoption within the insurance sector. Several respondents cited instances where successful ERM implementation by competitors catalysed similar initiatives within their organisations. For example, Respondent 5 shared, *"We have been kindly discussing ERM adoption with one of our industry Players who recently also got into the rating system of A.M Best"* This sentiment was echoed by Respondent 11, who noted, *"We have been influenced to some extent by one of our competitors who have been recently noted (rated) by one international rating organisation for its financial strength"* These insights illuminate the competitive imperative compelling organisations to fortify their risk management practices to maintain a competitive edge in the industry.

Moreover, the competitive landscape has spurred a knowledge-sharing culture among industry peers, with respondents acknowledging the exchange of insights and best practices as instrumental in informing their ERM strategies. Respondent 5 elaborated, *"Feedback included how they have initiated their ERM and how one of the big four audit firms has assisted them, and overall the resources they allocated"* Similarly, Respondent 11 remarked, *"We have been*

influenced to some extent by one of our competitors who have been recently noted (rated) by one international rating organisation for its financial strength".

These quotes underscore the collaborative dynamics at play within the industry, where organisations draw inspiration and lessons from each other's successes and innovations in ERM adoption.

5.4.2 Impact of Education, Experience, and Qualifications

The research findings underscore the profound influence of education, professional experience, and qualifications on the decision to adopt ERM within organisations. Respondents highlighted the pivotal role of leadership, particularly CEOs with extensive educational backgrounds and qualifications in accounting and auditing, in championing ERM initiatives. Respondent 2 elucidated, *"The CEO's level of education and her different qualifications acquired from different international well-reputed organisations in the accounting and auditing field reflects on her devotion towards enhancing our firm risk management practices"* Moreover, professional experience emerged as a significant factor shaping attitudes towards ERM adoption. Respondent 9, drawing on his extensive experience as a risk manager in the banking and insurance sectors, endorsed ERM adoption based on its proven benefits. He explained, *"I am a freelance lecturer in risk management; I am documented and aware of ERM implementation's benefits to companies worldwide. Also, I have 15 years of experience as a risk manager in the banking sector, where we have had good experience and results from ERM adoption previously. Seven years as a risk manager here (insurance firm) have made me endorse ERM adoption, to be honest,"* Similarly, Respondent 16 emphasised the impact of professional qualifications and certifications in risk management on ERM initiation and implementation. He stated, *"It is my professional qualifications in audit and certifications in risk management in different professional bodies that made support and contribute to initiate*

this adoption as well as allowed me with the help of employees who work under me in my department (audit) to build a risk database and design and build the ERM framework"

Additionally, respondents emphasised the influence of educational backgrounds, with advanced degrees such as MBAs and professional doctorates shaping individuals' perspectives and driving organisational decisions regarding ERM adoption.

The multifaceted nature of factors driving ERM adoption, encompassing competitive pressures, leadership influence, and the interplay of education, experience, and professional qualifications, underscores the complexity of organisational decision-making processes. These insights offer valuable perspectives on the intricate dynamics shaping ERM implementation within the insurance industry, paving the way for informed strategies to enhance risk management practices and organisational resilience.

5.4.3 Industry Requirements and Business Nature

The nature of the insurance business emerged as a significant driver of ERM adoption, shaped by the industry's inherent volatility and regulatory demands. Respondents emphasised the centrality of risk management to the core operations of insurance firms, driven by the imperative to assess risk impact at a granular level and navigate the dynamic market landscape. Respondent 1 elucidated, *"It is because of how our operating environment has developed. Because we take risks from other people and organisations who do not want to bear the loss, therefore by strengthening and enhancing our risk management, we are investing in sustaining our business in this fast-paced market"* Similarly, Respondent 14 underscored the evolving risk landscape, citing technological advancements and cyber risks as critical concerns. The high-risk exposure inherent in the insurance business was emphasised by Respondent 17, who remarked, *"Our risk exposure is high in our business compared to other companies in other sectors."*

Moreover, regulatory requirements imposed by authorities such as the Ministry of Finance underscored the imperative for robust risk management systems, as highlighted by Respondent 23.

Additionally, the unique value proposition of insurance firms bearing significant enterprise risks further accentuated the need for structured risk management approaches. Respondent 25 emphasised, *"Part of what we do is bear big enterprise risks. For example, we are the only insurance with the whole oil and gas industry risk portfolio, so you can imagine how critical it is. So what pushes us forward with a more structured approach to risk and update the risk management process is to have more visibility and understanding of their impact on the business"* These insights underscore the industry-specific dynamics driving ERM adoption, rooted in the imperative to navigate complex risk landscapes and ensure organisational sustainability.

5.4.4 Value Creation

A consensus among respondents highlighted the role of ERM in facilitating value creation and achieving organisational objectives. Respondents emphasised the importance of making informed risk-related decisions, enhancing returns on capital and risk, optimising risk rewards, and improving overall business performance. Respondent 10 articulated, *"We have the overall business strategy and specific goals to meet like increasing our profits; more specifically, we have to increase our return on equity and return on risk"* Respondent 9 aimed to optimise risk rewards, seeking better returns from risks. ERM facilitates strategic alignment and informed decision-making, according to Respondent 4. They stress the flow of risk information and its implications for strategy. Additionally, Respondent 18 highlights the integration of risk management with overall business strategy, emphasising their synergistic relationship. Moreover, ERM adoption enhances risk awareness and facilitates informed risk-

taking, as noted by Respondent 19 and echoed by Respondent 23. A risk framework guides risk appetite and decision-making processes. These insights highlight the strategic importance of ERM adoption, focusing on leveraging risk management as a value-enhancing tool to achieve organisational goals. Factors driving ERM adoption in the insurance industry include industry requirements, business nature, and value creation imperatives. These complexities underscore the intricate decision-making processes within organisations. These insights offer valuable perspectives on the strategic imperatives shaping ERM implementation, guiding organisations towards informed strategies to enhance risk management practices and drive sustainable value creation. The table below summarises the main factors revealed by respondents, providing a succinct overview of the drivers underpinning ERM adoption within the insurance firm studied.

Table 5.3: Summary of the findings of the factors driving the adoption of an ERM.

Factors Driving ERM Adoption	Key Points
Competition as a Catalyst	- Competitive pressures from industry peers drive organisations to adopt ERM. - Knowledge-sharing among competitors informs ERM strategies.
Education, Experience, and Qualifications	- Leadership with extensive educational backgrounds and qualifications champion ERM initiatives. - Professional experience in risk management influences ERM endorsement. - Professional qualifications and certifications in risk management support ERM initiation. - Educational backgrounds shape ERM perspectives and drive organisational decisions.
Industry Requirements and Business Nature	- Inherent volatility and regulatory demands within the insurance industry necessitate robust risk management systems. - High-risk exposure drives structured risk management approaches.

Value Creation	<p>- ERM facilitates value creation by enabling informed risk-related decisions. - Strategic alignment of ERM with organisational objectives enhances returns on capital and risk. - Integration of risk management with overall business strategy drives improved business performance.</p>
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Source: The researcher

5.5 Theme 3: Challenges facing ERM adoption

This theme discusses the challenges faced in adopting Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) as reported by respondents. The research offers insights into organisations' complexities and barriers when integrating ERM into their operations.

5.5.1 Lack of Appropriate Support from Top Management

Respondents often worry about the lack of backing from higher-ups, making it harder to implement ERM effectively. According to Beasley et al. (2010), senior management support is crucial in creating the right atmosphere for ERM adoption. Many respondents complained about the need for more dedication and involvement from top management, making it difficult for ERM initiatives to gain acceptance and integrate into the organisation. For instance, Respondent 11 emphasised, *“Senior management support is minimalistic regarding ERM adoption. In my opinion, top management support is a key factor in boosting the process and acceptance among employees, which is not the case at the moment”* This sentiment was echoed by Respondent 17, who noted the delegation of ERM responsibilities without active involvement or follow-up from top management. Similarly, Respondent 5 highlighted the absence of clear commitment from directors, citing it as a barrier to achieving maturity in ERM adoption. Respondents stressed the need for sustained involvement and leadership from top management to drive the successful integration of ERM across all business departments.

Contrastingly, Respondent 23 offered a divergent perspective, citing adequate support from top management in providing necessary resources and guidance for ERM adoption. This discrepancy underscores the variability in experiences and perceptions regarding senior management involvement in ERM initiatives.

5.5.2 Lack of Appropriate Technology

The inadequacy of technology emerged as a significant challenge impeding ERM adoption, with respondents citing limitations in existing technological infrastructure as a barrier to effective implementation. The participants noted that many still use outdated tools like spreadsheets, which are not ideal for the complex needs of ERM. One respondent stressed the importance of advanced technologies beyond spreadsheets to improve efficiency and accuracy. Another highlighted the value of investing in new tech to automate risk management and analyse data. The costs of updating infrastructure add to the challenge, requiring a strategic approach to resource allocation and investing in ERM tech solutions.

5.5.3 Lack of Clear Understanding of the Benefits of ERM Adoption

Respondents have pinpointed a significant obstacle to ERM adoption: employee comprehension of its advantages. This lack of awareness impedes ERM initiatives, as employees do not grasp its relevance to their duties and the organisation's performance. Comprehensive education and communication efforts are deemed necessary to clarify the benefits of ERM adoption in financial, operational, and strategic areas. Respondent 12 lamented, *“For us to have successful ERM adoption, we need to tackle the issue of technology and related problems; I know ERM require more advanced technologies beyond Excel to track risks and aggregate them.”*

Similarly, Respondent 2 emphasised the need to help employees understand and support effective ERM implementation. Overcoming this challenge involves actively

promoting a culture that values risk awareness and recognises the benefits of ERM initiatives. The obstacles mentioned in this theme highlight the challenges faced when implementing ERM in organisations—these range from inadequate support from senior management to technological constraints and a lack of employee support. Strategic interventions and organisational alignment are necessary to overcome these hurdles. By directly addressing these challenges and creating a favourable environment for ERM integration, organisations can fully leverage risk management practices to improve resilience and promote sustainable growth.

5.5.4 Lack of In-House Skills and Knowledge in ERM Adoption

Respondents emphasised the critical role of expertise in driving successful ERM adoption within their organisation. However, they identified a significant gap in in-house skills and knowledge necessary for effectively implementing ERM practices. Respondent 13 highlighted the absence of dedicated ERM specialists within the organisation, stating, *“We did not hire, specifically, an officer that we know has previous experience or contributed before that to design an ERM adoption strategy. Instead, we are using our employees from different functions to proceed with its adoption, which may be an obstacle”* This lack of specialised talent contributed to a prolonged timeline for ERM adoption, as the organisation relied on employees from various functions to navigate the complexities of ERM implementation. Similarly, respondent 19 expressed frustration over the scarcity of skilled personnel available in-house, noting, *“We have not reached full adoption yet from 2016; I think this is due to not having skilled people in ERM available in-house.”*

The organisation must gain expertise and focus on hiring or training people for ERM. This means getting specialists who can lead and advise on how to do ERM well. By investing in training and encouraging ongoing learning, organisations can overcome the problem of insufficient expertise and improve at ERM faster.

5.5.5 Lack of an Enterprise-Wide Risk Culture

The triumph of enterprise risk management (ERM) adoption is intricately linked to culture, as indicated by respondents. They emphasise the importance of nurturing a culture that is aware of risks throughout the organisation to incorporate risk management into its procedures seamlessly. Nonetheless, a prevalent challenge raised by respondents is the deficiency of awareness and engagement in risk management among employees, which impedes the efficient implementation of ERM principles. One respondent spotlighted the prevalence of information silos and inadequate communication as barriers to enhancing risk management maturity. Another highlighted the significance of management in tackling cultural barriers and fostering risk awareness among employees.

These discoveries underscore that organisational leaders need to concentrate on cultural transformation endeavours. These endeavours should strive to instil a mindset alert to risks and encourage collaboration among departments. Organisations can establish an environment conducive to ERM adoption and sustainable risk management practices by fostering transparency, accountability, and continuous enhancement.

5.5.6 Lack of a Clear Flow of Information Required for ERM

Respondents pinpointed the insufficient stream of information as a significant hurdle in ERM adoption, with data accessibility and transparency emerging as pivotal pain points. Despite the organisation's endeavours to gather and scrutinise data for risk mapping and assessment, respondents lamented the absence of a structured approach to information management, rendering it arduous to derive actionable insights from the accessible data. Respondent 19 expressed exasperation over the incomplete data, stating, *"I am not receiving all the information required for mapping the risks of the whole organisation, and it is making my job very challenging. It is very demanding to pursue employees for information."* Similarly,

respondent 14 stressed the necessity for enhanced communication channels to facilitate the efficient exchange of information among employees, highlighting the dependence on manual data collection and communication methods as a barrier to effective ERM adoption.

This challenge requires organisations to invest in digital platforms and information management systems that streamline data collection, analysis, and dissemination processes. By harnessing technology to centralise data repositories, automate data collection processes, and augment data accessibility, organisations can surmount the barriers posed by information flow issues and empower stakeholders to make well-informed risk management decisions. The challenges identified in this theme underscore the multifaceted obstacles encountered in ERM adoption within organisations. From skill shortages and cultural barriers to information flow issues, these challenges illuminate the intricacies of implementing ERM practices effectively. By proactively addressing these challenges and fostering a conducive environment for ERM integration, organisations can enhance risk management capabilities and propel sustainable growth.

Table 5. 3 Summary of the findings from the challenges facing ERM adoption

Table 5.4: Summary of the findings from the challenges facing ERM adoption

Challenge	Description
Lack of appropriate support from top management	Despite the importance of senior management support in driving ERM adoption, respondents noted minimalistic support from top management, hindering the organisation's ability to effectively promote ERM acceptance among employees.
Lack of appropriate technology	The absence of advanced technological infrastructure, such as dedicated ERM software, impedes the organisation's ability to implement ERM practices efficiently and accurately. The participants emphasised the constraints of current

	technology, such as dependence on spreadsheets, in addressing the intricate requirements of ERM.
Lack of clear understanding of ERM benefits	Employees' limited understanding of the benefits of ERM adoption hinders their engagement and commitment to the process. The participants observed a deficit in employee understanding regarding the benefits brought by ERM to their daily duties and overall organisational effectiveness, impeding adoption progress.
Lack of in-house skills and knowledge	The absence of specialised expertise in ERM within the organisation poses a significant barrier to successful adoption. The participants underscored the difficulties linked with the absence of specialised ERM experts and stressed the requirement for proficient staff to propel the adoption process efficiently.
Lack of an enterprise-wide risk culture	A pervasive lack of risk awareness and engagement among employees inhibits the organisation's ability to foster an enterprise-wide risk culture. The participants emphasised the significance of tackling cultural obstacles and fostering risk awareness to enable the incorporation of ERM principles into organisational processes.
Lack of a clear flow of information	Inadequate data accessibility and transparency hinder the organisation's ability to collect, analyse, and disseminate information necessary for ERM adoption. The participants pointed out the obstacles linked to manual data-gathering techniques. They stressed the necessity for enhanced communication avenues and information handling systems to tackle issues concerning information flow effectively.

Source: The researcher

5.6 Theme 4: Components of an effective ERM framework

This theme delves into the essential components of an effective ERM framework as perceived by top-level management. Participants, mainly heads of departments, provided insights into the organisational factors critical for successful ERM adoption and integration.

5.6.1 ERM and Key Organisational Areas

The individuals all stressed the significance of harmonising ERM with organisational strategies and objectives as a fundamental aspect of successful ERM implementation. This synchronisation guarantees that risk management endeavours are intricately linked to overarching business objectives, bolstering operational efficiency and performance. Respondent 3 underscored the critical nature of this alignment, stating, "*ERM must be aligned with the main strategies and objectives...to become more efficient performance and efficiency wise.*" This sentiment was echoed by respondent 7, who emphasised that without alignment with core strategies and objectives, ERM would lack direction and purpose. In agreement with these viewpoints, respondent 15 emphasised integrating ERM with strategic planning, noting that it allows the organisation to achieve its goals more effectively. These perspectives align with existing research, such as that by Mikes and Kaplan (2013), highlighting the importance of strategic integration for successful ERM implementation. The statements furnished by respondents underscore a shared perspective among senior executives concerning the importance of harmonising ERM with organisational strategies and objectives. This synchronisation is a guiding principle for risk management endeavours, guaranteeing their close correlation with broader business goals. By incorporating ERM into strategic planning procedures, organisations can bolster their capacity to recognise, evaluate, and alleviate risks by overarching objectives, enhancing overall performance and resilience.

5.6.2 The Internal Environment and its Effect on the ERM

Adoption Framework

Respondents were further asked to evaluate the role of internal organisational factors in ERM adoption and identify any additional components not previously proposed. Two key factors emerged from their responses: aligning risk appetite with risk tolerance and ensuring robust risk oversight.

Risk Appetite Aligned with Risk Tolerance

Respondents underscored the significance of harmonising risk inclination with risk endurance, stressing the necessity for consistency between the enterprise's risk inclination declarations and risk tolerance. Respondent 10 accentuated this aspect: "*They are both essential in the risk management process. Risk tolerance has to be aligned with the risk appetite. We define a risk appetite statement for every objective and identify to what extent this appetite can be tolerated.*" This viewpoint was reiterated by respondent 21, who highlighted enhancing risk oversight outcomes through harmonising risk inclination and endurance. The citations emphasise harmonising risk inclination with risk endurance in optimising risk oversight procedures. Organisations can establish distinct parameters for risk-assuming endeavours by ensuring coherence between these components and rendering informed judgments based on their risk oversight goals. This alignment promotes a more systematic approach to risk oversight, augmenting the organisation's capacity to navigate uncertainties proficiently.

Corporate Governance and Risk Oversight

Respondents emphasised the significance of sturdy risk supervision and corporate governance frameworks in facilitating efficient ERM adoption. Respondent 16 stressed the importance of a well-established risk supervision structure: "*When you have your risk appetite in line with the risk tolerance, you are sure that at least your decision-making process is based*

on clear grounds.” Likewise, respondent 11 voiced concerns about the organisation's current state of risk supervision, highlighting its pivotal role in supporting ERM initiatives. The statements provided by respondents highlight the importance of robust risk supervision and corporate governance frameworks in supporting ERM adoption and integration. These frameworks offer the essential supervision and accountability mechanisms to ensure ERM processes are effectively executed and harmonised with organisational objectives. Organisations can cultivate an environment conducive to ERM adoption by prioritising risk supervision and corporate governance and bolstering their overall risk management capabilities.

The insights provided by respondents underscore the critical organisational factors required for effective ERM adoption and integration. By aligning ERM with key organisational domains, such as strategic objectives, and ensuring sturdy risk supervision and corporate governance frameworks, organisations can enhance their capacity to manage risks effectively and accomplish their broader business goals. These findings underscore the significance of strategic alignment and governance structures in propelling successful ERM implementation within organisations.

5.6.3 Enterprise-wide Risk Culture

This segment delves into the function and influence of organisational culture on ERM implementation, as perceived by participants. Different facets of risk culture were scrutinised, encompassing risk mentality, data dissemination, openness in communication, comprehension of risk appetite and tolerance, and adherence to standards and morality.

Risk Mindset

Participants emphasised the necessity of fostering a risk-centric mindset within the organisation, concurring that this mindset should stem from upper management. One

respondent highlighted management's obligation to shape employees' viewpoints on risk, asserting, "*People do not develop risk mindset just like that. I mean. Naturally, it is the role of management to teach them and make them aware of the importance of thinking naturally about risk and not taking it as a task.*" This underscores the substantial impact of leadership in cultivating a culture that emphasises risk awareness and proactive risk management. The declaration underscores the significance of leadership in implanting a risk-aware culture in the organisation. By prioritising risk education and awareness endeavours, management can cultivate a workforce that acknowledges potential risks and is adept at making well-informed decisions to tackle them. This proactive approach to risk management is crucial for fortifying organisational resilience and facilitating the successful implementation of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM).

Information Sharing

Respondents unanimously recognised the importance of information sharing in facilitating effective ERM. They emphasised that quality information is essential for making informed risk-related decisions. Respondent 10 underscored this point: "*It is critical to ensure that our business decisions are based on quality information.*"

Efficient risk oversight depends significantly on data exchange within entities. This implies that exchanging data is pivotal for recognising, evaluating, and alleviating risks. Notably, data exchange performs a vital function in rendering risk oversight procedures efficient. When entities promote transparency and candidness, they guarantee that all stakeholders have access to pertinent data. This aids in making well-informed choices and formulating tactics to alleviate risks. Highlighting the significance of data exchange conforms with the optimal methods in Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) and is pivotal to its triumphant adoption.

Transparency in Communication

Respondents highlighted the importance of clear and transparent communication in fostering a strong organisational risk culture. They emphasised that transparent communication promotes trust and accountability, contributing to developing a robust risk culture. Respondent 25 emphasised this point: *"If we want to achieve a good adoption of ERM, we should work more on enhancing and promoting the importance of communicating information from both perspectives. I am not saying from the employees' side (bottom) but also from the top that it is the only way to reach transparency regarding risk information. In this way, we are contributing to a strong risk culture across the organisation"* This underscores the critical role of communication in fostering a culture of transparency and accountability. Clear communication is essential for nurturing a robust risk culture within businesses. By encouraging transparent communication channels, businesses can guarantee that risk-associated data reaches all stakeholders, enabling informed decision-making and proactive risk handling. This focus on transparency corresponds with top methods in ERM and underscores its significance in successful ERM implementation.

Understanding of Risk Appetite and Tolerance

The participants underscored the importance of ensuring that all staff grasp the company's risk inclination and endurance. They emphasised that clear risk criteria communication cultivates a risk-conscious culture and facilitates well-informed decision-making. According to Participant 23, understanding risk inclination and endurance by all staff, when effectively conveyed, prompts discussions about risk, thus reinforcing the organisational culture.

This highlights the importance of nurturing a mutual understanding of risk criteria throughout the company. The citation underscores the significance of promoting this mutual

understanding within the company. By guaranteeing that every employee grasps the corporation's risk standards, businesses can nurture a culture of risk awareness and enable well-informed decision-making. This focus on comprehending risk standards corresponds with top-notch Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) procedures and highlights its crucial function in propelling successful ERM implementation.

Respect for Norms and Ethics

The participants stressed the significance of integrating standards and morality into the organisational environment to support efficient ERM acceptance. They emphasised that sticking to moral principles nurtures reliance and honesty, contributing to establishing a sturdy risk atmosphere. Participant 5 articulated, “*Values and business ethics should be infused in our daily operations*”, highlighting the significance of moral behaviour in propelling prosperous ERM acceptance. The statement accentuates the importance of integrating standards and morality into the organisational environment to support efficient ERM acceptance. By prioritising moral behaviour and honesty, corporations can cultivate an atmosphere of reliance and responsibility, improving their capability to recognise, evaluate, and alleviate risks effectively. This focus on moral behaviour corresponds with recommended methods in ERM and accentuates its significance in propelling successful ERM acceptance.

Risk Education and Training

Participants stressed the significance of offering staff risk instruction and coaching to nurture a robust risk ethos within the establishment. They emphasised that such endeavours could enrich employees' comprehension of the establishment's risk outline and the advantages of ERM. Participant 17 articulated, “*Risk seminars and coaching that enlighten employees further about risk are the solution to embed risk culture gradually and enhance their perspective toward risk and how ERM can improve the establishment's performance*” This

underscores the role of instruction and coaching in advocating risk consciousness and fostering a proactive risk handling ethos. The citation emphasises the pivotal role of risk instruction and coaching in cultivating a sturdy risk ethos within the establishment. By allocating resources to endeavours that enrich employees' comprehension of risk management principles and practices, establishments can enable their workforce to actively pinpoint, evaluate, and alleviate risks. This proactive approach to risk handling is crucial for enriching organisational resilience and propelling successful ERM adoption.

5.6.4 Importance of the Infrastructure for ERM Adoption

This section examines the role and significance of the risk infrastructure in facilitating ERM adoption within the organisation. Respondents were asked to discuss the components of the risk infrastructure and their relevance to ERM adoption.

Risk Policies and Framework

Respondents acknowledged the importance of having clear risk policies and frameworks to support ERM adoption. However, they also pointed out gaps in their existing policies and frameworks, indicating a necessity for further advancement and synchronisation with ERM goals. Respondent 3 stressed the significance of formal risk directives in directing strategic objectives, remarking, *“We possess formal risk directives that I believe are accessible to everyone within the organisation. They encompass the actions we intend to undertake in our risk management process. They are important as they signify our actions towards our strategic objectives.”* This highlights the function of risk directives in furnishing a systematic approach to risk management and harmonising organisational endeavours with strategic aims. The statement underscores the pivotal role of risk directives and frameworks in fostering organisational ERM adoption. By establishing explicit guidelines and protocols for risk management, organisations can ensure coherence and synchronisation across departments and

facilitate efficacious decision-making processes. Nonetheless, recognising gaps in current policies accentuates the necessity for ongoing enhancement and evolution to support ERM objectives adequately.

ERM Governance

Survey participants emphasised the significance of governance arrangements in facilitating ERM acceptance and execution. They stressed that a well-defined governance framework is crucial for assigning responsibility and ensuring that risk management procedures are efficiently carried out. Participant 23 remarked, *“It is the only way to hold someone responsible or accountable for their actions. Well-defined governance allows you to have a clearer picture of the specific roles and responsibilities that, for instance, the risk manager has to be accountable for in the ERM process; the same applies to other people who are involved in ERM,”* highlighting the role of governance in providing clarity and responsibility in the ERM process. This statement underscores the importance of governance structures in supporting ERM acceptance and execution. By establishing explicit roles, duties, and accountability measures, organisations can guarantee that risk management procedures are effectively executed and harmonised with strategic objectives. This focus on governance is consistent with ERM best practices and highlights its significance in fostering successful ERM acceptance.

Oversight Structure

Respondents recognised the importance of oversight structures in supervising and evaluating risk management processes. They emphasised that a capable oversight structure is crucial for ensuring that risk management activities are conducted appropriately and contribute to achieving organisational goals. Participant 2 commented, *“It is very important for the adoption of the ERM framework, an oversight structure is the one that ensures that the processes of risk management are followed and performed appropriately and are working well*

towards achieving the goals,” highlighting the supervisory role in promoting consistency and adherence to established risk management methodologies. The quotation emphasises the crucial role of oversight structures in strengthening ERM integration and implementation. By providing guidance, monitoring, and supervision, these structures ensure the efficient implementation of risk management procedures and enhance organisational resilience. This emphasis on supervision aligns with ERM best practices and underscores its importance in driving successful ERM adoption.

Technology

Participants underscored the significance of technology as a crucial element of the risk framework and its function in facilitating efficient ERM. They emphasised that cutting-edge technologies can streamline risk evaluation processes and empower more organised risk charting compared to manual approaches. Participant 19 expressed, *“The use of advanced technologies can ease the way we assess internal and external risk more effectively compared to our methods that are done manually at the moment,”* stressing the potential advantages of technology in enhancing risk oversight practices. The statement underscores technology's role in augmenting the efficacy of ERM practices. Through harnessing cutting-edge technologies, entities can enhance the effectiveness and precision of risk evaluation processes, ultimately resulting in better-informed decision-making and risk mitigation strategies. This underscores the importance of investing in technological solutions to bolster ERM adoption and execution.

5.6.5 Role and Importance of ERM Integration

This section explored the significance of integrating risk into various organisational processes and decision-making aspects. Respondents were asked to discuss the importance of risk integration to ERM adoption.

Strategic Planning

Respondents accentuated the significance of assimilating risk considerations into strategic planning procedures to recognise potential hurdles and alleviate risks from the commencement. Respondent 16 articulated, *“Integrating risk when setting your strategy is very important. In this way, you uncover potential obstacles that may stop you from achieving your objectives. Hence, you can make changes,”* underscoring the role of risk integration in proactively tackling potential challenges and aligning strategic objectives with risk management priorities. The statement underscores the pivotal function of risk integration in strategic planning procedures. By encompassing risk considerations into strategic decision-making, organisations can bolster their capability to foresee and react to emerging risks, ultimately enhancing the probability of achieving strategic objectives. This underscores the significance of integrating risk management practices into broader organisational processes to amplify ERM adoption and effectiveness.

Structure and Ownership

The participants stressed the significance of explicit duties and supervision frameworks in facilitating ERM adoption and performance. They underscored that allocating explicit duties and instituting transparent supervision mechanisms are crucial for maximising the advantages of ERM. Participant 24 remarked, *“If you have clear on how risk should be identified, assessed and managed plus you understand who is responsible for ERM oversight undoubtedly you will achieve performance and a good adoption of ERM”*, highlighting the significance of clarity and responsibility in ERM implementation. The statement accentuates the crucial function of structure and ownership in propelling ERM adoption and performance. Organisations can ensure responsibility and transparency in risk management processes by outlining explicit roles and duties, ultimately boosting ERM's effectiveness. This underscores the significance of

establishing sturdy governance frameworks to support ERM implementation and integration within the organisation.

Performance Management

Respondents discussed the importance of performance management and performance metrics as part of ERM integration. They emphasised the value of using key risk indicators (KRIs) to monitor organisational risks and evaluate ERM performance. Respondent 19 commented, *“We are doing it like every organisation does. We measure our performance using Key performance indicators... um, like in the traditional way, but if I am to answer your question.... no, we do not use key risk indicators. Again, returning to our initial conversation, our ERM is not advanced, so I would not say we have a clear picture of performance and risk. However, I think it is valuable to know that key risk indicators allow you to monitor organisational risks constantly,”* highlighting the potential benefits of using risk metrics to assess risk exposure and inform decision-making processes. The quote underscores the importance of performance management and key risk metrics in supporting ERM integration and effectiveness. By instituting precise performance indicators and metrics, companies can monitor and assess their risk management endeavours, pinpoint areas for enhancement, and make educated choices to alleviate risks. This underscores the significance of integrating performance oversight methods into ERM frameworks to bolster organisational resilience and performance.

Enterprise-wide Communication

Respondents highlighted the role of enterprise-wide communication in facilitating effective risk integration and ERM adoption. They emphasised the importance of solid communication channels to ensure relevant stakeholders are engaged and informed about risk management processes. Respondent 16 stated, *“To integrate risk with the organisation's*

strategic directions, everyone should contribute by providing required information so everyone is involved for this to happen appropriately; powerful communication is the key.”

She underscores the critical role of communication in fostering collaboration and alignment across the organisation. The quote emphasises the importance of enterprise-wide communication in driving effective risk integration and ERM adoption. To enhance ERM endeavours, companies ought to prioritise transparent communication avenues. This nurtures stakeholder engagement and comprehension of risk management procedures, facilitating success. Highlighting communication and cooperation fosters a conducive atmosphere for ERM integration.

Table 5.5: Summary of the findings from the challenges facing ERM adoption

Components of Effective ERM Framework	Key Points
Strategic Alignment	- ERM should be aligned with organisational strategies and objectives for efficient performance.
	- Integration with strategic planning enables proactive risk management and goal alignment.
Internal Environment	- Factors like risk appetite, oversight, and corporate governance influence ERM adoption and effectiveness.
	- Clear risk policies and frameworks are essential but may require further development for ERM integration.
Risk Culture	- A risk-aware culture is crucial, supported by a risk mindset, information sharing, and transparency.
	- Norms, ethics, and risk education contribute to building a strong risk culture within the organisation.

Infrastructure	- Technology plays a critical role in facilitating risk assessment and management processes.
	- Governance structures and oversight mechanisms are essential for accountability and performance.
	- Integration of risk into strategic planning, performance management, and communication channels is vital.

5.7 Chapter Summary

The data analysis in the present chapter revealed the need for an ERM framework tailored to the needs of the insurance industry operating in Algeria. However, as demonstrated in Chapter 3, the existing ERM frameworks and standards need clearer implementation guidelines and consider the specific needs of the firms operating in the insurance industry. This chapter follows the proposed ERM adoption framework developed in Chapter 3 to validate its components.

Findings revealed an explicit agreement between the findings of the semi-structured interviews and the literature discussed in chapters 2 and 3 regarding the criticality and implication of the developed framework components.

The findings of this chapter revealed that ERM adoption across Algerian insurance firms is not associated with regulatory pressures as is the case for insurance firms operating in developed countries such as the USA and Europe; in contrast, ERM adoption has been mainly boosted by other factors such as competitors' successful adoption, nature of the business, education and professional qualifications, and the achievement of the objectives and maintain long-run sustainability. Moreover, the findings in this chapter demonstrated that ERM adoption

within the insurance firm studied is still immature and remains at an early stage. The findings also confirmed the challenges associated with ERM adoption discussed in Chapter Two.

Overall, the findings in this chapter support the aim of the research, which is to propose an ERM adoption framework tailored to the specific needs of insurance firms in Algeria. The next chapter will discuss the findings in line with the academic literature and provide practical guidelines to adopt the proposed framework.

6 Chapter Six: Results and Discussion of Findings

6.1 Introduction

Findings and discussion of outcomes presented in the previous chapter in the context of the qualitative analysis are discussed in the present chapter. The qualitative assessment of findings was conducted as a thematic analysis of data based on the data collected by the mean of 25 semi-structured interviews. The themes identified and formulated by the researcher have been discussed concerning the literature reviewed on ERM to establish the link between theory and findings revealed by the current research. Since the qualitative data analysis revealed mixed viewpoints concerning ERM adoption and its challenges at Cash Assurance Algeria, it is of utmost importance to analyse participants' responses based on existing literature and previous studies on ERM to achieve valid and reliable conclusions at the end of this research. Moreover, it was also identified by the analysis of interviews that ERM introduction and adoption at the company studied could be effective only if ERM is considered a strategic approach. In other words, the discussion chapter demonstrates the links between the literature and the findings in the context of the research objectives to clarify whether the set goals for the research have been attained.

In this regard, the first theme identified by the current research has addressed the ERM concept from the perspective of managers at the company studied. The second theme highlights the drivers boosting ERM adoption within the insurance firm learned Cash Assurance. The third theme identifies the challenges the insurance firm faces while adopting ERM. The fourth and final theme discusses the importance and role of different organisational factors required to achieve an effective ERM adoption within the insurance firm.

6.2 key findings of the interviews

The current section presents the findings and their connection to the research objectives in chapter 1.

6.2.1 Theme 1: Current Risk Management Practices at CASH

Assurance

Because the literature on ERM adoption and implementation in the context of developing countries is scarce (Silva et al.,2019), the empirical findings of the present research aimed to contribute by extending the knowledge on ERM adoption within the Algerian insurance industry, the first objective of the study sought to investigate how insurance firms have adopted ERM. The empirical findings revealed that ERM adoption within the insurance firm studied is still immature and at an early stage. Respondents' conceptions of the maturity level of their ERM adoption are reflected by their personal views. This implies that no standards or specific maturity models were employed to determine precisely the level of ERM maturity at the insurance firm studied. Respondents stated that they have made significant progress regarding ERM adoption since its introduction in 2016 in developing the basic blocks of their framework. In addition, the findings also confirmed that their firm is still following the traditional approach to risk, where risks are managed following a siloed approach through managing risks independently, and no interrelationship is considered.

To assess the ERM status at the insurance firm covered in this research, respondents were asked whether their firm has considered or adopted their firm considered or adopted universal ERM frameworks. They were further requested to identify any framework or standard used or adopted. The findings indicated that the most involved employees in the adoption process of ERM had identified the COSO ERM framework and ISO 31000:2009 as the most

widely known frameworks. They agreed that their firm had considered the COSO ERM framework (2004). However, most respondents agreed that the COSO ERM framework 2004 used to assist them in the ERM adoption is complex, which is in congruence with Purdy (2010), who argued that the COSO (1992; 2004) is involved in nature and lacks clear implementation guidelines on how ERM should be implemented.

The following section will discuss the findings of the second theme in line with the literature review.

6.2.2 Theme 2: factors driving ERM adoption

It is argued that ERM is an increasingly prevalent management practice adopted by organisations to coordinate a holistic risk management process. Anton (2018) opined that academics and industry practitioners consider ERM a new fundamental paradigm for managing the portfolio of organisations' risks. In congruence with this view, ERM adoption and implementation have been growing significantly in the past two decades, driven by both external and internal factors, such as those arising from regulatory pressures, and internal factors, such as the increased desire of the board within an organisation to achieve better risk management practices (Hernandez-Madrigal et al., 2020).

Previous research indicated that ERM adoption within the financial industry has been driven mainly by regulatory pressures (Kleffner et al., 2003; Simkins & Ramirez, 2008; Chapman, 2011). Several internal and external factors have shaped the shift in interest towards ERM adoption and implementation in the financial sector. In recent years, risk management practices of financial organisations have come under scrutiny from rating agencies, who have begun to advocate ERM adoption and implementation as part of their credit rating process (S&P, 2016). To respond to the regulatory requirement, senior management has started to align

ERM with their organisational structure, aiming to achieve effective ERM implementation and sustain business performance (Arena et al., 2011).

Regarding the insurance industry, ERM has become a highly significant and exciting field of investment (DiSerafino, 2016). Generally, ERM adoption and implementation among insurance firms have been driven primarily by the need to meet new regulatory standards, such as requirements for their Own Risk and Solvency Assessment (ORSA) (Tola, 2020).

Since ERM is a relatively emerging research area, it is probably typical for organisations to question the benefits behind its adoption and whether its implementation adds value (Locklear, 2012). Thus, insurance companies have specific characteristics and operate in dynamic business environments, causing them to face several risks and challenges arising from their political, social, and economic environment.

Findings accumulated from the qualitative analysis in Chapter 5 indicated that ERM adoption within the insurance firm studied has been mainly motivated by the following factors: "Successful ERM adoption among competitors » " level of education, professional experience, and professional qualifications » Industry nature

» and «value-creation «

Numerous internal and external factors have played critical roles in organisations' adoption of ERM. The literature reviewed on ERM adoption by insurance companies revealed that larger insurance companies are more likely to adopt ERM than smaller companies (Pagach & Warr, 2011). Empirical findings contradict the above findings. In the context of the insurance company study, the organisation's size has yet to be addressed by respondents as one of the factors that drove them to introduce and adopt an ERM.

Moreover, the literature highlighted that ERM adoption has responded to regulatory pressures in most regulated industries, such as insurance and banks, in the international context (Tola, 2020). In the context of insurance firms, it was noted that rating agencies have played a

significant role in driving the adoption and implementation of ERM. Credit was given to companies adopting and implementing the ERM process. Numerous studies have demonstrated how regulation scrutiny and rating agencies are among the significant factors shaping ERM adoption across the insurance industry and other financial industries; for instance, Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003), Lam (2006), Shenkir and Walker (2006), Acharyya (2008), Lundqvist (2014), and Khan et al. (2016). The findings of the above studies support the idea that ERM adoption decisions have responded to the influence of compliance and regulatory requirements. According to Acharyya (2008), insurance companies were found to be inspired by rating criteria to design and adopt an ERM. However, the findings of this research contradict those mentioned above, as analysis of qualitative data indicated that the adoption of ERM does not respond to any compliance and that any regulations have not boosted ERM adoption, nor has its adoption inspired by a rating system across the Algerian insurance industry. Therefore, findings could not support the effect of compliance and regulatory pressures on the adoption decision.

Thus, the findings did not support the effect of the big four as a driver behind ERM adoption. As interviewees highlighted clearly, they have yet to receive any suggestion from the Big Four to consider or adopt an ERM.

Successful ERM adoption among competitors

Regarding external factors, the findings are in line with the finding of Lam (2006), who argued that organisations that have adopted an ERM and benefited from its adoption could promote its adoption among players operating in the same industry. The finding indicated that ERM adoption within the insurance firm studied does respond to some extent to the feedback received from another firm within the insurance industry that adopted an ERM and perceived its benefits to their business and is now being rated by A.M Best.

Level of education, professional experience, and professional qualifications

Respondents revealed that the level of education, professional experience, and professional qualifications of their senior management were other factors that motivated ERM adoption within their firm. This is in correlation with previous literature, which showed that risk management integration level is positively affected by the background and training of managers (Colquitt *et al.*,1999). Moreover, professional experience, as revealed by the findings, affected not only the adoption decision of ERM but also the design of the ERM strategy to be followed regarding how to map the risks and allocate the required resources. Therefore, these findings support the idea that professional experience, qualifications and education are key in the ERM process.

Industry requirements (Nature of business)

Insurance firms' core business consists of accepting customers' unwanted risks; however, without efficient risk management mechanisms to tackle these risks, they are unlikely to achieve profitability or remain in business. It was argued in the literature that firms that belong to specific industries like the banking or energy industry are more likely to consider adopting an ERM to manage their risks due to the nature of their business (Colquitt *et al.*,1999; Kleffner *et al.*, 2003). The findings of this research agree with the literature and indicate that the nature of business operations has influenced ERM adoption decisions.

Value creation

There was a general agreement among respondents that value creation is considered one of the key factors shaping ERM introduction and adoption at the insurance firm studied. Findings are broadly congruent with prior literature on ERM, which argues that value is one of the roles of ERM, assuming that effective ERM implementation leads to value creation (Lechner & Gatzert, 2017; Shad *et al.*, 2018; Silva *et al.*, 2019; Iswajuni *et al.*, 2018; Li, 2018).

Thus, in the past few years, ERM has been accepted as an approach that helps organisations to create, preserve, and maximise the value for shareholders (KPMG, 2017b; Majdalawieh & Gammack, 2017; Bohnert *et al.*, 2019; Shad *et al.*, 2018; Slagmulder & Devoldere, 2018). Furthermore, in supporting the above ideas, Bohnert *et al.* (2019) stated that ERM supports the strategic planning process within organisations by providing capabilities to constantly examine, measure, and prevent risk. Moreover, ERM helps value creation for organisations through duplication avoidance, return on investment (ROA), management of silos, reducing risks, providing risk transparency for boards supporting the decision-making process, strong risk culture and optimisation, in addition to many other things (COSO, 2017; Lechner & Gatzert, 2017; Farrel & Gallagher, 2019).

6.2.3 Theme 3 challenges of ERM adoption at Cash Assurance

Findings from the qualitative analysis revealed no general agreement among interviewees regarding the anticipated adoption challenges of ERM within their respective companies. Interviewees highlighted that challenges encountered during the adoption of ERM are related to cultural issues, getting required talents, data resources constraints, time and cost, and inappropriate support from top managers.

The literature review in Chapter 2 identified some of the most recurring challenges concerning ERM adoption and implementation: lack of top management support, lack of supportive risk culture, lack of guidelines on developing and implementing ERM, and lack of industry-specific. It further highlighted that many financial organisations need help adopting and integrating ERM into their business environment (Beasley *et al.*, 2009).

Further challenges were identified by the current research, such as technological issues, data and information flow, and having the necessary outputs to adopt and implement ERM.

What is striking from the evaluation of the findings is that all challenges identified by participants are mainly related to internal factors.

However, results from this theme demonstrate that despite the different barriers and challenges encountered during ERM's introduction and adoption process, many organisations have reported positive results post-implementation (Beasley et al., 2018).

ERM is viewed as an integrative tool that drives unified risk oversight that is deemed to assist organisations with dealing with a spectrum of risks in a holistic manner (Sax & Anderson, 2018). Despite its successful implementation across different industries and recognised value, ERM is immature and affects organisational performance, sustainability, and resiliency (McShane, 2018). Accordingly, recognising what inhibits its adoption and implementation is the first step towards achieving maturity (Mensah & Gottwald, 2016; Viscelli et al., 2017).

The following section will discuss the challenges to adopting ERM as identified by respondents.

Lack of appropriate support from the top management

Support of ERM from top management is a common theme in the literature. Authors like Hoyt Liebenberg and Hoyt (2003) opined that senior management support is critical for ERM development. Hence, regardless of the wide adoption of ERM, senior management continues to fear adopting it within their organisations. This was attributed by Chapman (2007) and Barton et al. (2008a) to the difficulty in understanding how to align ERM with existing organisational processes to achieve sustainability and create value and competitive advantage.

Top management support has been widely debated in the literature. Developing an ERM strategy is a continuous process to maintain applicability (Aabo et al., 2005). ERM is mainly considered a top-down approach, where top management deploys organisational

imperatives. Beasley et al. (2005) elaborated that top management support and commitment are crucial and relevant for the effective adoption and execution of ERM.

Respondents suggested that setting up the tone at the top was insufficient to achieve an effective ERM. They further argued that top management's support, encouragement, and commitment should be present at all ERM adoption and implementation stages. This is by Kleffner et al. (2003) and Gates (2006), who consider top management commitment and support to be an internal force that drives ERM adoption and implementation regardless of the specificity of the industry. Commitment from top management should make people within the organisation perceive ERM as a priority. Although the findings are compatible with previous general findings of other researchers, evaluation of findings from the current study reinforces that the lack of top management support at all ERM adoption and implementation stages remains an issue.

Lack of Appropriate Technology

The evaluation of findings showed that respondents are concerned about technological issues that may be faced through the adoption and implementation process of ERM. Respondents expressed concern about the software utilised in their respective companies and described it as acceptable but not good enough to ensure a smooth ERM implementation. They further argued that some aspects of their software regarding information flow and how quickly data is updated.

Findings reveal that most interviewed participants understand the critical role of supporting tools and technologies in ERM adoption. Findings align with Francis and Paladino (2008), who argued that employing strong tools and technologies that support ERM would strengthen the automation of risk practices and allow for a more robust structure to manage risks.

Lack of clear understanding of the benefits of ERM adoption

This sub-theme has revealed that most respondents emphasised that understanding the benefits associated with introducing and adopting ERM within their respective insurance firm is the key to achieving an effective and mature ERM. Previous research has not demonstrated explicitly whether understanding the benefits associated with ERM adoption and implementation is an effect. However, most recent studies recognised that understanding the benefits of adopting an ERM is the key driver behind its adoption (Zhao et al., 2015). Hence, considering ERM is an emerging discipline, it is arguably natural for organisations to become concerned about its adoption and implementation benefits and whether they are sustainable (Locklear, 2012).

ERM adoption and implementation have benefited insurance companies differently (Jabbour, 2016). Most importantly, ERM adoption will differ from one organisation to another depending on the strategic objectives set to be achieved. The benefit of ERM adoption has been widely studied in the context of financial organisations. However, very little is known about its benefits in the context of insurance companies, where knowledge is scarce (Jabbour, 2016).

Lack of in-house skills and Knowledge in ERM adoption

This finding refers to the insufficient skills required for the risk functions. Respondents reported that a lack of skilled employees could affect the ability to understand what risks organisations are confronted with and their consequences, eventually affecting the deployment of suitable solutions. Given this, the lack of in-house qualified personnel to direct and implement ERM is a clear obstacle for organisations in deploying appropriate risk oversight, leading to difficulties in achieving ERM effectiveness and maturity (Zhao et al., 2015; Renault et al., 2016). This is congruent with respondents' views, who agreed that the lack of internally skilled personnel to execute ERM is a barrier.

Lack of an enterprise-wide risk culture

Despite the significant consideration of the literature on the importance of developing a strong and supportive risk culture across the organisation to support ERM adoption and implementation, empirical findings noted another challenge that could inhibit ERM adoption and implementation. Findings showed that respondents considered culture as a risk that could impact their organisation in achieving an effective ERM adoption. As reported by most respondents, one of the critical challenges to achieving an effective ERM is to achieve the buy-in across all company departments. More importantly, tackling a risk culture is found in the literature as a significant barrier as it involves cultural changes brought about by ERM (Hermanson & Beasley, 2017; Prioteasa. And Ciocoiu, 2017). People tend often to resist change; they need to be persuaded about the value of the change and how this change can add to their company.

Culture is undoubtedly a significant element of an ERM program (COSO, 2016). In organisational cultures, constraints, such as behaviour, beliefs, values, attitude, experience, communication, ethics, and informal norms, can hinder the effective adoption and implementation of an ERM program if adherence to change exists (Kimbrough & Compensation, 2009). The qualitative data analysis findings indicate that respondents recognise that culture is essential to value creation. However, as demonstrated in Chapter 2, literature still lacks the need to include culture from a practical perspective. The literature does not explicitly address the impact of developing an enterprise-wide culture in supporting the process of ERM adoption and implementation within organisations. To some extent, the findings align with Gates et al. (2009), who conclude that with a strong cultural foundation, it is easier to capitalise on the potential benefits that ERM adoption could offer.

Lack of a clear flow of information required for ERM adoption

Respondents reported this as being amongst the significant constraints facing the effective adoption and implementation of ERM. Based on respondents, the impact of the quality of data shared across the departments of the organisation, as well as communicating data that are poor, incomplete, or incorrect, is seen as significantly impacting issues on the execution of ERM, authors like Viscelli, Hermanson and Beasley (2017) stated that lack of flow of risk information can influence the decision-making process as well as affecting the organisational performance.

It is clear from the findings that participants understood the importance of communication and information sharing in time in promoting transparency and enabling more performance. Findings are congruent with Arena et al. (2010), who argued that communication is the standardised mechanism that supports risk integration and ensures that information is communicated promptly to different business units through internal communication channels, supporting collaboration, overcoming misunderstanding and breaking down siloed approaches.

Communication at all organisations and bottom) is critical for developing an enterprise-wide risk culture. Regular talks about risks promote an organisation that is free of pressure. Thus, creating good organisational communication and understanding of risk appetite and risk tolerance among all members.

6.2.4 Theme 4: To validate the proposed strategic ERM adoption framework

This section addresses the findings from Chapter 5 regarding the development and validation of the developed ERM adoption framework in Chapter 3.

Participant's perception of the alignment of ERM with key organisational areas

It is argued that ERM implementation ensures value creation, appropriate risk culture, and the organisational strategy; therefore, aligning ERM with key organisational areas remains a priority (Yaraghi & Langhe, 2011; Aebi *et al.*, 2012; Gatzert & Martin, 2015). Findings from the analysis revealed that the widely accepted view among participants is that, to achieve organisational objectives, an alignment between strategies and objectives and different organisational departments is required. COSO's (2004, 2016) definition of ERM explicitly emphasises the vitality of organisational objectives (strategic directions) and the control functions across the organisation. Achieving an alignment across an organisation not only helps reach expectations and strategic direction (objectives) but also helps promote a risk safeguard that helps to enhance the way organisations identify, understand, communicate, and mitigate risks at an enterprise-wide level (Mikes, 2004).

Participant's perception of the importance of the internal environment on the proposed ERM adoption framework

This subsection accounts for participants' answers regarding the importance of the internal organisational factors and their implications for adopting the proposed ERM framework.

- Mission, vision and core values: Every organisation is particular; consequently, its mission, vision and core values define its philosophy. Furthermore, how an organisation sets its strategies and objectives defines its risk oversight options. Therefore, achieving the mission, vision and core values rests on the support of risk oversight. Hence, this achievement depends on how it aligns with the strategy and objectives, as well as with the risk oversight (COSO, 2017)

- Risk appetite aligned with risk tolerance: Aligning the organisation's risk appetite with tolerance was articulated by respondents as compulsory for the adoption of the ERM. This is in line with the literature, where it is argued that the alignment of the risk appetite to risk tolerance allows the organisation to have a more optimal perspective towards risk and return (Society of Actuaries, 2012). Furthermore, findings demonstrated that respondents understood what can happen if the risk-bearing capacity exceeds the achievement of the strategic directions (Farrel & Gallagher, 2014)
- Risk oversight: According to Majdalawich and Gammack (2017), risk oversight represents the holistic approach followed by an organisation to deal with emerging risks. Risk is part of any organisation's activity; a poor risk oversight practice can result in high-risk exposure or failure (Jorion, 2009). Moreover, It is significantly vital that risk oversight be aligned with the business strategy (COSO, 2016) and implemented throughout the whole organisation. The oversight function is a prerequisite in an organisation, and findings from the analysis in Chapter 5 articulate its significant role and effect on ERM adoption. Defined as a top-down approach, risk oversight reduces risks and exploits opportunistic risks based on informed decisions (Agarwal & Ansell, 2016; Andren & Lundqvist, 2017). Accordingly, a well-developed risk oversight should ensure a holistic understanding of all the risks facing an organisation.
- Corporate governance: Corporate governance is responsible for setting the rules and regulations that should be applied to an organisation's processes, practices, systems and procedures. It creates assurance, accountability and structure in the decision-making (Dabari et al., 2017). ERM and corporate governance are interrelated as they help organisations understand, analyse, mitigate and manage

their risks in a structured way (Zahiruddin & Norlida, 2013). According to McShane (2018), ERM is active in corporate governance and incorporated into business-driven governance functions. Findings revealed that respondents need a clearer understanding of the strategic benefits of integrating ERM with corporate governance. It is yet to be integrated with corporate governance.

- Ignore the strategic benefits of integrating ERM with corporate governance, as stated in Chapter 3 by Frigo and Anderson (2011).

Role and effect of risk culture in ERM

Various research has considered the link between organisational culture and effective ERM adoption and implementation. “Infusing risk culture” was identified by interviewees as the second most important motivator for adopting and implementing ERM. This aligns with Keith et al. (2013), who highlighted the importance of a risk culture as a key element for a comprehensive ERM aiming to achieve strategic goals. Developing a culture that accepts risk in all its aspects is the key to a successful risk management process. Similarly, COSO 2016 defines ERM as dependent upon “culture, capabilities, and practices” (COSO, 2016; Bohnert *et al.*, 2019). However, as the literature indicates, establishing and infusing risk culture within an organisation is not easy. Researchers like Braumann (2018) found **that risk awareness** is an indirect component of culture influencing effective ERM adoption and organisational effectiveness. Risk culture is critical in strengthening oversight capability, awareness, and responsibility (Roeschmann, 2014). It further assists organisations in advancing their risk mindset by helping them understand the overall risk picture from risk-averse and opportunistic perspectives (Rochette, 2009). The risk culture mindset was reflected in participant’s responses through different lenses (communication, norms and ethics, and information sharing).

- **Risk mindset: Embedding ERM to the organisational culture fosters the organisation's risk mindset.** Enhancing a risk mindset implies understanding the whole risk picture from two different perspectives: a risk-averse and an opportunistic perspective (Rochette, 2009).
- **Information sharing: ERM should be considered everyone's responsibility; everyone within the organisation should consider "risk" as part of the organisation's risk awareness.** Sharing information is the key to creating and promoting an open-risk culture that supports ERM. Analysis of the findings in Chapter 5 revealed that most respondents (21 out of 25) consider that information sharing benefits all parties involved. According to Rodriguez and Edwards (2010), information sharing is knowledge management, which is done via people, processes and technology. These views emphasise the element of humans as critical. This is demonstrated in the empirical findings where respondents and through their personal experience and perceptions of the value of sharing and communicating information through the whole organisation. Furthermore, information sharing facilitates collaboration, leading to the creation of trust at an enterprise-wide level
- **Transparency in communication:** An enterprise-wide communication is a practice suggested by the COSO ERM Framework 2004 (COSO, 2004). The COSO ERM framework emphasises the importance of prompt communication and information sharing throughout the organisation.
- Respondents revealed that clear and transparent communication is the key to achieving a consistent risk culture and enabling performance. Findings are congruent with Arena et al.(2010), who consider communication a standardised mechanism supporting the integration of risks. Therefore, the findings support the view that ERM effectiveness and communication have a positive relationship.

- **Proper understanding of risk appetite and risk tolerance:** Appetite to risk is defined by The British Risk Standard BS 311100 as the amount and the type of risks that an organisation is ready to seek, accept and tolerate in pursuit of value and goals achievement (BSI, 2011). In other words, risk appetite sets the boundaries of tolerability with regard to risk degree and quantity (Oliveira *et al.*, 2018). It is about understanding what risk is accepted in return for an opportunity. The risk appetite statement must be constantly updated and communicated (COSO, 2012). Respondents highlighted its significance to the organisational culture and the adoption and implementation of the proposed framework. Researchers like Lam (2017) suggested that metrics such as KRIs can be used to identify whether risks are within acceptable levels. Surprisingly, the empirical findings revealed that the insurance firm studied does not use KRIs, which is part of the recommendations for the effective adoption and implementation of the proposed framework.
- **Respect of norms and ethics:** Regarding the respect of norms and ethics, the research findings demonstrated that most respondents understood how critical the respect of ethical values is to successful ERM adoption. Respect for norms and ethics represent key cultural attributes such as adherence to rules, enterprise-wide collaborations, and measuring and rewarding risk performance in order to enhance decision-making (Pagach & Warr, 2010).

The experiences and perceptions of the respondents on the importance of enterprise-wide risk culture to the proposed strategic adoption framework make it apparent that enterprise risk culture should be driven by the top management, who should be already actively involved in ERM. As ERM gains acceptance when driven by the organisation's leadership, who is responsible for gradually building its importance, therefore it can lead to its buy-in among other employees at the middle and lower levels of the organisation.

6.2.5 Respondent's perception of ERM infrastructure as a key element of the proposed framework

- **Risk policies and frameworks:** ERM policies represent the formal written statement that explains the responsibilities of the management and board and addresses risk culture, appetite and strategy as well as the organisation's risk management philosophy (CESG,2012). The policy sets ERM's statement (scope), objectives, and vision, and the framework represents the practices and processes (Chapman, 2011). The empirical findings demonstrated that respondents understood the importance of risk policies and frameworks. However, they argued that the company does not have a clear and formal statement yet included in its risk management policy.
- **ERM Governance:** Risk governance refers to the structure that includes how ERM roles and responsibilities are allocated to individuals and groups. It entails the reporting relationships and authorities involved in ERM, as well as policies and procedures covering ERM. Aksel's (2009) and Mehta's (2010) findings indicated that the risk governance structure of an organisation influences the adoption of ERM as it is the one responsible for determining how risk management should be performed.
- **Oversight structure:** An oversight structure is a critical enabler in aligning communication, functions, and practices with the organisation's objectives (Fraser & Simkins, 2010). Andren and Lundqvist (2017) argued that an oversight structure is an element of ERM, whose task entails the strategic coordination of structure, practices, and responsibilities. The empirical findings show that respondents understand the vital role of an oversight structure in ERM adoption and implementation.
- **Technology:** It was argued that technology affects risk management activities closely (Saeidi *et al.*, 2019). Scholars like Arena *et al.* (2010), Saeidi *et al.*(2019), and Yaraghi and Langhe (2011) highlighted the importance of advanced technology in improving

organisations' risk management capabilities. Similarly, authors like Rolland(2008) argued that it is almost impossible to effectively manage risks without an efficient IT system. Rolland (2008) further explained that technology may affect risk management differently, for instance, by generating relevant connections between risk management and business performance. Moreover, Oliveira *et al.*(2019), in their study to investigate the critical success factors that have the greatest influence on ERM implementation, identified technology as a critical success factor for ERM.

Respondents have explicitly revealed that to achieve an effective ERM adoption, support of technologies is critical, and a more advanced IT system is required to support ERM adoption within their firm. The strength and advantages of adopting technologies in ERM adoption and implementation is the automation of the risk practices and stronger structure for managing risks (Francis & Paladino, 2008)

6.2.6 Respondent's perception of ERM integration

- **Strategic planning:** According to Lam (2017), Effective and successful ERM allows the alignment of strategic planning with risk oversight and risk assessment in order to ensure integration. Integration generally happens through a top-down approach, which integrates strategy and objectives within the strategic planning (COSO, 2017). Integrating ERM at the strategic planning stage allows the organisation to understand the type and amount of risks that can be tolerated to achieve its strategic directions (COSO, 2017). Without integrating risk in the strategic planning stage, an organisation may establish objectives, strategic goals, and initiatives that do not anticipate the obstacles to realising value (Bromiley *et al.*, 2015; Frigo & Anderson, 2011). Findings indicated that respondents consider strategic planning critical for enabling risk

integration and revealed that risk is yet to be fully included in their organisation's strategic planning.

- **Structure and ownership:** Structure and ownership are referred to in the literature as the organisational structure and how different roles and processes are defined. It is considered the administrative mechanism responsible for performance delivery (Chenhall, 2003). Respondents indicated that risk integration cannot occur without having a clear structure on how risk should be managed and integrated and strong support from risk owners.
- **Performance management:** Most of the literature on ERM focuses on investigating the link between implementing an ERM and organisational performance (Gordon *et al.*, 2009). Performance is an objective resulting from ERM (Lin *et al.*, 2012). The importance of evaluating performance lies in its contribution to increasing organisational capability to receive more visibility changes (Lalitha & Nandini, 2015). Similarly, measuring performance allows organisations to draw more attention towards their risk management weaknesses. By doing this, risks will be classified and prioritised based on their severity. Therefore, their impact on the strategy and strategic directions of the organisation is controlled (COSO, 2017). Regarding performance management, respondents demonstrated that they understood the criticality of performance management to ERM sustainability and further indicated that measuring performance is a critical implication to the strategy and objective-setting process.
- **Enterprise-wide communication:** It is argued in the literature that communication plays an important role in implementing an ERM. Moreover, as identified earlier in the subsection (Role and importance of ERM culture in ERM framework), it is a critical component of ERM culture. It is an important enabler for building a consistent risk culture for successful ERM adoption. These findings agree with the literature, as

Oliveira et al.(2018) argued that communicating risks across different organisational levels promotes awareness and accuracy of information.

6.2.7 Research framework validation

The focus of this section is to investigate how the proposed ERM adoption framework developed in section 3.6, based on the literature review findings and the gap identified, has changed in the view of empirical findings.

The proposed ERM adoption framework in Chapter 3, figure 3.5, was built from the main findings of academic and industry contributions. The key aim of the framework was to address the literature gap that has highlighted the need for a framework that aligns ERM with critical internal and external factors within the organisation. Accordingly, the researcher first identified the key factors fundamental to integrating ERM and then validated their importance via empirical data (chapter 5).

Compared to the proposed ERM adoption framework presented in Chapter 3, section 3.6, this new version adds the perspective of empirical results in the context of the Algerian insurance industry. The conclusions that were drawn from the findings of the literature reviewed in Chapter 2 provided the grounds for developing the initial framework. Accordingly, the contributions from the empirical results have indicated the need to refine the initially proposed framework. On these bases, The ERM culture component originally comprised Transparent communication, a proper understanding of risk appetite, respect for norms and ethics, a risk mindset and accountability (Figure 3.5). The empirical findings demonstrated an essential element of ERM culture that must be added to achieve an enterprise-wide ERM culture. Interviewees considered risk education and training as critical components of an ERM culture, which was not part of the ERM culture component (section 3.7.2) and has been added as part of the contributions of empirical findings.

Moreover, the external and internal factors were regrouped following the findings to influence the infrastructure of ERM and the organisational mission and strategy.

As demonstrated in Chapter 5, respondents argued that risk ownership within the organisation must remain within the organisation at the top, and its accountability should be held by the senior managers (e.g. CEO) and directors. However, as reported in the literature in Chapter 2, ERM responsibility within an organisation still varies.

Following the interpretation of the empirical findings presented in Chapter 5, the researcher recommends that the following should be considered at an enterprise-wide level as efforts to achieve and sustain an effective ERM adoption and execution:

1. Top management support and buy-in of ERM
2. Enterprise risk culture
3. Risk education and training

An organisation's Risk culture reflects how employees understand, perceive and approach risk. Since many respondents argued that an ERM program can only be adopted effectively with a solid enterprise-wide risk culture, the researcher recommends that senior management and BOD should actively support and invest in ERM and communicate that devotion throughout the organisation, as reported by respondents in chapter 5, risk education and training that is supported by enterprise-wide risk culture across the various stages of the adoption and execution of the proposed framework as necessary and prerequisite to sustaining an effective ERM.

Respondents also reported that a risk-aware culture is a critical factor that helps to stimulate ERM buy-in and acceptance through the organisation. The researcher suggests that an enterprise-wide risk culture should be developed naturally rather than imposed within an organisation. Transparent communication among all organisational departments and allowing

contributions from all levels help identify organisational risks and create awareness among employees and culture across the organisation.

6.2.8 Objective 5: Practical guidelines for the adoption and implementation of the proposed ERM framework

This section presents the researcher's practical guidelines for adopting and implementing the proposed ERM framework developed in Chapter 3 and validated in the present chapter based on the literature review and empirical findings of the current research. According to previous academic and industry findings, organisations should initially analyse the current state of their risk management practices and then integrate it with a strategy that allows its evolution and transformation into ERM (Protiviti, 2006; Rao & Dev, 2007). Moreover, prior to embarking on the process of the implementation of the framework, the researcher suggests that senior management consider the following questions:

- What is the present organisational structure?
- How can ERM become embedded within the current organisational structure?
- How do you promote ERM buy-in and commitment among top management?
- What is the value for adopting an ERM?
- How can the ERM framework be aligned with the organisational strategies and objectives?
- How do you establish a strong risk culture that contributes to the effective alignment of ERM, promotes the buy-in of ERM among the organisation, and helps overcome different adoption challenges?

- How do you develop a clear risk structure and assign responsibilities throughout the ERM adoption and implementation?

The researcher considers the above questions as an important element of ERM and, hence, critical to validate the proposed ERM adoption framework and its practical adoption and implementation guidelines. Defining the current organisational structure is an integral step in ERM adoption, as it allows the top management to identify their current organisational structure and decide on how ERM can be integrated into it. Moreover, management should understand and define the goals behind adopting ERM and then clearly communicate them throughout the organisation. Every employee must understand and become aware of the organisation's strategic direction (i.e., vision, mission, key objectives). Accordingly, the researcher recommends the consideration of the following adoption and implementation steps to achieve an effective adoption and implementation of the proposed ERM framework.

- Establish the external context: Insurance firms operate in a highly complex environment (Gatzert et al., 2016) and are exposed to various dynamics arising from their external environment. Therefore, establishing the external context in which insurance firms operate is the first critical step towards adopting the proposed ERM framework. The researcher suggests that senior management must consider establishing the external environment as the initial step when designing the ERM alignment process, as managers should understand the external dynamic and its effect on operational performance prior to adopting and fully implementing an ERM program. Since external risks are beyond the organisation's control and should be managed with care by identifying their type, assessing the degree of their occurrence, and ultimately developing plans to mitigate their impact. Such factors could be investigated through the use of a variety of analytical tools like PESTEL

analysis (political, economic, sociocultural, technological, environmental and legal environment), scenario analysis, SWOT (strength, weakness, opportunities, threats)

- Define the mission, vision, and values clearly.
- Provide ERM deployment guidelines.
- Outline constantly the benefits and the challenges associated with the adoption of ERM.
- Establish clear structure and ownership of risk: Define the risk oversight structure that effectively aligns processes, functions, and practice. Determining the structure and ownership of risk has been a recurring topic in the reviewed literature (Hampton, 2010; Locklear, 2012). Management continues to face problems with determining the most appropriate risk structure that permits effective identification, reporting and the escalation of risk. Organisations may assign the risk oversight responsibility to a group or committee or an individual. Establishing the appropriate risk structure in an organisation is a key step towards an effective and sustainable ERM. Therefore, the researcher suggests that the organisation establish the roles of the board of directors (BOD) and senior managers and communicate them through all business departments. A clear ownership of ERM oversight must be developed. Furthermore, both roles and responsibilities of the BOD and the committee responsible for ERM oversight and their respective reporting lines must be communicated and made available to all individuals in the organisation. Furthermore, Identified ERM champions within the organisation must educate individuals within all levels of the organisation on ERM principles; by doing so, all employees within the organisation will understand their role in the process of

adoption and implementation of ERM, resulting in the creation of a consistent ERM culture across the organisation.

- Develop awareness and an enterprise-wide risk culture across the organisation: The empirical findings discussed in chapter five identified ERM culture as a key element to effectively adopting an ERM program. A weak risk culture may lead an organisation to lose opportunities and damage its reputation (Brooks, 2010). Due to its complexity, the proposed framework divided this component into sub-components, which were discussed in detail in chapter three, section 3.5 and validated in chapter six. This is also considered a key strength of the current research, as it highlights the main factors related to establishing a consistent risk culture. Promote enterprise-wide communication across the organisation continuously through the communication channels. The researcher suggests that a formal procedure should be implemented to reduce communication channel risks.
- The researcher recommends that the organisation, prior to starting designing its ERM framework, should first understand the key strategic risks and analyse their impact on achieving business goals. The identification of the key risks that are inherent in the strategic direction of an organisation is a prerequisite to the integration of ERM into the business plan (Oldfield & Santomero, 1997)
- Establish policies around the ERM framework and make them available across the organisation so all employees can refer to them for the enterprise-wide risk standards.
- The researcher also recommends that the organisation define the most efficient risk management tools and techniques to identify the key risks from an enterprise-wide approach, as this is a critical step in the development and integration of ERM. The

organisation must decide which tools to use to achieve its objectives. For instance, tools like risk databases and risk checklists.

- Participants in the semi-structured interviews indicated that their organisation relies mainly on Key performance indicators (KPIs) to track the business performance, as demonstrated by the literature reviewed in chapter three. Developing KPIs along with KRIs allows organisations to evaluate the ERMs strategy effectively (Althonayan *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, the researcher recommends the use of key indicators (KRIs) as part of ERM adoption, as this would assist the case company in determining its level of risk appetite (Immaneni *et al.*, 2004) as KRIs can warn management on the organisation's level of risk tolerance, therefore developing KRIs would help to provide the data needed in order to identify the risks that could prevent the organisation from achieving its objectives. These KRIs, as Lam (2005) recommended, could be derived from policies and regulations, strategies and objectives, past losses and incidents, and different stakeholder requirements and risk assessments. Developing KRIs along with KPIs is critical throughout adopting the ERM framework. They are valuable tools that help create feedback loops among the top management, the business and other departments.

The researcher suggests that Cash Assurance develop an enterprise-wide risk communication strategy which should be aligned with risk education and training programmes. Communication of risk information to different stakeholders across the organisation is vital to ERM. Decision-makers within the organisation rely on information on the main risks to make strategic decisions. This means that timely and high-quality information should be communicated across top management, directors and risk champion (Rizzi, 2010)

6.3 Chapter Summary

The present chapter has critically analysed the empirical findings in line with the research objectives. Moreover, this chapter validated the proposed ERM adoption framework discussed in the chapter by adding the perspective of the empirical findings.

Several key themes that have emerged from the data collected were discussed. Data analysis was drawn based on the research aim and objectives established in the first chapter of this research.

Empirical findings have presented a knowledge extension within the context of the insurance industry in Algeria. By addressing the research problem through research objectives, the current research assessed empirical findings to explore key determinants, factors shaping ERM adoption, and challenges associated with ERM introduction and adoption that would allow an effective ERM adoption to be achieved.

In this context, empirical findings showed that various factors have shaped the decision to adopt ERM at the insurance company studied. Further, results revealed that ERM introduction and adoption at CASH Assurance had been mainly driven by internal drivers, contrary to one mid-level manager who argued that competition as an additional external driver had led Cash Assurance towards ERM adoption. On the contrary, previous research investigating adoption drivers for ERM found that a mix of internal and external factors have shaped ERM adoption within insurance companies; this study demonstrated that risk management practices within the Algerian context are different and do not respond to similar forces. Thus, analysis of empirical findings further indicates that ERM adoption is not part of compliance, and therefore, ERM was mainly adopted for its benefits (Pagach & Warr, 2011) rather than as part of regulation scrutiny. This finding disagrees with the literature, which demonstrates that within the context of insurance companies, ERM adoption has responded mainly to regulation scrutiny from regulatory bodies and rating agencies in the aftermath of the

financial crisis, calling for more robust risk management practices. Thus, from an emerging market perspective, empirical results demonstrated that risk management practices do not follow international standards. Therefore, a big gap is present.

Various challenges associated with ERM introduction and adoption at CASH Assurance, Algeria, have been identified. Respondents mainly attributed challenges to a lack of support from top management, an enterprise-wide risk culture, human and intellectual resources, problems understanding strategic direction, data and information communication, ERM adoption benefits, and problems related to software and technological resources. To some extent, similar challenges were indicated by several research studies. Another key challenge that top-managers have highlighted is the alignment of ERM with key organisational areas, which is consistent with (Yaraghi & Langhe, 2011; Aebi *et al.*, 2012; Gatzler & Martin, 2015). Ultimately, top and mid-level managers perceive ERM as an expensive initiative that requires lots of investments.

Such challenges are considered to threaten the achievement of ERM adoption benefits. Nevertheless, findings demonstrate several determinants that support ERM adoption and implementation at Cash Assurance, Algeria. These determinants are associated with the support provided by the CEO, risk manager appointment, risk management experience, and the support of the CEO, CRO, and top managers in terms of endorsing a risk culture as well as educational resources.

7 Chapter Seven: Conclusion, Contribution and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

This chapter summarises the research findings and demonstrates how they contributed to achieving the research objectives. The chapter reviews the research objectives, justifies their achievements, and concludes the findings. In addition, the findings' implications are illustrated. Then, the chapter provides a perspective for future research. Finally, it highlights the potential limitations and whether those have affected the achievement of the research objectives.

The following section reiterates the research objectives to guide the findings.

7.2 Research aim, objectives and questions

Research aim:

To develop an ERM adoption framework applicable to the Algerian insurance industry.

Research Objectives

- To investigate ERM adoption at Cash Assurance Algeria.
- To investigate the main drivers behind ERM adoption in the insurance industry.
- To explore the key challenges to ERM adoption.
- To validate the proposed ERM framework
- To provide practical guidance for the proposed adoption framework.

Research Questions

1. What is the current state of ERM adoption at Cash Assurance?
2. What are the main drivers behind adopting ERM among insurance firms?

3. How do insurance firms face the ERM adoption challenges in general and in Algeria?
4. What are the components of an effective ERM adoption framework?
5. How can a proposed ERM adoption framework be adopted for insurance firms in Algeria?

Overall, the research accounts for five objectives developed at the beginning of the research in chapter one; each objective seeks to develop knowledge at different levels concerning ERM adoption at Cash Assurance, Algeria. The mean of both theoretical and empirical data achieved the five objectives. First, the researcher reviewed previous relevant studies to build a better understanding of the adoption of ERM along with its evolution in different industries and geographical contexts. Then, the researcher investigated its implications for the primary data collected.

The following session summarises the research objectives that this research aimed to achieve.

Objective One: *To investigate ERM adoption at Cash Assurance Algeria.*

This objective was addressed in the context of the empirical data collected from the qualitative interviews and represents the first stage for identifying the primary data. The findings indicated that ERM adoption within the insurance firm studied is still early. Furthermore, The findings also outlined that regardless of the availability of a large number of ERM frameworks that could be applied to any organisation, the insurance firm studied disregarded adopting one of the available ERM frameworks; instead, they aimed to design and develop their framework which can assist them to achieve strategic maturity.

The following section outlines objective two.

Objective Two: *To investigate the main drivers behind ERM adoption in the insurance industry*

This objective aimed to investigate the factors driving the adoption of ERM at the insurance firm studied (Cash Assurance). This objective was addressed in the context of the empirical findings of the research, where qualitative data was gathered from 25 qualitative, in-depth, semi-structured interviews. This implies that this objective was achieved through primary and secondary data, where secondary data from peer-reviewed journals and online databases were used for triangulation purposes (i.e. establishing similarities and differences found in primary data based on the secondary data reviewed previously). Findings indicated that ERM adoption at Cash Assurance is mostly driven by internal factors and only one external factor. The dominance of internal factors could be attributed in the case of the insurance firm studied to their ultimate objectives and views of management regarding ERM benefits.

The drivers as identified by respondents are: “Successful ERM adoption among competitors”, “Level of education, professional experience, and professional qualification”, “Nature of the industry”, and “Value creation”.

Surprisingly, the findings of this research contradict previous research findings, which found that regulations and compliance with several legislation drove ERM adoption and implementation. For instance, Bohnert *et al.*(2019) found that a significant proportion of this development of ERM in the insurance industry has been triggered by regulatory need, which has, for many insurance firms, tended to be interpreted as requiring a ‘compliance’ focus rather than being primarily driven by the business itself. Moreover, according to Bohnert *et al.*(2019), the adoption of ERM was mainly driven by regulation scrutiny across European insurance firms. Accordingly, ERM adoption across the insurance industry in Algeria responds to different factors compared to other insurance firms in other geographical settings.

The following section will present this research's third objective and how it has been achieved.

Objective Three: *To explore the key challenges to ERM adoption*

The third objective of the research was designed to investigate the challenges that insurance firms encounter during the ERM adoption process, as it is critical to identify any problems in order to be able to provide recommendations for enhancing this adoption. The findings of this research indicated that insurance firms face various challenges regarding adopting ERM. Current challenges, as identified by the participants, are:

- 1) Lack of time, cost of ERM and human resources
- 2) Lack of an Enterprise-wide risk culture
- 3) Lack of understanding of ERM adoption benefits and its value-driven
- 4) Lack of in-house competencies in the ERM topic
- 5) Lack of support from top management
- 6) Lack of practical adoption guidelines
- 7) Lack of clear strategic direction
- 8) Lack of technology

Since the knowledge of the challenges associated with ERM adoption in the literature is scarce from a development market perspective (Saiedi *et al.*, 2019), the research findings will help bridge the existing knowledge gap.

The following section will address the fourth objective.

Objective Four: *To validate the proposed ERM framework*

The main focus of this objective was to investigate how the adoption framework developed in chapter three based on the literature review has changed in light of the empirical findings of the research. The proposed framework represented in Chapter Three, figure 3.4, has been derived from theoretical and empirical research contributions. Its key aim was to address the existing gaps in the literature that have evidenced the need for a framework that provides organisations with a clearer understanding of how to align ERM to the internal and external factors across the organisation. Accordingly, the researcher initially defined the key applicable

organisational elements considered fundamental to aligning ERM (Chapter Three), then validated their significance through the empirical findings (Chapter Five).

The empirical findings of this research have provided a clearer understanding of the key factors of ERM, the importance of aligning ERM with the key organisational areas, and the effect of internal environment, roles and responsibilities, organisational structures and many other factors based on which the organisation could build its future risk strategy in order to achieve a sustainable future.

The following section will discuss the fifth objective of the research five.

Objective Five: *To propose practical guidance on the adoption of the proposed framework*

The fifth and final research objective was designed to provide practical guidance for adopting the proposed ERM framework after its validation by adding the perspectives of the empirical findings. This objective was achieved through the empirical findings that have added insights to the proposed ERM adoption framework developed in chapter three, section 3.4, and validated in chapter six.

7.3 Contributions of the Research

This research contributes to the theory and practice in several ways. The following sections will present the research contribution to the theory and the practice.

7.4 Contribution To the theory

- This empirical research contributes to the body of knowledge by adding an in-depth understanding of ERM adoption in the Algerian insurance industry.
- This research also contributes to the body of knowledge by addressing the gap existing in the empirical research by focusing on identifying industry-

specific adoption barriers through the combination of academic and empirical findings.

- It contributes further by proposing an ERM adoption framework which is tailored to the specific needs of the Algerian insurance industry, along with practical guidance for its effective adoption.
- Despite being specific to the context studied in this research, the components of the proposed ERM adoption framework can be slightly customised to the needs of firms operating in other industries.

7.5 Contribution to Practice

The findings of this research have many implications for future practices. Each contribution is stated below:

- **Insurance firms operating in Algeria:** The findings of this research study support previous academic and industry suggestions made by regulators, the Big Four, and other international bodies about the importance and the benefits of enterprise risk management (ERM) adoption and implementation. Though this research focuses on a single company to collect the empirical data, findings urge senior executives (CFO et al.) in the Algerian insurance industry to transform their traditional risk management practices into ERM to create more value for the business. Moreover, this research proposes an ERM adoption framework highlighting the most important factors of an effective ERM in the insurance industry. These factors can be taken into consideration by the top management when implementing ERM.
- **Future ERM implementers and senior managers:** The present research highlights the challenges associated with ERM adoption as perceived by high-level managers. These findings provide a clearer understanding of the factors to consider

and improve by future implementers and senior executives of other insurance firms. Also, the primary findings of the research may support other firms that have considered or initiated the adoption of an ERM but did not proceed due to the lack of information about the components of an effective ERM or the factors to consider and improve prior to its adoption.

- **Regulatory Bodies:** Empirical findings will help policymakers and regulators in the Algerian insurance industry identify areas that require development in the risk management policies that should be reviewed imminently.
- **Risk culture policy:** The findings of the previous academic and industry publications and the empirical findings of this research reveal explicitly that an enterprise-wide risk culture within an organisation has a significant implication towards the effectiveness of ERM adoption and implementation. Therefore, findings are relevant for both future adopters of ERM and policymakers.

7.6 Limitations of the research

According to Simon and Goes (2013), the limitations of any research are important. They should be discussed and addressed in detail to mark the research's boundaries and obstacles. The major limitation encountered while conducting the present research was attributed to the topic studied in Algeria, particularly in the insurance industry. Time was another limitation, as the researcher was challenged by completing the research within a defined time frame.

Case study as a research strategy

One of the limitations of the research can be attributed to the research strategy adopted for the research. The current research was conducted focusing on a single case study. Thus, the study's outcomes reflect a single organisational perspective, Cash Assurance, Algeria;

therefore, the findings are limited. Further studies should include a larger sample of organisations to outline a comparison.

Geographical context

Another limitation of the research is attributed to the geographical location where the research is conducted, which can limit the scope of the findings concerning generalisation. The study used a small sample size; therefore, findings cannot be generalised beyond the context studied.

Moreover, the researcher has considered only one developing country, Algeria, to investigate the adoption of ERM. Therefore, it is useful for future research, which can consider comparative studies and examine the phenomena in another developing country within the insurance industry context.

Nevertheless, conducting the study in a single developing country has enabled the researcher to scrutinise the phenomena in more detail and within a specific industry context, allowed the conceptualisation of the subject studied in general and provided directions for future comparative studies.

Another study limitation was that manual thematic analysis involved coding manually unstructured data to arrive at more structured data. Not using NVIVO software could, to some extent, impact the study, as manual thematic analysis was time-consuming.

Further limitations experienced during the completion of the present study were:

- **Limited sample size:** The research used a small sample of respondents (25 participants). However, the high profile of the individuals interviewed can justify the relatively small sample used.
- **Research design limitations:** The present research used a mono-research design, which is a qualitative design. The lack of quantitative data is a possible

limitation, and perhaps using a mixed design would help gain more insights into the research problem.

With regards to enhancing the quality of the interpretive philosophy adopted for the research and in an attempt to enhance and ensure the validity and reliability of the findings, using an interview guide and the debriefing technique set the tone of the interview. It permitted the verification of the results obtained. Thus, building the interview questionnaire on a sound theoretical foundation has helped ensure that relevant data that helps achieve the research objectives set in Chapter 1 has helped enhance the credibility of the findings.

Internal validity of the findings was enhanced through the use of the purposive sampling technique, targeting the most informed individuals at the organisation about the phenomenon explored, which has helped achieve meaningful analysis of the qualitative data gathered. Furthermore, adopting the purposive sampling technique assisted the researcher in identifying patterns through the organisation studied, improving the reliability of the findings.

7.7 Recommendations and directions for future research

As demonstrated throughout the research, the literature on ERM lacked clear, practical guidance that is particular to the firms operating in the insurance industry, specifically in the Algerian context. Moreover, the findings of the research, being exploratory, provide a starting point for future research on several themes related to the topic of ERM within and beyond the insurance industry in Algeria. Therefore, the following areas deserve to be investigated further to surround the shortcomings and limitations of the current research more easily.

- **The first recommendation** of the research is to develop the proposed ERM framework further: future research should explore its applicability in industries other than insurance by studying, for instance, an organisation in the airline,

manufacturing, or healthcare sector. This would provide insights into how adopting the proposed framework may vary across organisations and industries.

- Moreover, Since the current research is qualitative, the researcher recommends that future research be more quantitative in nature and use a larger sample to achieve greater generalisability of the results.
- The researcher further recommends that future research could focus on investigating the qualities and components of ERM that are critical to the effective adoption of the proposed framework, such as creating a consistent and strong enterprise-wide risk culture or exploring how the adoption and implementation of the proposed framework can add value to the organisation. Also, the researcher recommends, where possible, measuring the value associated with all the ERM aspects, including its benefits, potential challenges, and limitations.

7.8 Conclusions of the Research

This chapter summarised the research, examined how every research objective was met, discussed the theoretical and practical implications, and ultimately provided several recommendations for future research—the research aimed to develop an industry-specific ERM adoption framework for insurance firms in a specific geographical area.

Several conclusions can be drawn from the present research and will be summarised in this section. Based on our literature review, the researcher concludes that ERM is still understudied and that little research has been completed that exclusively relates to ERM in the context of developing countries.

The researcher further concludes that defining ERM remains an issue across organisations in different industries. Top management is still struggling to understand what an

ERM can bring to their organisation, its benefits, how it can be embedded into the organisational structure and how to sustain an effective ERM adoption and implementation.

This research has demonstrated the relevance of coping with uncertainty for organisations operating within the insurance industry, given the nature of their operations, which are challenged by various risks and hazards.

ERM has developed significantly over the past two decades, impacting organisations' identity by affecting their governance process. However, despite this significant progress, most contributions to the academic and industry literature remain descriptive rather than offering clear guidance and practical directions on ERM. This research revealed that defining ERM is still an issue across different industries. The gaps identified following the review of the literature demonstrated that little is known about how to establish a strong and consistent risk culture that supports ERM adoption; ambiguity regarding the importance of aligning ERM with strategy and decision-making process; scarcity of practical guidelines on how ERM should be adopted and execute; uncertainty surrounding what constitutes an ERM concept leading to deficiency in the allocation of resources, lack of top management support, also lack of management confidence in the risk management practices. Organisations cannot achieve ERM benefits if these problems are not tackled effectively. Furthermore, since the literature on ERM is still scarce regarding the need for practical guidance, the researcher suggested the development of an adoption framework specific to the Algerian insurance organisations to overcome the limitations of the present literature. Moreover, this has a greater implication for the management, which is in greater need of clear, practical guidance that directs ERM adoption.

The broad implication of the present research is that the widely existing and adopted frameworks have been evaluated, detailing different authors' analysis of the shortcomings of each framework reviewed, concluding with the need for a more comprehensive, practical

response to a specific geographical context's external and internal environment of the Algerian insurance industry.

Accordingly, the proposed framework aims to assist insurance firms operating in Algeria in upgrading their current risk management practices and to cope with their dynamic internal and external environments by aligning the key factors with their strategic risk approach. The main aim of the proposed framework is to improve organisational performance by reducing the volatility of the risk portfolio and increasing the probability of profitability. It further aims to assist organisations in managing upside risks with negative effects on their performance by enhancing techniques used to achieve organisational objectives.

The qualitative paradigm was considered most appropriate in conducting this research, as it matches the researcher's philosophical beliefs (ontological and epistemological stances). Thus, a single case study research strategy has been adopted for data collection due to time constraints and resources. Findings revealed that the insurance firm studied still adopts traditional risk management methods to tackle risks, and ERM adoption is still early. Furthermore, findings regarding key challenges to ERM adoption align with the literature reviewed in chapters two and three. Most participants agree that top management's commitment to ERM is critical to its success. Thus, the findings also identified risk culture as a crucial enabler of ERM's effective integration and adoption. Thus, most participants admit that the lack of in-house ERM experts may limit the effectiveness of ERM adoption.

Surprisingly, in contrast to the findings of the literature where ERM adoption across the insurance industry in Western countries has been mainly responding to regulatory scrutiny and compliance, the findings of the present research revealed that there is no regional regulation or compliance developed in Algeria regarding ERM.

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Appendix

Ethical approval Letter

24/10/2019

Dear Nehla Bouachria,

Your application 8734: EXPLORING BARRIERS TO ERM IMPLMENETATION WITHIN AN ALGERIAN INSURANCE, submission 7265, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Research Participant information sheet

Title of the research: Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). Developing an ERM adoption framework for the Algerian Insurance Industry.

Researcher: Miss Nehla Bouachria

Institution: The University of the west of Scotland-London Campus.

Contact details of the researcher: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

My name is Nehla Bouachria. I am studying towards a Doctorate of Business Administration in the UK For the purpose of the study I am trying to gather information from people with relevant experience that would help me achieve the aim of my research. Because of your position and experience in the risk management, I would like to request you if you could please participate in this interview. The interview will last between 35 to 45 minutes' maximum and it will be a qualitative semi-structured face to face interview or over the phone as per your convenience and availability and the questions will be related to your experience with risk management. The interview will include a set of questions and cover three areas: 1) The adoption Level of ERM 2) ERM adoption Motivators and challenges 3) Discussion about the components of the framework that I am recommending.

As a research student, I have to follow an ethical code as per the university of the West of Scotland rules and therefore I would like to assure you that all the information and

data that you will be providing me with will be treated with high confidentiality and will be stored in a password secured file in my computer which is accessible by a password as well as your identity will remain confidential as per your choice.

Your participation is voluntary and as a participant you have the full right to withdraw from the study at any time without any given reasons.

By signing below, I am giving my consent to take part in the above-mentioned research as it has been described to me in the information sheet and in discussion with miss Nehla Bouachria.

Signed:.....

Name:.....

Date:.....